

Data S1. List of the 322 nuclear validated core genes used in the phylogenomic analyses of the studied *Brachypodium* and outgroup samples. Information on *Brachypodium* gene identity (ID; *Brachypodium* database), gene annotation results from SwissProt and Ensemble Genomes databases, and gene description from SwissProt, are indicated for each gene.

ID of gene (this study)	SwissProt			Ensembl Genomes (EG44)			gene description (SwissProt)
	Identity (%)	E-value	id	Identity (%)	E-value	id	
100065_c35185	90.092	0	Q10SC8	99.113	0	KQK23877	CIPK9_ORYSJ CBL-interacting protein kinase 9
100128_c35206	75.492	0	Q9LVD9	99.588	0	KQK14360	DTX40_ARATH Protein DETOXIFICATION 40
100174_c37800	43.192	2.01E-84	F4J3R7	97.783	0	PNT76512	SPD1_ARATH Protein SEEDLING PLASTID DEVELOPMENT 1
100177_c27057	71.595	0	Q9C512	99.027	0	KQJ84444	MNS1_ARATH Mannosyl-oligosaccharide 1,2-alpha-mannosidase MNS1
100247_c34971	48.03	2.09E-111	F4I8I0	94.881	0	KQK10855	SUN4_ARATH SUN domain-containing protein 4
100433_c38261	61.128	3.04E-137	Q9SX20	92.683	0	KQK18670	PTR18_ARATH Protein NRT1/ PTR FAMILY 3.1
100471_c17252	41.62	3.20E-121	P81898	95.522	0	KQK06405	PNAAL_PRUDU Peptide-N4-(N-acetyl-beta-glucosaminy)l-asparagine amidase A
100491_c34465	94.909	1.09E-165	Q10S58	97.887	3.30E-176	KQK23790	SAT2_ORYSJ Probable serine acetyltransferase 2
100546_c28312	50	9.82E-73	Q0WVK7	97.706	1.95E-152	HORVU2Hr1G046710.3	PPR12_ARATH Pentatricopeptide repeat-containing protein At1g05670, mitochondrial
100632_c70104	37.5	9.20E-26	Q55BK0	99.016	0	KQK08205	UFD1_DICDI Ubiquitin fusion degradation protein 1 homolog
100693_c25007	92.093	1.32E-115	O22380	100	3.33E-122	KQJ93749	CADH_LOLPR Probable cinnamyl alcohol dehydrogenase
100870_c36848	68.563	2.16E-168	Q9SII6	97.326	0	KQK16654	PIX13_ARATH Probable serine/threonine-protein kinase PIX13
100945_c32632	96.831	0	B8BB68	100	0	KQJ95194	BAK1_ORYSI LRR receptor kinase BAK1
100966_c25470	73.856	1.50E-73	Q84VX4	97.814	7.02E-123	KQK13565	MPS1_ARATH Serine/threonine-protein kinase MPS1
100996_c35916	58.421	5.06E-73	Q5XF57	98.077	3.14E-134	KQJ95791	Y5576_ARATH Probable receptor-like serine/threonine-protein kinase At5g57670
101053_c36587	86.711	0	Q0DLB9	99.668	0	KQK08041	RH17_ORYSJ DEAD-box ATP-dependent RNA helicase 17
101207_c33326	57.418	1.56E-153	Q9LFAQ0	94.375	0	KQJ95041	GT14B_ARATH Beta-glucuronosyltransferase GlcAT14B
101281_c36814	72.973	1.55E-96	Q9FFE6	100	2.68E-143	OGLUM04G29340.1	AAE5_ARATH Probable acyl-activating enzyme 5, peroxisomal
101324_c27023	96.629	0	Q0DCT8	99.44	0	KQK18564	G11A_ORYSJ Protein kinase G11A
101368_c37945	79.634	0	Q39817	99.22	0	KQK02438	CALX_SOYBN Calnexin homolog
101695_c33591	53.005	6.31E-59	O22056	98.936	3.14E-122	KQK22365	SIGB_ARATH RNA polymerase sigma factor sigB
101731_c34879	38.953	4.91E-27	Q9LDD4	97.625	0	KQK10618	ARID2_ARATH AT-rich interactive domain-containing protein 2
101758_c24293	39.669	1.21E-31	Q9SY60	96.825	1.24E-101	BGIOGA024066-PA	EX84C_ARATH Exocyst complex component EXO84C
101870_c37290	-	-	-	99.065	3.97E-111	KQK22359	-
101908_c35641	85.857	0	Q9SWW5	99.004	0	KQK18782	PCS1_WHEAT Glutathione gamma-glutamylcysteinyltransferase 1
102229_c29432	47.354	1.08E-120	Q8GYE0	98.652	0	KQK20513	PHF1_ARATH SEC12-like protein 1
102319_c39933	73.649	5.77E-160	Q8LED9	99.661	0	KQK11068	CXE16_ARATH Probable carboxylesterase 16
102348_c17293	85.77	0	Q9SZJ5	99.213	0	KQK13310	GLYM1_ARATH Serine hydroxymethyltransferase 1, mitochondrial
102509_c24408	71.751	0	Q84XU2	99.793	0	KQK03219	PPP5_ARATH Serine/threonine-protein phosphatase 5
102699_c35083	56.404	8.51E-167	Q9MA87	98.639	0	KQJ93522	OFT23_ARATH O-fucosyltransferase 23

102767_c29192	-	-	-	96.552	1.96E-165	KQJ85842	-
102863_c29425	95.339	6.60E-136	Q10N79	98.729	2.73E-144	KQK22302	ARGJ_ORYSJ Arginine biosynthesis bifunctional protein ArgJ, chloroplastic
103105_c37405	61.732	5.64E-157	Q93YN1	95.25	0	PNT65960	CRPK1_ARATH Cold-responsive protein kinase 1
103128_c28430	36.923	1.18E-32	P48758	96.447	2.55E-138	KQK11336	CBR1_MOUSE Carbonyl reductase [NADPH] 1
103136_c37124	40.909	6.94E-49	Q9C9V6	77.011	2.25E-92	KQK00153	Y1790_ARATH BTB/POZ domain-containing protein At1g67900
103171_c31304	40.04	4.43E-104	Q9SCP6	96.97	0	KQJ83659	U73D1_ARATH UDP-glycosyltransferase 73D1
103289_c29065	-	-	-	98.84	0	KQK00125	-
103297_c30760	92.105	0	B9F3B6	99.342	0	KQJ93575	SSDH_ORYSJ Succinate-semialdehyde dehydrogenase, mitochondrial
103407_c38565	31.405	5.63E-24	Q9SIT7	97.692	6.76E-161	PNT70820	PP151_ARATH Pentatricopeptide repeat-containing protein At2g13600
103486_c30978	85.358	0	Q8LPJ5	98.447	0	KQJ83487	ICDHP_ARATH Isocitrate dehydrogenase [NADP], chloroplastic/mitochondrial
103719_c70411	77.593	0	Q84KI6	98.758	0	KQK06534	SQD1_SPIOL UDP-sulfoquinovose synthase, chloroplastic
103771_c38054	88.718	0	Q6K638	97.436	0	KQK00300	HCT2_ORYSJ Hydroxycinnamoyltransferase 2
103826_c27290	21.023	2.52E-09	Q8BRG8	99.492	1.56E-141	KQK22179	TM209_MOUSE Transmembrane protein 209
103828_c33242	37.5	4.24E-21	Q589Y0	98.969	3.69E-99	PNT69451	MAT1_TOBAC Phenolic glucoside malonyltransferase 1
103906_c31047	25.839	4.33E-14	Q9ZPS1	97.347	0	KQJ90061	FB94_ARATH Putative F-box protein At2g02030
103934_c39029	74.432	6.54E-61	O64761	100	2.66E-102	TRITD6Av1G144210.1	PIGC_ARATH Phosphatidylinositol N-acetylglucosaminyltransferase subunit C
103998_c35404	50.916	2.80E-132	Q9FLD5	96.715	0	KQJ85594	ASD_ARATH AAA-ATPase ASD, mitochondrial
104072_c32819	71.883	0	Q9LV16	99.458	0	KQK12626	B3GTJ_ARATH Hydroxyproline O-galactosyltransferase GALT6
104089_c32175	76.558	0	Q9FGK3	99.405	0	KQK15494	MO25N_ARATH Putative MO25-like protein At5g47540
104173_c36217	100	0	Q6H849	100	0	BGIOSGA008680-PA	NRL4_ORYSJ Bifunctional nitrilase/nitrile hydratase NIT4
104260_c24970	93.766	0	Q69QJ7	100	0	KQJ90291	MGDG1_ORYSJ Probable monogalactosyldiacylglycerol synthase 1, chloroplastic
104286_c22159	70.052	0	Q9LPV9	96.758	0	KQJ99665	LWD1_ARATH WD repeat-containing protein LWD1
104333_c30896	-	-	-	99.074	0	PNT76105	-
104394_c37671	66.193	5.67E-169	Q9SAL0	99.468	0	KQJ94978	RGLG4_ARATH E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase RGLG4
104400_c33367	64.784	1.32E-135	Q8VZJ9	99.045	0	KQK23643	CRCK2_ARATH Calmodulin-binding receptor-like cytoplasmic kinase 2
104560_c35398	73.228	1.54E-111	Q8L4R0	99.608	3.57E-148	KQJ83956	TGD1_ARATH Protein TRIGALACTOSYLDIACYLGLYCEROL 1, chloroplastic
104658_c24006	88.158	0	Q9FMR9	100	0	KQK10483	RIN1_ARATH RuvB-like protein 1
104969_c39614	80.362	0	A3F5L3	95.866	0	KQK01024	DES2_SORBI Fatty acid desaturase DES2
105249_c36817	64.948	3.45E-35	Q9FJ81	98.969	6.92E-61	KQJ97512	CCB2_ARATH Protein COFACTOR ASSEMBLY OF COMPLEX C SUBUNIT B CCB2, chloroplastic
105293_c26472	43.75	1.35E-20	Q8S9J6	94.531	1.52E-61	KQJ95841	ASPA_ARATH Aspartyl protease family protein At5g10770
105327_c33414	-	-	-	96.386	0	PNT74819	-
105386_c30856	83.08	0	Q5Z5R4	99.138	0	KQK17910	C7016_ORYSJ Ent-kaurene oxidase 2
105421_c37353	-	-	-	94.366	1.40E-89	KQJ98985	-
105621_c15517	64.334	0	Q8GT20	99.111	0	KQJ97350	BEBT_TOBAC Benzyl alcohol O-benzoyltransferase
105651_c38782	69.231	8.88E-45	O80642	100	1.73E-69	HORVU3Hr1G013720.1	PGTB1_ARATH Geranylgeranyl transferase type-1 subunit beta
105679_c38534	35.277	1.15E-59	D3UAG7	94.277	0	KQK09608	U88F3_PYRCO UDP-glycosyltransferase 88F3
105725_c30094	44.231	2.73E-14	Q69SP5	97	1.13E-59	KQK06307	EREC1_ORYSJ LRR receptor-like serine/threonine-protein kinase ER1

105728_c31115	89.051	0	Q8L5U0	98.54	0	TRITD4Bv1G156790.2	CSN4_ARATH COP9 signalosome complex subunit 4
105750_c35595	-	-	-	98.976	0	KQK01694	-
105833_c4836	86.873	9.39E-162	Q9LDU6	98.473	0	KQJ99405	ST7R_ARATH 7-dehydrocholesterol reductase
105841_c33930	65.574	3.71E-88	Q66GS2	100	5.71E-142	KQK07104	B3GTC_ARATH Probable beta-1,3-galactosyltransferase 12
105846_c36859	41.096	4.06E-09	A2BIJ3	95.189	7.96E-142	KQK14922	BSDC1_DANRE BSD domain-containing protein 1
105893_c35914	39.819	1.58E-39	Q55DL2	87.821	4.67E-167	TRIDC5AG030740.1	MET18_DICDI Histidine protein methyltransferase 1 homolog
106233_c38246	54.671	1.50E-103	Q7XJE6	96.842	0	KQK21440	MCA1_ARATH Metacaspase-1
106386_c28547	-	-	-	84.091	4.83E-59	KN539730.1_FGP008	-
106413_c36952	-	-	-	91.525	9.36E-109	HORVU2Hr1G099250.1	-
106643_c24140	46.488	1.53E-58	O65896	100	6.94E-173	KQK09442	CDA1_ARATH Cytidine deaminase 1
106661_c34261	93.243	0	Q6Z5N4	99.73	0	KQK02000	ODPA1_ORYSJ Pyruvate dehydrogenase E1 component subunit alpha-1, mitochondrial
106985_c22209	75.895	0	O82533	100	0	KQJ82505	FTZ21_ARATH Cell division protein FtsZ homolog 2-1, chloroplastic
107139_c17566	38.278	1.85E-29	Q9ZUZ6	99.01	0	KQK13982	WTF9_ARATH Protein WHAT'S THIS FACTOR 9, mitochondrial
107733_c33247	52.328	2.07E-170	Q9LUC6	95.455	0	KQK08850	C7A14_ARATH Cytochrome P450 72A14
107805_c30549	86.89	0	Q10D80	100	0	PNT74180	CCH11_ORYSJ Cyclin-H1-1
107872_c27097	59.343	2.91E-166	Q6PQJ9	98.485	0	KQK14406	5BPOR_DIGLA 3-oxo-Delta(4,5)-steroid 5-beta-reductase
108306_c29439	49.721	7.45E-51	Q8RWH9	98.824	1.45E-107	KQJ90494	NUP58_ARATH Nuclear pore complex protein NUP58
108365_c26521	89.888	4.76E-32	Q7XLY8	99.02	1.22E-44	KQJ84301	ATL41_ORYSJ E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase Os04g0590900
108514_c31253	52.901	7.26E-105	Q8L7Z0	92.814	0	KQK01078	CNG17_ARATH Cyclic nucleotide-gated ion channel 17
108532_c36259	78.161	6.19E-88	Q8H0W0	100	5.25E-113	KQJ92910	LPA3_ARATH Protein LOW PSII ACCUMULATION 3, chloroplastic
108571_c28305	93.009	0	Q10PP8	99.088	0	KQK22713	MTP4_ORYSJ Metal tolerance protein 4
108599_c28282	34.263	3.07E-35	A1RYE4	98.868	0	KQK20200	GYAR_THEPD Glyoxylate reductase
108696_c30417	68.75	6.63E-98	Q8VYV9	98	0	KQJ81954	APF1_ARATH Aspartyl protease family protein 1
108808_c28097	73.16	4.93E-125	Q93YN1	99.138	2.99E-169	TraesCS2D02G463100.1	CRPK1_ARATH Cold-responsive protein kinase 1
108974_c33377	58.547	4.27E-77	Q8VYH6	97.899	6.33E-136	KQJ99062	B651B_ARATH Cytochrome b561 and DOMON domain-containing protein At4g17280
109023_c34226	41.86	4.55E-33	Q8RX01	82.716	6.75E-99	TraesCS7D02G055900.1.cds1	Y3567_ARATH BTB/POZ domain-containing protein At3g05675
109456_c31426	29.151	1.13E-16	Q6DHN0	100	0	PNT65814	TMM53_DANRE Transmembrane protein 53
109471_c27285	85.784	0	Q75GK4	97.772	0	KQK14076	CIPK7_ORYSJ CBL-interacting protein kinase 7
109475_c32054	82.515	0	P49730	98.471	0	KQK20574	RIR2_TOBAC Ribonucleoside-diphosphate reductase small chain
109765_c35611	89.958	1.40E-163	Q40784	100	1.42E-177	KQJ95730	AAPC_CENCI Putative glucose-6-phosphate 1-epimerase
109837_c23943	91.163	6.13E-131	Q6K439	100	1.64E-141	KQJ86970	PAP2_ORYSJ Probable plastid-lipid-associated protein 2, chloroplastic
109914_c24454	73.333	5.20E-26	Q9M2S3	73.288	1.83E-56	KQK22376	AHL15_ARATH AT-hook motif nuclear-localized protein 15
109918_c21893	57.812	4.88E-139	Q6GKV1	99.068	0	KQK02828	GET4_ARATH Protein GET4
110014_c35659	77.011	9.71E-31	Q9FN42	98.851	4.62E-42	Zm00001d002969_P001	CLPP2_ARATH ATP-dependent Clp protease proteolytic subunit 2, mitochondrial
110087_c37750	54.589	4.21E-65	Q7XJE6	97.642	3.50E-142	KQK21446	MCA1_ARATH Metacaspase-1
110296_c29187	34.574	4.51E-26	Q9QXN3	100	0	KQJ90222	TRIP4_MOUSE Activating signal cointegrator 1
110566_c25564	50	2.88E-81	Q84XV2	98.256	0	BGIOSGA022262-PA	GTE1_ARATH Transcription factor GTE1

110653_c33612	56.684	1.44E-123	P46086	93.766	0	ORUFI10G06310.2	KIME_ARATH Mevalonate kinase
110848_c37690	88.012	0	Q0JBZ6	100	0	PNT61393	MRS2C_ORYSJ Magnesium transporter MRS2-C
110940_c27653	52.432	7.42E-48	A2X052	87.654	1.81E-66	OMERI02G00700.3	ATG5_ORYSI Autophagy protein 5
111010_c29888	67.881	5.92E-139	Q941F1	100	0	KQK06501	PLA15_ARATH Phospholipase A1-Igama1, chloroplastic
111154_c38287	64.045	4.01E-34	Q9M1S3	98.819	8.70E-178	KQK17627	ARP1_ARATH Probable RNA-binding protein ARP1
111627_c39128	38.281	6.33E-53	Q54PM7	98.227	0	KQJ94951	NAGK_DICDI N-acetyl-D-glucosamine kinase
112152_c25636	72.587	2.80E-140	Q9FVR6	99.621	0	KQJ82405	Y1222_ARATH Uncharacterized protein At1g32220, chloroplastic
112186_c28315	77.826	5.35E-131	O81884	99.565	7.85E-169	KQJ86719	GALDH_ARATH L-galactose dehydrogenase
112385_c26285	39.665	1.77E-35	Q5D013	99.567	5.62E-171	KQK02459	EFMT2_DANRE EEF1A lysine methyltransferase 2
112421_c23759	35.897	1.24E-14	Q43468	70.968	3.14E-146	KQJ85633	HSOP1_SOYBN Hsp70-Hsp90 organizing protein 1
112877_c25887	60.174	6.67E-149	Q9FKJ0	98.312	0	KQJ84642	FK132_ARATH F-box/kelch-repeat protein At5g60570
113098_c14831	83.6	6.77E-147	Q942D4	95.142	1.04E-169	PNT72784	BURP3_ORYSJ BURP domain-containing protein 3
113100_c23456	88.991	2.03E-83	Q6H5U3	93.578	3.87E-85	KQJ83732	DES1L_ORYSJ Sphingolipid delta(4)-desaturase DES1-like
113203_c24441	84.956	3.43E-52	Q5N7C7	96.46	4.74E-57	KQK10688	LG2_ORYSJ Transcription factor LG2
113329_c32357	78.868	5.04E-147	Q76BW5	96.875	5.62E-173	KQJ95697	XTH8_ORYSJ Xyloglucan endotransglycosylase/hydrolase protein 8
113426_c13412	56.154	3.55E-37	Q9LJR6	95.42	7.80E-72	KQJ97609	PP253_ARATH Putative pentatricopeptide repeat-containing protein At3g25060, mitochondrial
113536_c26797	86.464	0	P80284	96.133	0	KQJ89043	PDI_HORVU Protein disulfide-isomerase
113799_c33370	48.485	1.27E-13	Q9Y3E5	100	1.04E-51	PNT62036	PTH2_HUMAN Peptidyl-tRNA hydrolase 2, mitochondrial
113902_c21285	90.4	3.58E-85	Q7Y0D4	98.4	2.17E-89	KQK13014	TR164_ORYSJ Thioredoxin-like protein HCF164, chloroplastic
114100_c24673	93.393	0	B9FI63	99.104	0	KQK04816	ERA_ORYSJ GTPase ERA-like, chloroplastic
114289_c34927	78.495	1.60E-36	Q8L4N1	89.726	3.13E-66	KQK15836	PHO34_ARATH Universal stress protein PHOS34
114730_c36667	78.344	1.10E-54	Q655V5	97.452	2.37E-61	KQK17051	NFYC4_ORYSJ Nuclear transcription factor Y subunit C-4
114889_c32584	-	-	-	100	2.73E-78	TRIDC4AG013350.1	-
115234_c35250	86.935	1.62E-120	Q6K9N1	95.5	2.69E-133	KQK00394	CKI1_ORYSJ Casein kinase 1
115327_c23587	65.552	5.24E-149	Q8GWU0	97.993	0	KQK08278	PGP2_ARATH Phosphoglycolate phosphatase 2
115440_c25708	-	-	-	98.969	3.97E-61	KQK08391	-
115658_c19965	35.622	7.97E-44	Q9C942	99.149	8.07E-172	PNT72606	CSE_ARATH Caffeoylshikimate esterase
116004_c25468	-	-	-	98.171	7.30E-77	KQJ90581	-
116028_c30284	-	-	-	100	2.16E-67	KQJ81426	-
116160_c29813	76.506	7.17E-62	Q0JKG7	94.323	1.87E-77	KQK09168	IAA5_ORYSJ Auxin-responsive protein IAA5
116302_c28944	36.923	2.58E-06	O48923	95.238	3.16E-34	PNT74474	C71DA_SOYBN Cytochrome P450 71D10
118247_c18729	55.459	6.25E-87	Q946Y7	99.087	9.72E-160	KQJ89278	SYP61_ARATH Syntaxin-61
118419_c21912	88.71	1.36E-67	B4FF80	99.2	1.12E-73	KQK03815	CNR5_MAIZE Cell number regulator 5
118552_c33800	35.426	6.32E-28	Q8C5Q4	97.26	0	KQJ92874	GRSF1_MOUSE G-rich sequence factor 1
119255_c28328	59.848	5.98E-54	Q9SWS1	98.214	1.49E-96	KQJ98104	ACFR2_ARATH Probable transmembrane ascorbate ferrireductase 2
119329_c30409	69.811	6.62E-69	F4IXJ7	100	1.41E-124	KQK18996	MED6_ARATH Mediator of RNA polymerase II transcription subunit 6
119420_c33192	69.231	3.31E-107	Q9XEA1	98.047	2.01E-174	KQK08048	CSSL5_ARATH Protein OSCA1

119583_c21851	66.265	5.06E-33	Q8W3L1	97.872	1.35E-58	KQK07043	MFDR_ARATH NADPH:adrenodoxin oxidoreductase, mitochondrial
119718_c25618	-	-	-	97.287	4.50E-170	KQK20666	-
120059_c26265	41.875	7.53E-43	Q39224	100	5.86E-115	KQK11410	SRG1_ARATH Protein SRG1
120948_c35674	36.735	2.32E-06	Q5R9T9	87.805	2.28E-41	Et_s10075-0.16-1.mrna1	GBP6_PONAB Guanylate-binding protein 6
121407_c27545	71.014	2.47E-68	P49175	97.826	9.15E-98	KQJ83796	INV1_MAIZE Beta-fructofuranosidase 1
121508_c35347	75.41	1.23E-80	Q5N9Q7	87.288	5.29E-100	TRITD1Bv1G202830.2	PTHM_ORYSJ Peptidyl-tRNA hydrolase, mitochondrial
121561_c25782	-	-	-	100	6.98E-108	KQK08626	-
122048_c21995	78.621	1.37E-76	Q9SVD7	96.203	7.59E-107	TRIDC4AG041750.2	UEV1D_ARATH Ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2 variant 1D
122216_c9503	74.699	7.40E-87	Q84WW3	99.497	8.72E-155	PNT72969	VIP2L_ARATH Inositol hexakisphosphate and diphosphoinositol-pentakisphosphate kinase VIP2
122457_c32036	33.469	3.29E-32	Q9SY07	71.721	4.12E-99	KQJ86532	PP302_ARATH Pentatricopeptide repeat-containing protein At4g02820, mitochondrial
123071_c37866	-	-	-	100	1.53E-27	KQK19862	-
125030_c36948	45.333	1.94E-36	Q9GKX6	96.154	5.82E-96	KQK14372	GALM_PIG Galactose mutarotase
126469_c13898	50	6.68E-23	Q9LZ19	98.734	2.12E-49	KQJ92190	PP364_ARATH Pentatricopeptide repeat-containing protein At5g04780, mitochondrial
127370_c17868	77.193	1.85E-55	P42856	98.561	4.22E-70	KQK17053	ZB14_MAIZE 14 kDa zinc-binding protein
127538_c39110	59.155	3.38E-19	Q8VY16	93.846	1.40E-32	KQJ85273	CDP1_ARATH Plastid division protein CDP1, chloroplastic
128199_c35528	37.5	7.08E-10	Q5EAE9	100	2.01E-82	KQK17334	ATL43_ARATH RING-H2 finger protein ATL43
129680_c30483	68.304	4.58E-93	Q9FNL7	97.976	1.87E-172	KQJ97032	PTR3_ARATH Protein NRT1/ PTR FAMILY 5.2
138010_c48758	-	-	-	97.143	3.44E-117	PNT69295	-
150384_c9485	43.902	8.84E-24	Q940H8	95.506	5.08E-52	KQK12726	FRL4B_ARATH FRIGIDA-like protein 4b
170988_c39896	81.818	1.35E-24	O65258	92.727	4.74E-32	Sspon.02G0018620-1A-mRNA-1	BAM2_ARATH Beta-amylase 2, chloroplastic
92912_c37841	66.667	1.65E-26	Q8BKX6	99.766	0	HORVU4Hr1G011510.11	SMG1_MOUSE Serine/threonine-protein kinase SMG1
92924_c40008	27.203	3.00E-20	Q55GD2	96.845	0	KQK03051	Y8328_DICDI Protein DDB_G0268328
92963_c40154	62.903	0	F4I718	98.882	0	KQJ89128	CSI3_ARATH Protein CELLULOSE SYNTHASE INTERACTIVE 3
93005_c39841	70.905	0	Q9SXA1	98.272	0	KQK13612	P4KA1_ARATH Phosphatidylinositol 4-kinase alpha 1
93015_c39718	67.723	0	F4JLS1	98.035	0	KQJ96911	LDL3_ARATH Lysine-specific histone demethylase 1 homolog 3
93024_c38398	-	-	-	93.662	0	KQK09117	-
93041_c35006	91.291	0	Q8LMR2	97.32	0	KQK23926	DCL1_ORYSJ Endoribonuclease Dicer homolog 1
93044_c32261	53.589	0	Q7XZU0	97.983	0	KQK06603	SAC9_ARATH Probable phosphoinositide phosphatase SAC9
93084_c40063	61.686	0	F4IUU4	96.039	0	KQK21044	AIR9_ARATH 187-kDa microtubule-associated protein AIR9
93167_c39585	22.901	4.16E-30	Q9LUI2	99.419	0	BGIOGA035878-PA	NET1A_ARATH Protein NETWORKED 1A
93175_c39120	58.298	0	F4HW51	97.662	0	KQJ96960	CHR20_ARATH Protein CHROMATIN REMODELING 20
93178_c36564	-	-	-	95.122	0	KQK22975	-
93191_c38774	63.855	0	F4HXV6	98.057	0	KQK22825	NU155_ARATH Nuclear pore complex protein NUP155
93198_c36177	66.761	0	Q8LPT9	97.526	0	KQK18353	GWD1_CITRE Alpha-glucan water dikinase, chloroplastic
93218_c37187	77.44	0	Q8LPT1	99.574	0	KQK22291	AB6B_ARATH ABC transporter B family member 6
93237_c39035	40.667	1.38E-102	F4IXE7	94.745	0	KQK13228	IDM1_ARATH Increased DNA methylation 1

93245_c30946	39.294	1.48E-107	Q3EDF8	96.267	0	PNT74492	PPR28_ARATH Pentatricopeptide repeat-containing protein At1g09900
93247_c37224	51.88	1.12E-145	O04539	96.947	0	KQK08164	SNL4_ARATH Paired amphipathic helix protein Sin3-like 4
93263_c37146	36.086	4.85E-92	F4JW79	84.043	0	KQK05519	RDM3_ARATH Protein RNA-directed DNA methylation 3
93349_c39377	-	-	-	96.729	0	KQK01449	-
93355_c29482	67.904	0	F4JGZ1	99.415	0	KQJ97301	MED16_ARATH Mediator of RNA polymerase II transcription subunit 16
93382_c36452	61.103	0	F4JAA5	97.691	0	KQJ93427	SKI2_ARATH DExH-box ATP-dependent RNA helicase DExH11
93497_c35561	37.853	2.99E-30	Q54I39	96.191	0	KQK09398	IST1L_DICDI IST1-like protein
93502_c39766	56.187	0	F4IGA5	99.329	0	KQK22783	NU133_ARATH Nuclear pore complex protein NUP133
93520_c38073	66.879	3.85E-66	Q9FWS1	100	3.49E-147	KQK08882	AUL1_ARATH Auxilin-like protein 1
93543_c34825	43.003	1.72E-72	Q8L840	87.455	8.14E-173	OBART04G13160.1	RQL4A_ARATH ATP-dependent DNA helicase Q-like 4A
93578_c37407	46.018	1.03E-58	O95628	96.085	0	KQJ92644	CNOT4_HUMAN CCR4-NOT transcription complex subunit 4
93600_c38222	59.506	0	F4INY4	96.563	0	PNT72928	HVT1_ARATH DExH-box ATP-dependent RNA helicase DExH6
93630_c35709	57.938	0	Q9M907	88.542	0	KQK20246	PP217_ARATH Pentatricopeptide repeat-containing protein At3g06920
93685_c40190	53.691	5.38E-37	Q6P4R8	97.373	0	KQK07807	NFRKB_HUMAN Nuclear factor related to kappa-B-binding protein
93716_c30923	56.25	9.16E-75	Q9SZL8	97.973	4.26E-160	KQK13910	FRS5_ARATH Protein FAR1-RELATED SEQUENCE 5
93726_c25330	92.677	0	B9EXM2	100	0	KQK08367	CARB_ORYSJ Carbamoyl-phosphate synthase large chain, chloroplastic
93727_c26358	50	2.62E-59	F4I8S3	97.044	2.64E-145	Os05t0392400-01	CLS3_ARATH SNF2 domain-containing protein CLASSY 3
93747_c28807	38.592	4.07E-59	Q5YDB6	96.491	0	KQJ83718	CPL1_ARATH RNA polymerase II C-terminal domain phosphatase-like 1
93854_c34987	62.732	0	Q9LUD7	98.806	0	PNT66265	CALS8_ARATH Putative callose synthase 8
93879_c34115	44.853	7.87E-134	Q9LUM0	98.579	0	KQK21360	FAB1B_ARATH 1-phosphatidylinositol-3-phosphate 5-kinase FAB1B
93899_c35618	22.879	6.46E-22	Q5ZKD5	95.6	0	KQK02054	RRP12_CHICK RRP12-like protein
93967_c38349	52.92	0	Q8GXJ4	83.978	0	KQK15965	GLR34_ARATH Glutamate receptor 3.4
94018_c35272	54.564	3.19E-172	Q0WQW5	99.456	0	KQK20489	PPR85_ARATH Pentatricopeptide repeat-containing protein At1g59720, chloroplastic/mitochondrial
94034_c39684	57.143	4.67E-176	Q9SIW2	100	0	KQJ95950	CHR35_ARATH Protein CHROMATIN REMODELING 35
94071_c36199	74.54	0	O23461	99.398	0	KQJ93282	ARAK_ARATH L-arabinokinase
94106_c38373	86.196	0	Q2QY12	98.669	0	KQJ92384	ACA9_ORYSJ Probable calcium-transporting ATPase 9, plasma membrane-type
94127_c38831	53.078	0	Q8LFN2	97.358	0	KQK20737	Y3037_ARATH Probable inactive leucine-rich repeat receptor-like protein kinase At3g03770
94149_c36595	47.586	1.11E-104	Q9C9U5	98.454	0	KQK18836	SIS8_ARATH Probable serine/threonine-protein kinase SIS8
94173_c39588	69.75	0	F4I116	98.905	0	KQK03525	SYLC_ARATH Leucine--tRNA ligase, cytoplasmic
94177_c33174	78.229	0	Q2QM84	97.896	0	KQJ85792	ARFY_ORYSJ Auxin response factor 25
94265_c30389	93.561	7.09E-176	Q8S0F0	100	0	KQK10961	FH1_ORYSJ Formin-like protein 1
94330_c35811	26.562	1.13E-25	Q0VGW4	96.241	0	KQJ83635	ERMP1_XENLA Endoplasmic reticulum metalloproteinase 1
94421_c38483	41.497	5.86E-98	Q8S9K3	91.285	0	KQK10301	VAR3_ARATH Zinc finger protein VAR3, chloroplastic
94430_c34551	75.163	0	P92943	99.125	0	KQK13684	CLCD_ARATH Chloride channel protein CLC-d
94442_c31077	40	2.46E-07	Q9M347	96.053	0	KQK01645	TRP6_ARATH Telomere repeat-binding protein 6
94460_c40171	55.777	0	F4J3D9	91.562	0	Os07t0570500-01	IDE2_ARATH Insulin-degrading enzyme-like 2

94461_c37889	72.453	0	P92948	98.563	0	KQJ86680	CDC5L_ARATH Cell division cycle 5-like protein
94474_c36570	90.749	0	Q5N7W4	93.074	0	Os01t0911100-01	RH30_ORYSJ DEAD-box ATP-dependent RNA helicase 30
94479_c28724	49.071	1.45E-171	O80933	96.359	0	PNT73167	SCL9_ARATH Scarecrow-like protein 9
94511_c39151	99.816	0	Q53PC7	99.816	0	ORUFI11G04520.1	COPB1_ORYSJ Coatomer subunit beta-1
94512_c39587	79.891	0	Q0D3J9	97.238	0	KQK14595	C3H53_ORYSJ Zinc finger CCCH domain-containing protein 53
94527_c30825	-	-	-	99.023	3.99E-136	KQK04122	-
94563_c24121	45.69	1.69E-21	Q9LER0	100	1.87E-65	KQK01451	PP381_ARATH Pentatricopeptide repeat-containing protein At5g14770, mitochondrial
94634_c40164	-	-	-	100	1.02E-16	PNT71803	-
94808_c36276	-	-	-	88.298	1.08E-67	TRIDC3BG057020.3	-
94812_c40229	89.268	0	Q1EHT7	99.507	0	KQK03654	C3H4_ORYSJ Zinc finger CCCH domain-containing protein 4
94826_c38849	68.794	5.95E-100	Q6KAI0	99.288	2.89E-161	KQK00360	PNP2_ORYSJ Polyribonucleotide nucleotidyltransferase 2, mitochondrial
94868_c36247	88.803	3.17E-156	Q9XGC9	98.456	4.59E-170	KQK14295	MSH2_MAIZE DNA mismatch repair protein MSH2
94904_c39039	27.848	3.86E-08	Q5ZM41	95.331	0	PNT61250	TEX10_CHICK Testis-expressed protein 10 homolog
94920_c35188	92.459	0	Q10MJ1	98.604	0	KQK22007	CGEP_ORYSJ Probable glutamyl endopeptidase, chloroplastic
94941_c23680	65.486	0	Q9SCZ4	98.713	0	KQK21820	FERON_ARATH Receptor-like protein kinase FERONIA
95043_c25833	74.279	0	Q9SSF9	99.758	0	KQJ85601	PP123_ARATH Pentatricopeptide repeat-containing protein At1g74750
95044_c38151	65.842	0	Q9XHM1	98.717	0	KQJ90313	EIF3C_MEDTR Eukaryotic translation initiation factor 3 subunit C
95062_c39169	-	-	-	94.945	0	KQJ83501	-
95078_c33167	69.697	5.76E-63	Q9C5Y0	99.242	3.42E-87	PNT76765	PLDD1_ARATH Phospholipase D delta
95080_c37176	33.696	3.96E-34	A3KGB4	96.838	4.33E-159	KQK05838	TBC8B_MOUSE TBC1 domain family member 8B
95278_c35098	-	-	-	100	1.82E-17	KQK23615	-
95283_c36760	51.62	0	Q1KPV0	98.144	0	KQK06500	FZL_ARATH Probable transmembrane GTPase FZO-like, chloroplastic
95288_c40059	36.534	3.90E-105	Q9FXA9	97.441	0	KQK14961	PPR83_ARATH Putative pentatricopeptide repeat-containing protein At1g56570
95300_c37222	59.403	0	F4JSH1	89.376	0	KQK20651	APY7_ARATH Probable apyrase 7
95314_c39555	-	-	-	98.311	0	PNT68493	-
95339_c40217	73.367	3.97E-175	Q9LX66	94.162	0	KQK21184	HERK_ARATH Receptor-like protein kinase HERK 1
95384_c38540	-	-	-	100	2.53E-129	KQJ89428	-
95470_c31241	71.293	0	Q7XIT1	94.405	0	KQK16335	IRE1_ORYSJ Serine/threonine-protein kinase/endoribonuclease IRE1
95580_c35565	76.667	1.27E-68	Q7FAD5	91.908	1.31E-83	KQJ82914	ZEP1_ORYSJ Synaptonemal complex protein ZEP1
95617_c34504	53.107	2.01E-91	F4K4L7	95.5	0	KQK00582	TAF4B_ARATH Transcription initiation factor TFIID subunit 4b
95629_c35487	-	-	-	96.991	0	KQK09064	-
95648_c37550	-	-	-	78.571	1.76E-144	KQK23699	-
95669_c28862	89.73	7.99E-92	Q10EL1	76.889	2.04E-100	Et_s5807-1.13-1.mrna1	C3H24_ORYSJ Zinc finger CCCH domain-containing protein 24
95744_c31500	59.92	0	Q94BP7	100	0	KQJ91732	AUG6_ARATH AUGMIN subunit 6
95769_c40076	68.421	0	Q8LPQ8	99.502	0	KQJ97606	MSSP2_ARATH Monosaccharide-sensing protein 2
95865_c38260	51.252	1.92E-156	Q9S972	99.599	0	KQK05544	SD16_ARATH Receptor-like serine/threonine-protein kinase SD1-6
95918_c37821	51.982	1.39E-96	Q8LLD0	97.333	0	KQK23395	NUP96_ARATH Nuclear pore complex protein NUP96

95956_c37943	82.215	0	A2YV85	99.688	0	KQJ98274	RH29_ORYSI DEAD-box ATP-dependent RNA helicase 29
95964_c31981	69.221	0	Q9FGN0	99.059	0	KQK17069	COG7_ARATH Conserved oligomeric Golgi complex subunit 7
95989_c32325	87.5	7.61E-93	Q6L545	98.039	1.51E-107	KQK06302	GID1_ORYSJ Gibberellin receptor GID1
96084_c37183	46.626	2.51E-33	Q8RXR2	98.235	2.43E-102	KQJ98826	CLCF_ARATH Chloride channel protein CLC-f
96171_c33946	71.726	0	Q94BR1	100	0	OGLUM08G01470.1	MRF1_ARATH MA3 DOMAIN-CONTAINING TRANSLATION REGULATORY FACTOR 1
96183_c24459	47.701	7.51E-95	P46032	95.77	0	PNT72419	PTR2_ARATH Protein NRT1/ PTR FAMILY 8.3
96288_c39169	32.997	1.25E-43	Q6LA54	98.79	0	KQJ82574	YF48_SCHPO Uncharacterized WD repeat-containing protein C3H5.08c
96312_c37439	38.02	1.63E-101	A7S6A5	99.304	0	ONIVA04G25270.1	SDA1_NEMVE Protein SDA1 homolog
96315_c40001	58.104	1.08E-96	Q0BPG2	97.053	0	KQK07902	IF2_GRABC Translation initiation factor IF-2
96333_c34776	-	-	-	97.398	0	KQJ94583	-
96340_c39945	82.117	0	P53684	94.727	0	KQK23854	CDPK7_ORYSJ Calcium-dependent protein kinase 7
96381_c39534	39.61	6.38E-48	Q9LTY1	93.631	3.21E-168	TRIUR3_12273-P1	MAD1_ARATH Mitotic spindle checkpoint protein MAD1
96397_c32916	90.838	0	Q10LJ0	98.242	0	KQK21716	NCBP1_ORYSJ Nuclear cap-binding protein subunit 1
96474_c36772	42.857	2.19E-09	Q0MW30	97.436	0	PNT75044	NEU1B_MOUSE E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase NEURL1B
96517_c36192	32.468	2.66E-53	Q10MI0	94.472	0	Os01t0898300-01	SRL2_ORYSJ Protein SEMI-ROLLED LEAF 2
96651_c39229	48.148	5.81E-97	Q9SX31	99.604	0	KQK08607	PERK9_ARATH Proline-rich receptor-like protein kinase PERK9
96728_c38318	66.667	6.45E-66	Q3EBL9	97.758	3.15E-123	KQK23229	VP372_ARATH Vacuolar protein-sorting-associated protein 37 homolog 2
96731_c39675	50.909	3.38E-18	Q38796	93.056	0	KQK11394	LUMI_ARATH Homeobox protein LUMINIDEPENDENS
96803_c39628	71.552	6.84E-118	A9LLI7	91.857	0	KQK23561	RP6L2_ARATH Protein RRP6-like 2
96937_c38500	86.32	0	Q9SDG8	100	0	KQK03878	AGO4A_ORYSJ Protein argonaute 4A
97030_c21999	80.263	0	Q688R3	96.765	0	KQK07846	C3H33_ORYSJ Zinc finger CCCH domain-containing protein 33
97082_c35004	76.064	7.28E-92	Q0IP28	95.312	2.28E-120	KQJ91717	LAC25_ORYSJ Laccase-25
97142_c37959	75.694	0	Q0JDM0	99.506	0	KQK04724	C3H27_ORYSJ Zinc finger CCCH domain-containing protein 27
97188_c37114	43.396	1.57E-35	Q76LS9	97.851	0	KQK17516	MINY1_MOUSE Ubiquitin carboxyl-terminal hydrolase MINDY-1
97230_c36219	54.627	1.25E-114	Q0WVV6	96.185	0	KQK12395	CB60D_ARATH Calmodulin-binding protein 60 D
97360_c29758	58.466	1.17E-152	F4JTP5	99.267	0	KQJ92138	STY46_ARATH Serine/threonine-protein kinase STY46
97393_c24767	47.399	8.96E-168	Q8W4B1	95.76	0	KQK18318	RCF3_ARATH RNA-binding KH domain-containing protein RCF3
97407_c32626	22.439	4.16E-10	Q96301	97.196	0	KQK11097	SPY_ARATH Probable UDP-N-acetylglucosamine--peptide N-acetylglucosaminyltransferase SPINDLY
97412_c37214	57.377	2.34E-15	Q84K00	97.446	0	KQJ94670	NAC78_ARATH NAC domain-containing protein 78
97415_c34213	49.217	8.18E-109	Q9SIW1	96.87	0	KQK13789	BLH7_ARATH BEL1-like homeodomain protein 7
97535_c36680	36.806	1.57E-87	P93203	97.522	0	KQK03030	MFP1_SOLLC MAR-binding filament-like protein 1
97547_c21232	79.903	0	O23627	100	0	KQJ99172	SYGM1_ARATH Glycine--tRNA ligase, mitochondrial 1
97587_c32286	63.291	2.69E-160	Q8L836	100	0	KQK22669	MA657_ARATH 65-kDa microtubule-associated protein 7
97650_c28588	84.689	0	B9F4I8	95.444	0	KQK01388	LPA1_ORYSJ P-loop NTPase domain-containing protein LPA1
97678_c34175	76.905	0	Q9LU89	99.226	0	KQK12158	2A5N_ARATH Serine/threonine protein phosphatase 2A 59 kDa regulatory subunit B' eta isoform

97696_c39323	31.674	6.11E-08	Q9C9N6	92.617	7.11E-125	KQK09280	PMI2_ARATH Protein PLASTID MOVEMENT IMPAIRED 2
97735_c37560	69.154	4.99E-92	Q9C5E7	70.772	0	KQJ99005	PUM6_ARATH Pumilio homolog 6, chloroplastic
97776_c38769	34.865	3.20E-42	Q9LTA6	98.022	0	PNT69402	WAV3_ARATH E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase WAV3
97785_c70131	69.937	0	Q94BR1	98.101	0	KQJ83210	MRF1_ARATH MA3 DOMAIN-CONTAINING TRANSLATION REGULATORY FACTOR 1
97830_c36821	23.81	3.33E-06	Q498R3	96.136	0	PNT74693	DJC10_RAT DnaJ homolog subfamily C member 10
97860_c36611	50	1.52E-160	Q9C950	99.465	0	KQJ86484	VIP5_ARATH Protein RTF1 homolog
98131_c38723	36.041	5.26E-24	A7IKI9	96	3.24E-138	KQJ91916	TRUA_XANP2 tRNA pseudouridine synthase A
98228_c30397	73.667	1.02E-123	Q5VQL3	100	0	KQK07278	PPT3_ORYSJ Phosphoenolpyruvate/phosphate translocator 3, chloroplastic
98244_c36488	44.762	8.59E-35	Q9H501	76.5	7.31E-152	BGIOSGA025856-PA	ESF1_HUMAN ESF1 homolog
98279_c35100	51.57	0	Q3ECP0	99.502	0	KQJ95401	TFB1A_ARATH General transcription and DNA repair factor IIH subunit TFB1-1
98367_c37934	29.139	6.60E-58	Q9LZD3	99.125	0	Os06t0698600-01	E70A1_ARATH Exocyst complex component EXO70A1
98373_c36345	26.382	4.74E-25	Q3UDW8	96.296	0	KQJ82431	HGNAT_MOUSE Heparan-alpha-glucosaminide N-acetyltransferase
98469_c33716	35.714	1.53E-102	Q9ZPV5	98.96	0	KQJ85696	NOC2L_ARATH Nucleolar complex protein 2 homolog
98470_c34116	40.909	7.08E-14	Q8BZG5	95.575	2.43E-72	TRIDC5BG009060.4	RRNAD_MOUSE Protein RRNAD1
98484_c33441	85.344	0	Q01899	96.992	0	KQK01672	HSP7M_PHAVU Heat shock 70 kDa protein, mitochondrial
98551_c36299	91.031	0	Q6Z690	98.473	0	KQK01792	LDL1_ORYSJ Lysine-specific histone demethylase 1 homolog 1
98731_c40152	23.005	5.46E-16	Q9ZT96	95.808	0	KQJ91473	MTEF4_ARATH Transcription termination factor MTERF4, chloroplastic
98762_c30966	33.559	1.61E-89	Q969N2	97.162	0	KQJ88525	PIGT_HUMAN GPI transamidase component PIG-T
98884_c29609	78.788	0	Q9C9P4	99.536	0	KQK15130	KASC2_ARATH 3-oxoacyl-[acyl-carrier-protein] synthase II, chloroplastic
98912_c36244	79.684	0	Q8RWM2	98.422	0	KQK12258	NPRT1_ARATH Nicotinate phosphoribosyltransferase 1
98971_c31654	32.934	6.73E-55	Q9LL45	97.48	0	KQK22345	TBP1_ORYSJ Telomere-binding protein 1
99055_c38413	54.739	0	F4HTQ1	95.677	0	KQK11067	MPRO1_ARATH Probable thimet oligopeptidase
99067_c33353	48.228	1.74E-158	Q93XX4	98.179	0	KQJ94538	C2D61_ARATH C2 domain-containing protein At1g53590
99109_c30686	26.71	1.00E-08	Q66JA8	98.261	0	KQJ89711	EPC2_XENLA Enhancer of polycomb homolog 2
99148_c26047	51.587	1.69E-151	Q8VYC8	96.964	0	KQK16229	RIN2_ARATH E3 ubiquitin protein ligase RIN2
99172_c33079	78.795	0	Q6Z2W3	100	0	KQJ93247	ARFE_ORYSJ Auxin response factor 5
99182_c38366	30.412	5.14E-28	Q5XI31	78.19	0	KQK11107	PIGS_RAT GPI transamidase component PIG-S
99247_c33208	25.753	5.42E-35	D4AZ24	98.051	0	KQJ90093	ENG1_ARTBC Probable endo-1,3(4)-beta-glucanase ARB_01444
99335_c33361	42.781	4.80E-154	Q681K7	94.426	0	KQJ90428	GEX1_ARATH Protein GAMETE EXPRESSED 1
99449_c38935	-	-	-	89.655	1.37E-105	TRIDC2BG041720.1	-
99486_c29450	72.603	3.77E-103	C6TBN2	94.118	1.97E-136	TraesCS7D02G197100.1	AKR1_SOYBN Probable aldo-keto reductase 1
99587_c26497	44.972	1.08E-153	Q66GP4	97.377	0	KQJ84199	PP379_ARATH Pentatricopeptide repeat-containing protein At5g13770, chloroplastic
99716_c37819	70.466	0	Q9LY87	100	0	KQJ91668	RGLG2_ARATH E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase RGLG2
99821_c25697	55.376	8.86E-67	Q8W034	99.749	0	KQJ87604	RNP1_ARATH Heterogeneous nuclear ribonucleoprotein 1
99843_c28760	90.667	0	Q9AV81	99.467	0	KQJ97010	PRP19_ORYSJ Pre-mRNA-processing factor 19
99849_c35358	43.992	1.42E-143	Q9MA55	100	0	KQK01468	ACBP4_ARATH Acyl-CoA-binding domain-containing protein 4

99985_c30921

73.548

1.04E-116

Q94AN2

87.662

1.86E-144

OB08G10130.1

CHER1_ARATH Choline transporter protein 1

Data S2. Blastn matching analysis of the *B. stacei* TE4.3 and *B. hybridum* BdTR6g nuclear validated core transcript used in this study to the primary transcripts of their respective reference transcriptomes. **(a)** 322 *B. stacei* TE4.3 core transcripts were used as query to match the corresponding primary transcripts of the *B. stacei* ABR114 reference transcriptome. **(b)** 222 *B. hybridum* BdTR6g core transcripts were used as query to match the corresponding primary transcripts of the *B. hybridum* ABR113 reference transcriptome. Values highlighted in bold indicate the best match for each query. In *B. hybridum*, values with red and blue background colors correspond to *B. stacei* and *B. distachyon* subgenomic matches respectively.

(a) *B. stacei*

Query (322 assembled transcripts of <i>B. stacei</i> TE4.3)	Database (all Primary transcripts of <i>B. stacei</i> ABR114)	percentage of identical matches	alignment length (sequence overlap)	number of mismatches	number of gap openings	start of alignment in query	end of alignment in query	start of alignment in subject	end of alignment in subject	expect value	bit score
Bsta_c10001_g1_i2_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G236400.1	99.655	3193	1	4	1	3183	2980	6172	0	5827
Bsta_c10011_g1_i1_Chr10_Bsta	Brast10G023000.1	99.788	2358	1	3	1	2354	1760	4117	0	4324
Bsta_c1004_g1_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G169600.1	97.043	913	0	6	1	886	625	1537	0.00E+00	1511
Bsta_c10050_g1_i2_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G036300.1	98.945	1612	5	3	1	1600	341	1952	0	2872
Bsta_c10138_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G252100.1	99.152	825	1	3	1	819	1159	1983	0	1480
Bsta_c10237_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G126500.1	99.881	838	0	1	1	837	2456	3293	0	1541
Bsta_c10261_g1_i2_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G020400.1	75.443	1128	233	31	100	1210	581	1681	4.22E-143	508
	Brast05G260800.1	99.93	1426	1	0	1	1426	629	2054	0	2628
Bsta_c10314_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G054000.1	99.808	1039	1	1	1	1038	2500	3538	0	1906
Bsta_c10444_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G038300.1	96.443	984	1	19	1	950	2027	3010	0.00E+00	1592
Bsta_c10582_g1_i1_Chr07_Bsta	Brast07G030200.1	98.207	781	0	10	1	767	813	1593	0	1352
Bsta_c10640_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G058900.1	99.666	1199	0	4	1	1195	2246	3444	0	2189
Bsta_c10714_g2_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G185500.1	99.869	765	1	0	1	765	773	9	0	1408
Bsta_c10810_g1_i2_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G302900.1	99.295	567	2	1	1	565	457	1023	0	1024
Bsta_c10818_g1_i2_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G151100.1	93.375	966	2	26	1	904	512	1477	0	1373
Bsta_c10850_g2_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G003400.1	99.659	293	1	0	1	293	642	934	3.71E-152	536
Bsta_c10851_g1_i2_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G066900.1	99.844	642	0	1	1	641	1397	2038	0	1179

Bsta_c10856_g1_i1_Chr07_Bsta	Brast07G239800.1	100	33	0	0	1	33	256	288	1.13E-08	62.1
	Brast07G239800.1	98.058	1133	3	6	32	1145	305	1437	0	1953
Bsta_c10858_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G132600.1	99.814	539	0	1	1	538	140	678	0	989
Bsta_c10874_g2_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G240700.1	99.083	1091	2	3	1	1083	1026	2116	0	1953
Bsta_c1090_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G134900.1	99.67	910	2	1	1	909	1002	1911	0	1663
Bsta_c11020_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G095400.1	99.913	1143	1	0	1	1143	453	1595	0	2106
Bsta_c11219_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G238100.1	96.685	543	0	5	1	525	499	1041	0	887
Bsta_c11361_g2_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast05G210200.1	78.109	571	100	17	292	844	1269	1832	3.52E-92	339
	Brast09G255900.1	95.916	906	0	15	1	869	1031	1936	0	1434
Bsta_c11448_g1_i1_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G144800.1	99.626	535	2	0	1	535	353	887	0	977
Bsta_c11515_g1_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G098800.1	98.646	443	0	6	1	437	475	917	0	780
Bsta_c1157_g1_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G047200.1	99.13	920	1	4	1	913	687	1606	0	1648
Bsta_c11702_g1_i2_Chr07_Bsta	Brast04G209200.1	79.208	3208	640	23	1265	4460	843	4035	0	2204
	Brast07G119600.1	99.697	4627	4	6	1	4618	255	4880	0	8458
Bsta_c11734_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G086800.1	99.607	1783	0	3	7	1782	169	1951	0	3247
Bsta_c11888_g1_i1_Chr03_Bsta	Brast02G035500.1	85.382	1546	222	3	157	1701	131	1673	0.00E+00	1600
	Brast03G144000.1	98.634	2050	2	9	1	2026	7	2054	0	3607
Bsta_c11897_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G057100.1	97.173	849	1	11	1	826	1628	2476	0	1413
Bsta_c12015_g1_i1_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G177800.1	99.725	363	0	1	1	362	195	557	0	664
Bsta_c12117_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G339200.1	99.739	383	0	1	1	382	667	1049	0	701
Bsta_c12264_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G055100.1	99.116	1131	4	2	1	1125	743	1873	0	2028
Bsta_c12345_g1_i2_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G329600.1	97.98	792	1	11	1	777	1440	649	0.00E+00	1360
Bsta_c12518_g1_i1_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G129600.1	100	1279	0	0	1	1279	470	1748	0	2362
Bsta_c12522_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G047600.1	97.059	1224	3	15	1	1191	146	1369	0	2030
Bsta_c12597_g1_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G128800.1	81.465	669	89	18	363	1027	343	980	4.89E-145	516
	Brast06G128900.1	99.53	2767	0	4	1	2754	126	2892	0	5025
Bsta_c12718_g1_i2_Chr07_Bsta	Brast07G104800.1	99.771	1308	2	1	2	1308	561	1868	0	2398
Bsta_c12820_g1_i3_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G284400.1	99.014	913	5	3	1	909	432	1344	0	1633
Bsta_c12876_g1_i2_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G041500.1	99.898	980	1	0	1	980	293	1272	0	1805

Bsta_c12897_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G101400.1	99.759	2074	4	1	3	2075	824	2897	0	3801
Bsta_c12907_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G080500.1	99.093	992	1	5	1	984	426	1417	0	1775
Bsta_c12936_g1_i2_Chr07_Bsta	Brast07G212900.1	99.168	601	0	4	1	596	172	772	0.00E+00	1077
Bsta_c12949_g1_i2_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G239000.1	94.718	549	4	3	1	544	59	587	0	830
Bsta_c12957_g1_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G194800.1	99.125	1714	3	6	1	1702	78	1791	0	3072
Bsta_c13033_g1_i2_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G079500.1	98.831	1967	1	11	1	1945	35	2001	0	3485
Bsta_c13087_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G201600.1	97.623	1220	0	11	127	1318	254	1472	0	2065
	Brast02G201700.1	79.888	890	145	26	363	1238	519	1388	4.77E-177	621
Bsta_c13153_g2_i1_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G137200.1	99.789	3322	6	1	1	3321	2992	6313	0	6095
Bsta_c13277_g1_i1_Chr10_Bsta	Brast10G064900.1	98.977	2346	0	6	1	2322	78	2423	0	4178
Bsta_c13428_g1_i1_Chr07_Bsta	Brast07G150400.1	86.787	1385	183	0	1	1385	71	1455	0	1544
	Brast07G150700.1	98.775	1469	6	3	1	1457	287	1755	0	2603
Bsta_c13462_g1_i1_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G288700.1	99.145	117	0	1	926	1041	2455	2339	3.47E-53	209
	Brast03G288800.1	99.808	1042	1	1	1	1041	2564	3605	0	1912
Bsta_c13533_g1_i3_Chr10_Bsta	Brast10G005800.1	97.831	876	0	9	1	857	1428	553	0	1495
Bsta_c13624_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G401300.1	99.555	898	0	1	1	894	434	1331	0.00E+00	1633
Bsta_c13737_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G225600.1	99.92	2489	1	1	89	2576	696	3184	0	4584
Bsta_c13796_g1_i1_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G070500.1	95.556	540	0	17	1	516	1162	1701	0	843
Bsta_c13811_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G380400.1	98.886	2065	6	8	1	2048	352	2416	0	3670
	Brast06G144400.1	81.756	1321	234	6	309	1624	974	2292	0	1098
Bsta_c13848_g1_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G260300.1	99.798	990	0	2	1	988	1184	2173	0	1816
Bsta_c13855_g2_i3_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G276700.1	99.538	3030	9	3	1	3025	526	3555	0	5513
Bsta_c13941_g1_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G111700.1	99.757	1235	1	1	1	1233	427	1661	0	2263
Bsta_c14075_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G058800.1	99.604	1514	1	4	1	1509	678	2191	0	2758
Bsta_c14140_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G025800.1	98.688	2744	12	12	2	2721	98	2841	0	4846
	Brast02G025900.1	94.444	90	0	2	2637	2721	1473	1384	5.68E-30	134
Bsta_c14172_g2_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G232800.1	97.437	1756	15	9	1	1726	90	1845	0	2966
Bsta_c14201_g1_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G211100.1	98.963	1833	0	6	1	1814	208	2040	0	3262
Bsta_c14261_g1_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G241300.1	98.871	974	0	4	36	998	2891	1918	0.00E+00	1727

Bsta_c14324_g1_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G119500.1	98.566	1883	4	3	1	1860	923	2805	0.00E+00	3306
Bsta_c14325_g1_i2_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G145600.1	99.045	2303	3	8	1	2284	1039	3341	0.00E+00	4113
Bsta_c14383_g1_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G188700.1	98.995	1691	2	9	1	1676	108	1798	0	3014
Bsta_c14484_g1_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G138700.1	98.238	1135	1	13	1	1116	619	1753	0	1967
Bsta_c14635_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G239200.1	98.3	1353	7	5	1	1337	195	1547	0	2357
Bsta_c14801_g1_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G072000.1	99.031	1651	0	6	1	1635	299	1949	0	2946
Bsta_c14807_g2_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G188800.1	98.195	2770	3	7	1	2723	2960	5729	0	4795
Bsta_c14813_g1_i1_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G131700.1	99.472	3218	2	8	1	3203	10	3227	0	5834
	Brast05G131800.1	98.788	3218	11	9	1	3190	81	3298	0	5701
Bsta_c14826_g1_i1_Chr03_Bsta	Brast02G295300.1	86.623	912	103	11	5	897	8	919	0.00E+00	990
	Brast03G061600.1	98.007	903	9	4	5	898	13	915	0	1559
Bsta_c14832_g1_i2_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G232400.1	99.301	2860	2	10	1	2842	4	2863	0	5155
Bsta_c14872_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G166800.1	98.185	1322	5	6	1	1305	4	1323	0	2290
Bsta_c14903_g1_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G068300.1	95.782	2347	7	43	1	2255	289	2635	0.00E+00	3701
Bsta_c14904_g1_i2_Chr07_Bsta	Brast07G088100.1	99.72	1788	0	4	1	1783	2325	538	0	3269
Bsta_c14917_g1_i3_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G207000.1	99.837	2456	2	1	1	2454	3811	6266	0	4512
Bsta_c14918_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G213000.1	99.722	1437	0	4	1	1433	38	1474	0.00E+00	2628
Bsta_c14946_g1_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G137000.1	98.434	1660	0	5	1	1634	412	2071	0	2898
Bsta_c14976_g1_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G031600.1	99.487	974	2	1	2	972	444	1417	0	1768
Bsta_c15013_g1_i2_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G152900.1	98.249	1713	6	7	1	1689	72	1784	0	2976
Bsta_c15092_g1_i1_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G112600.1	99.924	1320	0	1	1	1319	259	1578	0	2431
Bsta_c15144_g1_i1_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G124200.1	99.766	1283	1	2	1	1281	153	1435	0.00E+00	2351
Bsta_c15148_g1_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G019600.1	99.513	1232	1	1	1	1227	237	1468	0	2237
Bsta_c15153_g1_i2_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G246400.1	99.669	905	1	2	1	903	674	1578	0	1653
Bsta_c15192_g6_i2_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G309200.1	99.785	1863	1	2	6	1865	2381	519	0	3415
	Brast04G158600.1	100	29	0	0	1837	1865	522	494	3.11E-06	54.7
Bsta_c15214_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G347600.1	98.892	1805	0	8	1	1785	157	1961	0	3205
Bsta_c15368_g1_i1_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G227300.1	98.456	1943	4	12	1	1920	660	2599	0	3398
Bsta_c15373_g1_i2_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G212000.1	99.724	1085	0	1	1	1082	1649	565	0.00E+00	1984

	Brast09G192000.1	79.331	987	160	27	1	956	1200	227	0	652
Bsta_c15379_g1_i1_Chr07_Bsta	Brast07G125000.1	99.957	2307	0	1	12	2317	1	2307	0	4253
Bsta_c15390_g2_i2_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G179700.1	98.148	810	1	3	1	796	579	1388	0	1400
Bsta_c15392_g1_i4_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G211400.1	99.697	1652	2	1	1	1649	790	2441	0	3020
Bsta_c15414_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G208500.1	97.841	1714	0	16	1	1677	423	2136	0	2926
Bsta_c15425_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G306600.1	99.32	4853	4	16	1	4824	39	4891	0	8752
Bsta_c15455_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G067800.1	99.032	2169	4	8	1	2152	940	3108	0	3873
Bsta_c15489_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G311100.1	98.551	69	0	1	986	1053	1478	1546	1.69E-26	121
	Brast04G311100.1	99.365	945	4	2	1	943	443	1387	0	1711
Bsta_c15575_g1_i1_Chr05_Bsta	Brast04G067500.1	94.813	1928	94	3	1	1923	272	2198	0	3001
	Brast05G139400.1	99.637	1928	2	2	1	1923	704	2631	0	3517
Bsta_c15579_g1_i3_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G031200.1	98.715	934	1	2	1	923	455	1388	0	1648
Bsta_c15690_g1_i1_Chr07_Bsta	Brast04G302700.1	74.911	1682	374	37	2	1654	510	2172	0	725
	Brast07G194200.1	99.128	1720	2	9	1	1707	957	2676	0.00E+00	3081
Bsta_c15707_g1_i2_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G105900.1	95.29	1656	1	29	1	1579	176	1831	0	2555
Bsta_c15733_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G089900.1	96.748	738	1	2	2423	3137	4415	5152	0	1208
	Brast02G089900.1	99.876	2427	0	2	1	2424	1946	4372	0	4462
Bsta_c15818_g1_i2_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G207800.1	73.139	1169	268	38	312	1454	454	1602	1.26E-103	377
	Brast01G208000.1	99.931	1446	1	0	9	1454	231	1676	0	2665
Bsta_c15935_g1_i1_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G280600.1	98.985	1872	2	12	1	1855	889	2760	0	3336
Bsta_c16041_g1_i1_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G163900.1	99.477	4208	3	8	1	4189	233	4440	0	7631
Bsta_c16112_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G100100.1	99.333	3896	2	10	1	3872	618	4513	0	7029
Bsta_c16246_g1_i4_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G219700.1	99.135	1619	1	4	1	1606	64	1682	0	2900
	Brast02G219800.1	75.198	1391	305	36	236	1606	227	1597	5.84E-177	621
Bsta_c16253_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G154700.1	99.699	996	0	3	1	993	1	996	0	1820
	Brast05G202600.1	90.647	1005	76	7	1	993	64	1062	0.00E+00	1319
Bsta_c16269_g2_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G199700.1	98.972	2432	0	13	1	2407	295	2726	0	4329
Bsta_c16288_g1_i3_Chr10_Bsta	Brast10G004000.1	99.493	2168	9	2	1	2166	3181	1014	0	3941
Bsta_c16339_g1_i4_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G063800.1	98.628	1093	0	6	1	1078	403	1495	0.00E+00	1921

	Brast09G197100.1	84.29	732	115	0	1	732	494	1225	0	715
Bsta_c16461_g1_i3_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G086700.1	99.469	1506	0	3	1	1498	1075	2580	0.00E+00	2730
Bsta_c16473_g2_i2_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G206100.1	100	810	0	0	1	810	3404	4213	0	1496
Bsta_c16493_g1_i1_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G185000.1	98.981	2159	0	5	1	2137	645	2803	0	3845
Bsta_c16499_g1_i1_Chr07_Bsta	Brast07G093700.1	99.334	1651	3	6	1	1643	1786	136	0	2981
Bsta_c16572_g1_i2_Chr07_Bsta	Brast07G074800.1	99.687	959	1	2	1	957	196	1154	0	1753
Bsta_c16588_g2_i1_Chr10_Bsta	Brast10G016100.1	98.855	3056	10	14	1	3034	314	3366	0	5426
Bsta_c16635_g1_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G211200.1	99.857	698	1	0	1	698	1090	1787	0	1284
Bsta_c16673_g1_i2_Chr10_Bsta	Brast10G009600.1	98.321	2383	11	8	1	2354	86	2468	0	4152
Bsta_c16701_g1_i3_Chr06_Bsta	Brast02G167400.1	80.73	986	130	43	160	1130	960	1900	0	713
	Brast06G009700.1	95.936	2682	4	40	1	2587	810	3481	0	4252
Bsta_c16750_g2_i4_Chr09_Bsta	Brast08G224500.1	76.42	810	172	16	209	1010	574	1372	1.73E-116	420
	Brast09G133400.1	98.071	1244	1	8	1	1221	399	1642	0.00E+00	2143
Bsta_c16762_g1_i2_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G065900.1	100	1247	0	0	248	1494	264	1510	0	2303
Bsta_c16833_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G053400.1	99.34	1819	4	6	1	1811	125	1943	0	3286
Bsta_c16857_g1_i2_Chr10_Bsta	Brast10G164100.1	98.659	2013	1	14	1	1987	241	2253	0	3544
Bsta_c16877_g1_i5_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G129300.1	99.398	830	2	3	1	827	345	1174	0	1502
Bsta_c16914_g1_i2_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G130300.1	99.776	893	0	1	1	891	721	1613	0	1637
Bsta_c17075_g2_i1_Chr07_Bsta	Brast07G181000.1	99.265	2585	2	9	1	2568	3	2587	0	4652
Bsta_c17107_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G066400.1	80	300	60	0	1	300	1007	1306	3.95E-57	222
	Brast04G133600.1	97.17	954	0	16	1	927	1023	1976	0	1587
Bsta_c17201_g1_i2_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G105700.1	100	835	0	0	28	862	1	835	0	1543
Bsta_c17204_g2_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G187300.1	99.553	1119	1	1	1	1115	273	1391	0	2036
	Brast07G094400.1	89.645	985	102	0	1	985	261	1245	0	1254
Bsta_c17226_g1_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G226300.1	99.259	3915	14	4	1	3900	617	4531	0	7055
Bsta_c17376_g2_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G305500.1	99.344	1676	0	9	1	1665	1515	3190	0	3024
Bsta_c17462_g1_i2_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G192600.1	97.222	612	3	6	1324	1921	2487	3098	0.00E+00	1024
	Brast01G192600.1	99.249	1332	2	3	1	1324	1123	2454	0	2398
Bsta_c17564_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G177000.1	99.082	1742	8	4	1	1734	293	2034	0	3121

Bsta_c17567_g1_i2_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G108600.1	98.645	1328	5	6	1	1315	386	1713	0.00E+00	2340
Bsta_c17653_g1_i3_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G222500.1	100	167	0	0	1	167	1269	1435	4.71E-84	309
Bsta_c17713_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G070400.1	99.83	1765	0	3	1	1762	442	2206	0.00E+00	3240
Bsta_c17837_g1_i2_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G220600.1	99.449	2539	1	7	1	2526	166	2704	0	4599
Bsta_c17861_g1_i1_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G034500.1	99.437	2665	15	0	1	2665	4217	6881	0	4839
Bsta_c17928_g2_i2_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G012400.1	99.381	1455	5	3	3	1453	21	1475	0	2634
	Brast07G089600.1	82.098	1201	190	20	28	1211	146	1338	0	1003
Bsta_c17958_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G271200.1	98.757	1529	2	4	1	1512	1246	2774	0	2702
Bsta_c17969_g2_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G012900.1	98.981	1865	8	6	1	1854	1313	3177	0	3328
Bsta_c18034_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G020300.1	99.595	247	1	0	4830	5076	1360	1114	2.59E-125	451
Bsta_c18034_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G020300.1	99.586	4834	17	3	1	4831	6303	1470	0	8813
Bsta_c18067_g1_i2_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G052700.1	99.677	1860	1	4	1	1855	55	1914	0	3397
Bsta_c18083_g1_i2_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G151100.1	98.043	1073	0	6	1	1052	2067	3139	0	1845
Bsta_c18108_g1_i2_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G179700.1	99.81	2627	1	4	1	2623	74	2700	0	4820
Bsta_c18133_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G248300.1	99.935	1529	1	0	1	1529	312	1840	0	2819
Bsta_c18185_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G036600.1	98.641	2428	6	10	1	2402	20	2446	0	4277
	Brast04G036800.1	99.16	1785	12	1	410	2194	1	1782	0	3210
Bsta_c18304_g1_i2_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G141800.1	99.856	4864	2	5	1	4859	643	5506	0.00E+00	8938
Bsta_c18324_g2_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G147200.1	98.399	1686	4	8	1	1663	37	1722	0	2942
	Brast09G147500.1	77.32	1455	269	45	83	1502	17	1445	0	802
Bsta_c18419_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G084800.1	98.432	1594	1	11	3	1572	154	1747	0	2784
	Brast08G094600.1	90.783	1584	85	34	5	1566	213	1757	0	2060
Bsta_c18440_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G058700.1	98.222	2531	2	22	1	2488	755	3285	0	4385
Bsta_c18447_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G218400.1	100	1044	0	0	46	1089	802	1845	0	1929
Bsta_c18483_g1_i4_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G042100.1	99.639	1937	5	1	1	1935	40	1976	0	3537
Bsta_c18527_g1_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G034800.1	98.719	1795	6	7	1	1778	94	1888	0	3171
Bsta_c18575_g1_i1_Chr07_Bsta	Brast07G211900.1	99.523	2304	9	1	1	2302	495	2798	0	4193
Bsta_c18648_g1_i5_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G375500.1	99.485	1748	2	3	1	1741	242	1989	0	3171
Bsta_c18750_g1_i2_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G340900.1	98.79	248	0	2	1	245	443	690	8.84E-123	438

Bsta_c18768_g1_i3_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G070800.1	99.535	215	1	0	1	215	877	1091	2.04E-108	392
	Brast02G070900.1	99.851	671	1	0	1	671	351	1021	0	1234
Bsta_c18784_g1_i3_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G031100.1	98.602	1431	5	15	1	1416	1505	2935	0.00E+00	2518
Bsta_c18841_g1_i5_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G040400.1	99.442	1254	1	3	1	1248	404	1657	0	2272
Bsta_c18893_g1_i2_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G294800.1	99.71	1033	2	1	1	1032	26	1058	0	1890
	Brast04G294800.1	99.908	3250	1	2	1032	4279	1019	4268	0	5984
Bsta_c18931_g1_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G108800.1	98.969	2521	1	8	1	2496	792	3312	0	4488
Bsta_c18953_g2_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G242400.1	98.478	1117	1	2	1	1101	134	1250	0	1954
Bsta_c19027_g1_i1_Chr07_Bsta	Brast07G016900.1	97.738	221	2	2	14	231	451	231	1.83E-104	377
Bsta_c19042_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G169800.1	99.291	3809	7	8	1	3789	223	4031	0	6866
Bsta_c19052_g1_i2_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G008200.1	99.48	2117	6	2	1	2112	483	2599	0.00E+00	3843
Bsta_c19074_g1_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G193200.1	98.792	1738	1	6	1	1718	43	1780	0	3075
Bsta_c19085_g1_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G173900.1	100	283	0	0	1	283	945	1227	2.78E-148	523
Bsta_c19089_g1_i3_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G266900.1	99.667	900	1	1	1	898	2070	2969	0	1644
	Brast02G346000.1	99.729	1108	1	2	1	1106	731	1838	0	2028
Bsta_c19117_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast06G184000.1	80.341	1114	202	10	7	1106	968	2078	0	828
Bsta_c19131_g1_i1_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G300300.1	99.86	3560	5	0	1	3560	287	3846	0.00E+00	6547
Bsta_c19159_g1_i4_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G013700.1	99.178	2312	4	8	1	2297	34	2345	0	4150
Bsta_c19175_g1_i3_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G092400.1	99.617	2611	1	4	1	2602	183	2793	0	4758
Bsta_c19221_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G118300.1	99.751	2813	2	1	1	2808	2827	15	0	5151
Bsta_c19240_g1_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G165900.1	99.213	381	0	2	1	378	269	649	0	684
Bsta_c19260_g1_i3_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G247000.1	98.987	1086	3	6	1	1078	1508	423	0	1938
Bsta_c19262_g2_i2_Chr08_Bsta	Brast06G153700.1	92.857	112	5	2	231	339	1255	1366	2.65E-38	159
	Brast08G036300.1	96.552	812	1	11	1	785	226	1037	0	1319
Bsta_c19309_g1_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G091700.1	98.693	765	0	7	1	755	1052	1816	0	1349
Bsta_c19348_g1_i2_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G200900.1	99.886	880	0	1	1	879	648	1527	0	1618
Bsta_c19351_g1_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G129600.1	97.984	2133	0	15	5	2094	1	2133	0	3661
Bsta_c19404_g1_i2_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G364300.1	99.884	1720	0	2	1	1718	1111	2830	0	3164
Bsta_c19466_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G321900.1	99.613	3621	3	7	1	3610	26	3646	0	6599

	Brast03G042200.1	85.891	2580	349	15	834	3405	651	3223	0	2734
Bsta_c19553_g1_i2_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G133900.1	98.312	237	0	2	3282	3514	641	405	8.43E-114	412
	Brast01G134000.1	99.49	3532	0	12	1	3514	233	3764	0	6407
Bsta_c19587_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G170000.1	99.616	3123	2	4	1	3113	94	3216	0	5692
Bsta_c19588_g1_i2_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G034600.1	99.561	1368	0	5	1	1362	1051	2418	0	2488
Bsta_c19589_g1_i2_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G038900.1	99.542	2183	4	4	1	2177	232	2414	0	3971
	Brast04G140500.1	97.56	1721	2	20	37	1717	1	1721	0	2909
Bsta_c19602_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast09G132900.1	78.853	1343	255	20	143	1467	322	1653	0	880
Bsta_c19653_g1_i2_Chr07_Bsta	Brast04G015200.1	75.582	2535	528	58	52	2530	729	3228	0	1168
	Brast07G084200.1	99.96	2530	1	0	1	2530	466	2995	0	4667
Bsta_c19686_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G240600.1	99.664	3866	4	4	8	3864	290	4155	0	7059
Bsta_c19725_g2_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast01G122700.1	75.374	1405	316	26	49	1435	1358	2750	0	651
	Brast08G070500.1	98.773	1712	2	8	1	1693	1180	2891	0	3027
Bsta_c19769_g1_i3_Chr07_Bsta	Brast04G086200.1	81.557	244	43	2	18	260	282	524	2.25E-50	200
	Brast07G171900.1	92.262	168	1	4	967	1122	1410	1577	1.03E-58	228
Bsta_c19769_g1_i3_Chr07_Bsta	Brast07G171900.1	99.486	972	0	4	1	967	408	1379	0	1762
Bsta_c19774_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G402600.1	91.873	1698	115	17	1	1694	147	1825	0	2350
	Brast01G402700.1	99.558	1810	2	2	1	1804	127	1936	0	3293
Bsta_c19792_g1_i3_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G134200.1	99.372	3027	4	3	1	3012	13	3039	0	5470
Bsta_c19823_g1_i5_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G281300.1	99.517	1035	0	3	1	1030	1196	2230	0	1879
Bsta_c19831_g1_i1_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G013700.1	93.056	1152	71	7	4	1148	396	1545	0	1676
	Brast05G013800.1	97.832	1153	20	4	1	1148	406	1558	0	1986
Bsta_c1984_g1_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G074200.1	99.392	1151	1	6	1	1145	390	1540	0	2082
Bsta_c19877_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G108400.1	96.825	63	2	0	2729	2791	2851	2913	1.27E-21	106
	Brast01G108400.1	99.429	2802	5	4	1	2791	52	2853	0	5075
Bsta_c19901_g1_i1_Chr10_Bsta	Brast10G080000.1	98.653	3489	3	12	1	3445	3527	39	0	6143
Bsta_c19929_g1_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G020300.1	98.479	1118	2	6	1	1103	637	1754	0	1956
Bsta_c19942_g1_i2_Chr07_Bsta	Brast07G096400.1	98.522	1218	0	11	1	1200	640	1857	0	2134
	Brast07G096600.1	98.837	430	0	4	776	1200	2627	2198	0	761

Bsta_c19970_g2_i3_Chr06_Bsta	Brast02G335300.1	79.386	1009	191	16	1538	2539	2112	3110	0	695
	Brast06G206800.1	99.616	2601	1	6	1	2592	594	3194	0	4739
Bsta_c20121_g1_i4_Chr10_Bsta	Brast10G003100.1	86.336	1471	181	16	45	1510	1487	32	0	1585
	Brast10G003400.1	99.615	1558	4	2	1	1556	1558	1	0	2843
Bsta_c20158_g1_i4_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G359700.1	97.619	504	2	7	7122	7615	2416	1913	0.00E+00	856
	Brast01G359700.1	99.566	7149	4	11	1	7125	9592	2447	0	13005
Bsta_c20169_g1_i3_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G135800.1	99.473	4932	0	10	1	4906	4966	35	0	8940
Bsta_c20220_g1_i4_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G111400.1	99.452	1826	4	4	1	1820	402	2227	0	3312
Bsta_c20275_g1_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G228000.1	99.394	3136	4	9	1	3121	2661	5796	0	5672
	Brast06G228100.1	97.119	486	0	8	2631	3102	1	486	0.00E+00	808
Bsta_c20337_g1_i2_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G139600.1	99.705	1355	1	1	1	1352	820	2174	0	2477
Bsta_c20381_g2_i8_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G298200.1	99.505	2625	1	7	18	2630	3106	482	0	4765
	Brast08G009400.1	93.103	174	10	2	693	866	959	788	4.04E-66	254
Bsta_c20382_g2_i2_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G139800.1	99.582	2874	4	3	1	2866	1907	4780	0	5234
Bsta_c20445_g2_i4_chr9_Bsta	Brast07G195600.1	85.959	641	54	18	1	616	979	1608	0	652
Bsta_c20520_g1_i2_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G291400.1	98.679	2650	33	2	8	2655	1	2650	0	4752
	Brast07G103400.1	97.779	2657	57	2	1	2655	87	2743	0	4632
Bsta_c20522_g2_i2_Chr08_Bsta	Brast01G408800.1	79.688	512	96	7	3497	4004	2020	1513	9.83E-99	363
	Brast01G408800.1	82.312	1306	203	20	1925	3227	3653	2373	0	1107
	Brast08G249700.1	99.181	4030	5	6	1	4002	4296	267	0.00E+00	7234
Bsta_c20555_g6_i6_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G332100.1	98.625	1091	0	6	1	1076	1223	133	0	1917
Bsta_c20594_g1_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G066800.1	99.084	982	0	8	1	973	214	1195	0	1755
Bsta_c20723_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G079800.1	100	826	0	0	1	826	251	1076	0	1526
Bsta_c20788_g1_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G182700.1	99.566	1842	2	4	55	1890	1	1842	0.00E+00	3352
Bsta_c20860_g1_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G232200.1	98.408	1382	1	14	1	1364	930	2308	0	2410
Bsta_c20988_g1_i1_Chr10_Bsta	Brast10G067900.1	99.069	859	1	6	1	852	813	1671	0	1535
Bsta_c21025_g1_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G166300.1	99.652	1435	2	3	1	1432	538	1972	0	2619
Bsta_c21244_g1_i1_Chr10_Bsta	Brast10G107400.1	99.881	838	1	0	1	838	388	1225	0	1543
Bsta_c21430_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G277100.1	93.103	551	1	5	1	514	1190	1740	0	773

Bsta_c21500_g1_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G084700.1	97.204	1073	5	18	11	1058	3028	4100	0	1792
Bsta_c21939_g1_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G132400.1	99.837	614	1	0	1	614	4039	4652	0	1129
Bsta_c21979_g1_i1_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G114900.1	99.202	2130	6	4	1	2119	1055	3184	0	3829
Bsta_c23074_g1_i1_Chr07_Bsta	Brast07G213600.1	100	471	0	0	1	471	327	797	0	870
Bsta_c26263_g1_i1_Chr10_Bsta	Brast10G018900.1	98.836	773	2	7	1	766	972	1744	0	1371
Bsta_c26272_g1_i1_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G228000.1	99.509	2241	0	4	1	2230	658	2898	0	4067
Bsta_c26279_g1_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G119000.1	100	301	0	0	1	301	771	1071	2.93E-158	556
Bsta_c26373_g1_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G122000.1	99.657	2043	0	6	22	2057	103	2145	0	3727
Bsta_c26436_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G142700.1	99.832	595	1	0	1	595	1579	2173	0	1094
Bsta_c2645_g1_i1_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G213600.1	99.74	1152	2	1	1	1151	368	1519	0	2109
Bsta_c2659_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G283100.1	100	1370	0	0	1	1370	332	1701	0	2531
Bsta_c26787_g1_i1_chr3_Bsta	Brast01G361100.1	99.675	2152	7	0	7	2158	617	2768	0	3936
	Brast08G183700.1	72.55	1745	437	38	130	1853	474	2197	1.37E-149	531
Bsta_c27116_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G089100.1	99.432	528	0	3	1	525	354	881	0	955
Bsta_c27154_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G044300.1	99.281	278	0	1	1	276	29	306	1.27E-141	501
Bsta_c2729_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G127800.1	99.87	769	1	0	1	769	1767	2535	0	1415
Bsta_c2774_g1_i2_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G037900.1	98.351	1334	10	8	1	1322	500	1833	0	2331
Bsta_c27845_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G024000.1	99.82	1664	0	3	1	1661	998	2661	0	3053
Bsta_c28069_g1_i1_Chr10_Bsta	Brast10G019800.1	95.755	424	1	7	1	407	707	1130	0	667
Bsta_c3142_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G262700.1	99.167	1201	0	7	1	1191	84	1284	0	2154
Bsta_c32007_g1_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G047400.1	99.567	1846	2	5	1	1840	534	2379	0	3360
Bsta_c32116_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G307600.1	99.698	1990	2	2	1	1986	2209	4198	0	3639
Bsta_c3215_g1_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G076500.1	99.957	2312	0	1	1	2311	2608	297	0	4263
Bsta_c32557_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G281800.1	100	478	0	0	1	478	190	667	0.00E+00	883
Bsta_c32724_g1_i1_Chr10_Bsta	Brast10G083200.1	98.169	710	13	0	1	710	63	772	0.00E+00	1240
Bsta_c32880_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G245400.1	99.501	1403	2	3	1	1398	144	1546	0	2547
Bsta_c32897_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G226100.1	98.052	308	0	3	1	302	679	986	1.78E-150	531
Bsta_c3388_g1_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast01G369900.1	92	100	7	1	866	965	2662	2760	8.35E-32	139
	Brast09G198900.1	99.839	1868	2	1	1	1867	331	2198	0	3432

Bsta_c34369_g1_i1_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G265400.1	99.623	265	0	1	1	264	1874	2138	4.37E-136	483
Bsta_c3471_g1_i1_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G216200.1	98.396	748	3	4	1	739	272	1019	0.00E+00	1306
Bsta_c34925_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G053800.1	100	176	0	0	1	176	2502	2677	1.53E-88	326
Bsta_c37406_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G201200.1	98.514	875	0	6	5	866	1	875	0	1531
	Brast02G201400.1	79.025	472	78	14	272	740	519	972	1.28E-81	303
Bsta_c38335_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G319800.1	99.744	390	0	1	1	389	896	507	0	713
Bsta_c38494_g1_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G148500.1	100	81	0	0	1	81	418	498	6.73E-36	150
	Brast09G148500.1	100	264	0	0	82	345	534	797	1.26E-137	488
Bsta_c39117_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G381600.1	100	313	0	0	1	313	449	761	6.53E-165	579
Bsta_c39131_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G287900.1	99.263	1899	2	7	1	1887	253	2151	0	3419
Bsta_c39343_g1_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G151900.1	99.033	517	1	3	1	513	225	741	0	924
Bsta_c40182_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G290000.1	99.034	1450	2	8	1	1438	413	1862	0	2590
Bsta_c416_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G262200.1	99.709	2403	2	4	3	2400	668	3070	0	4394
Bsta_c41803_g1_i1_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G278800.1	97.458	472	0	5	1	460	1260	789	0.00E+00	795
Bsta_c42763_g1_i1_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G230800.1	99.125	686	2	2	1	682	1890	1205	0.00E+00	1230
Bsta_c42766_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G058400.1	98.579	1337	2	10	1	1320	697	2033	0	2348
Bsta_c42819_g1_i1_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G040500.1	99.179	1218	2	4	1	1210	16	1233	0	2187
Bsta_c43006_g1_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G067600.1	99.095	1547	1	8	1	1534	199	1745	0	2767
Bsta_c4313_g1_i1_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G028200.1	99.52	1041	1	3	1	1037	918	1958	0	1892
Bsta_c43409_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G270900.1	98.135	858	0	9	1	842	1405	548	0	1482
Bsta_c44074_g1_i1_Chr07_Bsta	Brast07G011300.1	97.868	985	2	8	1	966	185	1169	0.00E+00	1685
Bsta_c44977_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G206600.1	99.771	875	0	2	1	873	432	1306	0	1604
Bsta_c4502_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G328600.1	99.025	513	2	3	1	510	1072	560	0	917
Bsta_c45496_g1_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G101500.1	96.112	643	0	10	1	618	1937	2579	0	1026
Bsta_c45603_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G029800.1	99.176	607	0	4	1	602	298	904	0	1088
Bsta_c46046_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G035700.1	98.99	594	3	2	1	591	419	1012	0	1061
Bsta_c46197_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G136400.1	99.569	928	2	1	1	926	2238	3165	0	1690
Bsta_c4749_g1_i1_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G185200.1	100	395	0	0	1	395	1213	1607	0	730
Bsta_c4820_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G023800.1	97.496	1837	6	14	1	1797	28	1864	0	3101

	Brast05G006900.1	72.784	970	227	33	177	1126	322	1274	1.69E-78	294
Bsta_c48255_g1_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G159100.1	100	397	0	0	1	397	2096	2492	0	734
Bsta_c4839_g1_i2_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G299100.1	99.185	1350	3	3	1	1342	339	1688	0	2425
Bsta_c4849_g2_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G155300.1	99.589	974	1	2	1	971	744	1717	0	1773
	Brast05G293100.1	78.501	707	128	17	50	744	313	1007	2.92E-123	442
Bsta_c48495_g1_i1_Chr05_Bsta	Brast05G152400.1	98.6	500	1	3	1	494	584	1083	0	880
Bsta_c4851_g1_i1_Chr09_Bsta	Brast09G256500.1	98.833	257	0	2	1	254	540	796	9.13E-128	455
Bsta_c48591_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G280800.1	99.138	1392	0	6	1	1380	1174	2565	0	2494
Bsta_c48669_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G130000.1	100	568	0	0	1	568	1262	1829	0	1050
Bsta_c49436_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G225400.1	99.578	948	0	3	1	944	157	1104	0	1725
Bsta_c49738_g1_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G087600.1	99.836	608	0	1	1	607	1300	1907	0	1116
Bsta_c49777_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G055200.1	99.469	1695	6	2	1	1692	59	1753	0	3077
Bsta_c50031_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G006800.1	99.495	2374	11	1	1	2373	385	2758	0	4316
Bsta_c50088_g1_i1_Chr07_Bsta	Brast07G014100.1	99.815	540	0	1	1	539	577	1116	0	990
Bsta_c5026_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G272100.1	99.192	866	0	3	1	859	1251	2116	0.00E+00	1554
Bsta_c50620_g1_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G204500.1	97.222	36	0	1	192	226	1867	1902	7.35E-09	60.2
	Brast08G204500.1	98.246	171	2	1	1	170	1652	1822	1.43E-80	298
Bsta_c51995_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G259600.1	98.734	632	4	2	1	628	551	1182	0	1120
Bsta_c52347_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G215700.1	100	471	0	0	1	471	529	999	0	870
Bsta_c5585_g1_i1_Chr04_Bsta	Brast04G185800.1	98.972	1264	0	6	1	1251	117	1380	0	2250
Bsta_c567_g1_i1_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G292800.1	99.086	2079	10	3	1	2070	333	2411	0	3725
Bsta_c5764_g1_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G146400.1	99.879	826	1	0	1	826	516	1341	0	1520
Bsta_c5791_g1_i1_Chr03_Bsta	Brast03G166800.1	98.142	1399	2	6	1	1384	1630	241	0.00E+00	2418
	Brast08G213800.1	72.871	634	135	28	735	1348	828	212	2.81E-45	183
Bsta_c582_g1_i1_Chr08_Bsta	Brast08G134300.1	98.246	1254	4	11	1	1236	710	1963	0	2178
Bsta_c6123_g1_i1_Chr06_Bsta	Brast06G112800.1	98.977	684	6	1	10	692	813	1496	0	1232
Bsta_c6161_g1_i1_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G224500.1	99.563	687	1	2	1	685	300	986	0.00E+00	1251
Bsta_c6255_g1_i2_Chr01_Bsta	Brast01G050500.1	97.803	1411	0	24	1	1380	114	1524	0	2405
Bsta_c6693_g1_i1_Chr02_Bsta	Brast02G042300.1	98.35	1636	0	14	1	1609	235	1870	0	2846

Bsta_c6890_g1_i1_Chrom6_Bsta	Brast06G085500.1	99.684	2845	6	3	1	2842	233	3077	0	5201
Bsta_c6968_g1_i2_Chrom2_Bsta	Brast02G131500.1	98.622	2249	3	7	14	2234	1	2249	0	3956
Bsta_c7338_g1_i1_Chrom9_Bsta	Brast09G166200.1	98.362	1038	0	13	1	1021	183	1220	0	1807
Bsta_c7431_g1_i1_Chrom1_Bsta	Brast01G312500.1	99.378	2089	1	11	1	2077	798	2886	0	3775
Bsta_c7557_g1_i1_Chrom2_Bsta	Brast02G299800.1	99.871	1554	2	0	30	1583	68	1621	0	2859
Bsta_c7737_g1_i1_Chrom2_Bsta	Brast02G155800.1	99.894	2828	3	0	7	2834	22	2849	0	5206
Bsta_c8359_g1_i1_Chrom2_Bsta	Brast02G129400.1	94.444	72	0	4	999	1066	1457	1528	1.33E-22	108
	Brast02G129400.1	89.713	1079	2	40	3	972	315	1393	0	1277
Bsta_c8643_g1_i1_Chrom1_Bsta	Brast01G082400.1	100	343	0	0	1	343	1141	1483	0	634
Bsta_c8814_g1_i1_Chrom4_Bsta	Brast04G052700.1	100	124	0	0	1	124	1119	1242	5.07E-59	230
	Brast04G052800.1	98.445	1994	0	7	1	1963	2026	33	0	3482
Bsta_c9090_g1_i1_Chrom5_Bsta	Brast05G023500.1	96.565	1077	29	5	1	1069	19	1095	0	1777
Bsta_c9219_g1_i1_Chrom7_Bsta	Brast07G037900.1	99.51	1430	4	3	1	1427	2233	804	0	2599
Bsta_c9231_g1_i1_Chrom1_Bsta	Brast01G098900.1	95.921	662	2	17	1	637	754	1415	0	1050
Bsta_c9252_g1_i1_Chrom8_Bsta	Brast08G119400.1	93.288	730	0	10	1	681	1055	1784	0	1031
Bsta_c9256_g1_i1_Chrom3_Bsta	Brast03G077600.1	98.717	1637	1	8	1	1617	1613	3249	0	2889
	Brast08G078200.1	83.395	1349	201	19	6	1339	889	2229	0	1229
Bsta_c9272_g1_i1_Chrom3_Bsta	Brast03G045500.1	97.441	2345	3	30	1	2288	206	2550	0	3945
Bsta_c9384_g1_i1_Chrom9_Bsta	Brast04G098600.1	86.824	296	33	3	187	476	412	707	1.47E-88	326
	Brast09G189000.1	98.119	319	6	0	156	474	1	319	4.78E-158	556
Bsta_c9552_g1_i1_Chrom8_Bsta	Brast08G137200.1	99.881	1681	2	0	1	1681	204	1884	0	3094
Bsta_c9732_g1_i1_Chrom9_Bsta	Brast09G156200.1	99.199	624	1	2	1	620	892	1515	0	1122
Bsta_c9737_g1_i2_Chrom2_Bsta	Brast02G299700.1	97.45	353	0	4	2187	2530	8964	9316	2.02E-168	593
	Brast02G299700.1	99.589	2192	3	4	1	2186	6657	8848	0	3993
Bsta_c9975_g1_i1_Chrom3_Bsta	Brast03G145700.1	99.159	832	0	5	1	825	1188	2019	0	1491
	Brast03G145800.1	91.286	700	58	2	2	701	1180	1876	0	952

(b) *B. hybridum*

Query (222 assembled transcripts of <i>B. hybridum</i> BdTR6g)	Database (all primary transcripts of <i>B. hybridum</i> ABR113)	percentage of identical matches	alignment length (sequence overlap)	number of mismatches	number of gap openings	start of alignment in query	end of alignment in query	start of alignment in subject	end of alignment in subject	expect value	bit score
Bhyb_B_c15520_g1_i1_Chr01_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0326700.1	98.947	2089	10	11	1	2077	641	2729	0	3725
	Brahy.D02G0126100.1	97.75	2089	35	11	1	2077	654	2742	0	3587
Bhyb_B_c18894_g1_i1_Chr06_Bhyb	Brahy.S06G0160900.1	99.748	397	1	0	1	397	2677	3073	0	728
	Brahy.D01G0714800.1	97.985	397	8	0	1	397	1952	2348	0	689
Bhyb_B_c24621_g1_i1_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.S08G0140800.1	99.722	360	1	0	1	360	3746	4105	0	660
	Brahy.D02G0372600.1	99.167	360	3	0	1	360	3937	4296	0	649
Bhyb_B_c25015_g1_i1_Chr03_Bhyb	Brahy.S03G0077300.1	94.091	440	4	16	1	418	1244	1683	0.00E+00	649
	Brahy.D03G0279400.1	91.449	421	33	3	1	418	1345	1765	2.39E-163	575
Bhyb_B_c26707_g1_i1_Chr06_Bhyb	Brahy.S06G0160600.1	99.796	489	1	0	1	489	860	1348	0	898
	Brahy.D01G0714500.1	95.277	487	23	0	1	487	706	1192	0	773
Bhyb_B_c27131_g1_i1_Chr04_Bhyb	Brahy.S04G0025400.1	99.56	910	4	0	1	910	1189	2098	0	1659
	Brahy.D03G0805400.1	96.813	910	29	0	1	910	1372	2281	0	1520
Bhyb_B_c27382_g1_i1_Chr10_Bhyb	Brahy.S10G0006200.1	97.489	876	3	9	1	857	1377	502	0	1478
	Brahy.D04G0007000.1	95.32	876	22	9	1	857	1361	486	0	1373
Bhyb_B_c28186_g1_i1_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.S04G0228000.1	98.336	1142	16	1	1	1139	923	2064	0	2001
	Brahy.D03G0157200.1	99.122	1139	10	0	1	1139	951	2089	0	2049
Bhyb_B_c28326_g1_i1_Chr01_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0164700.1	100	846	0	0	1	846	1	846	0.00E+00	1563
	Brahy.D02G0656500.1	97.281	846	23	0	1	846	763	1608	0	1435
Bhyb_B_c28409_g1_i2_Chr03_Bhyb	Brahy.S03G0163500.1	98.905	822	2	5	1	815	1198	2019	0.00E+00	1461
	Brahy.D03G0380900.1	91.961	821	60	2	1	815	1188	2008	0	1146
Bhyb_B_c29299_g2_i1_Chr07_Bhyb	Brahy.S07G0237600.1	99.575	471	2	0	1	471	332	802	0	859
	Brahy.D01G0427600.1	97.877	471	10	0	1	471	337	807	0	815
Bhyb_B_c29329_g1_i2_Chr06_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0342600.1	97.258	693	18	1	1	692	207	899	0	1173
Bhyb_B_c30147_g1_i1_Chr09_Bhyb	Brahy.S09G0219300.1	100	698	0	0	1	698	378	1075	0	1290

	Brahy.D05G0293700.1	96.991	698	21	0	1	698	343	1040	0	1173
Bhyb_B_c30192_g1_i1_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.S04G0336200.1	97.66	940	20	2	1	938	378	1317	0	1613
	Brahy.D03G0036300.1	93.87	1093	27	11	1	1053	443	1535	0	1611
Bhyb_B_c30238_g1_i3_Chr03_Bhyb	Brahy.S03G0067400.1	98.237	851	12	1	1	848	65	915	0	1485
	Brahy.D03G0266600.1	93.514	848	55	0	1	848	72	919	0	1262
Bhyb_B_c30327_g1_i2_Chr10_Bhyb	Brahy.S10G0090600.1	98.028	710	14	0	1	710	83	792	0	1234
	Brahy.D04G0101500.1	96.479	710	25	0	1	710	41	750	0	1173
Bhyb_B_c30628_g1_i3_Chr01_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0038900.1	98.653	594	5	2	1	591	424	1017	0	1050
	Brahy.D02G0795800.1	95.455	594	24	1	1	591	604	1197	0	944
Bhyb_B_c30796_g1_i2_Chr07_Bhyb	Brahy.S07G0012100.1	97.97	985	1	8	1	966	180	1164	0	1690
	Brahy.D01G0692200.1	93.712	986	41	11	1	966	199	1183	0	1458
Bhyb_B_c30837_g1_i1_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0141500.1	99.67	909	2	1	1	908	907	1815	0	1661
	Brahy.D01G0910600.1	97.14	909	25	1	1	909	910	1817	0	1533
Bhyb_B_c30952_g1_i1_Chr02_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0217300.1	99.231	1561	10	1	1	1559	4625	6185	0	2815
	Brahy.D01G0830100.1	98.206	1561	26	2	1	1559	4494	6054	0	2726
Bhyb_B_c31029_g1_i1_Chr03_Bhyb	Brahy.S03G0072900.1	100	451	0	0	1	451	1502	1952	0	833
	Brahy.D03G0274300.1	95.344	451	21	0	1	451	1499	1949	0	717
Bhyb_B_c31134_g1_i1_Chr09_Bhyb	Brahy.S09G0150900.1	99.73	1482	1	1	61	1539	1	1482	0.00E+00	2712
	Brahy.D05G0214300.1	95.161	1488	63	3	61	1539	1	1488	0	2340
Bhyb_B_c31186_g2_i2_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0111200.1	99.045	838	8	0	1	838	386	1223	0	1504
	Brahy.D01G0947800.1	98.926	838	9	0	1	838	310	1147	0	1498
Bhyb_B_c31234_g1_i1_Chr08_Bhyb	Brahy.S08G0179800.1	98.95	381	1	2	1	378	274	654	0.00E+00	678
	Brahy.D02G0415600.1	96.588	381	10	2	1	378	288	668	1.63E-179	628
Bhyb_B_c31264_g1_i1_Chr01_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0177800.1	98.485	1320	3	5	1	1303	56	1375	0	2311
	Brahy.D02G0643100.1	96.261	936	32	2	110	1042	1	936	0	1531
Bhyb_B_c31284_g1_i1_Chr01_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0219700.1	100	807	0	0	1	807	3416	4222	0	1491
	Brahy.D02G0595800.1	96.283	807	30	0	1	807	3419	4225	0	1325
Bhyb_B_c31446_g1_i2_Chr09_Bhyb	Brahy.S09G0219200.1	98.691	1833	5	6	1	1814	190	2022	0	3234
	Brahy.D05G0293600.1	97.854	1817	35	4	1	1814	57	1872	0	3136
Bhyb_B_c31503_g2_i1_Chr01_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0101700.1	99.825	1143	2	0	1	1143	447	1589	0	2100

	Brahy.D02G0726300.1	99.213	1143	9	0	1	1143	345	1487	0	2061
	Brahy.S09G0249300.1	99.244	529	2	1	1	527	60	588	0	953
Bhyb_B_c31915_g1_i2_Chr09_Bhyb	Brahy.D05G0325200.1	94.41	483	19	3	53	527	154	636	0	736
	Brahy.D05G0325200.1	95.161	62	3	0	1	62	81	142	8.06E-20	99
	Brahy.S01G0191200.1	97.531	810	6	3	1	796	572	1381	0	1373
Bhyb_B_c31996_g1_i3_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0629200.1	96.041	783	11	3	1	763	427	1209	0	1256
	Brahy.S05G0025700.1	98.514	1077	8	5	1	1069	3	1079	0	1893
Bhyb_B_c32000_g1_i2_Chr05_Bhyb	Brahy.D04G0356700.1	94.259	1080	51	3	1	1069	48	1127	0	1640
	Brahy.S04G0149600.1	97.76	1339	4	9	3	1315	1	1339	0	2283
Bhyb_B_c32420_g2_i5_Chr04_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0670100.1	96.212	1320	37	8	7	1315	1	1318	0	2148
	Brahy.S05G0235300.1	99.653	1152	3	1	1	1151	358	1509	0	2104
Bhyb_B_c32486_g1_i2_Chr05_Bhyb	Brahy.D04G0549700.1	97.569	1152	27	1	1	1151	354	1505	0	1971
	Brahy.S02G0033300.1	97.901	905	9	6	1	895	496	1400	0	1557
Bhyb_B_c32585_g1_i3_Chr02_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G1037300.1	98.996	896	8	1	1	895	520	1415	0.00E+00	1604
	Brahy.S03G0310200.1	96.575	1022	13	6	1	1001	429	1449	0	1674
Bhyb_B_c32612_g1_i1_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0559500.1	94.272	1030	30	5	1	1001	424	1453	0	1548
	Brahy.S09G0271600.1	99.663	891	1	2	1	889	1277	2167	0	1628
Bhyb_B_c32627_g1_i1_Chr09_Bhyb	Brahy.D05G0351400.1	97.868	891	17	2	1	889	1283	2173	0	1539
	Brahy.S04G0013900.1	99.175	1455	8	3	3	1453	21	1475	0	2617
Bhyb_B_c32809_g1_i1_Chr04_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0818400.1	97.129	1463	30	5	3	1453	31	1493	0	2459
	Brahy.S05G0119900.1	99.348	1074	0	2	1	1067	118	1191	0	1938
Bhyb_B_c32838_g1_i2_Chr05_Bhyb	Brahy.D04G0415900.1	94.315	1073	55	3	1	1067	99	1171	0	1639
	Brahy.S01G0266700.1	98.418	632	6	2	1	628	564	1195	0	1109
Bhyb_B_c33012_g1_i1_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0192800.1	98.576	632	5	2	1	628	696	1327	0.00E+00	1114
	Brahy.S07G0265000.1	98.723	940	2	2	32	961	305	1244	0	1661
Bhyb_B_c33014_g2_i1_Chr07_Bhyb	Brahy.S07G0265000.1	100	33	0	0	1	33	256	288	1.97E-08	62.1
	Brahy.D01G0391400.1	94.082	980	39	3	1	961	195	1174	0.00E+00	1471
	Brahy.S08G0020300.1	99.514	1234	1	1	1	1229	245	1478	0	2241
Bhyb_B_c33272_g1_i1_Chr08_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0223200.1	95.33	1242	44	2	2	1229	236	1477	0	1960
Bhyb_B_c33523_g1_i3_Chr02_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0232900.1	99.039	1249	0	7	1	1237	830	2078	0.00E+00	2230

	Brahy.D01G0207100.1	96.29	1240	33	7	1	1227	950	2189	0	2023
Bhyb_B_c33575_g2_i2_Chr03_Bhyb	Brahy.S03G0031000.1	99.424	1041	2	3	1	1037	1158	2198	0	1886
	Brahy.D03G0216100.1	98.367	1041	13	3	1	1037	702	1742	0	1825
Bhyb_B_c33662_g1_i2_Chr07_Bhyb	Brahy.S07G0080900.1	98.957	959	8	2	1	957	196	1154	0	1714
	Brahy.D01G0607200.1	95.53	962	32	7	1	951	234	1195	0	1528
Bhyb_B_c33986_g1_i1_Chr07_Bhyb	Brahy.S07G0113300.1	99.389	1309	7	1	1	1308	553	1861	0	2372
	Brahy.D01G0570000.1	98.778	1309	15	1	1	1308	559	1867	0	2327
Bhyb_B_c34101_g1_i1_Chr04_Bhyb	Brahy.S04G0135100.1	99.48	769	4	0	1	769	303	1071	0	1399
	Brahy.D03G0685500.1	97.919	769	16	0	1	769	308	1076	0	1332
Bhyb_B_c34119_g1_i2_Chr02_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0075400.1	99.702	671	2	0	1	671	352	1022	0	1229
	Brahy.D01G0989300.1	97.626	674	13	2	1	671	168	841	0	1153
Bhyb_B_c34244_g1_i1_Chr06_Bhyb	Brahy.S06G0032800.1	99.076	974	6	1	2	972	392	1365	0	1746
	Brahy.D01G0252200.1	95.16	971	47	0	2	972	404	1374	0	1533
Bhyb_B_c34385_g1_i5_Chr05_Bhyb	Brahy.S05G0285900.1	99.86	1432	2	0	1	1432	749	2180	0	2634
	Brahy.D04G0601700.1	97.906	1433	29	1	1	1432	627	2059	0	2479
Bhyb_B_c34498_g2_i1_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0075600.1	99.332	1497	10	0	1	1497	427	1923	0	2710
	Brahy.D02G0755000.1	97.061	1497	44	0	1	1497	421	1917	0	2521
Bhyb_B_c34572_g1_i1_Chr05_Bhyb	Brahy.S05G0162800.1	98.879	535	6	0	1	535	301	835	0	955
	Brahy.D04G0464300.1	98.505	535	8	0	1	535	317	851	0	944
Bhyb_B_c34647_g1_i1_Chr05_Bhyb	Brahy.S05G0044300.1	98.933	1218	5	4	1	1210	17	1234	0	2170
	Brahy.D04G0331300.1	95.098	1224	46	5	1	1210	15	1238	0	1916
Bhyb_B_c34745_g1_i3_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.S06G0068800.1	97.222	1512	24	7	1	1494	36	1547	0.00E+00	2543
	Brahy.D01G0292200.1	95.043	1513	38	11	1	1494	69	1563	0	2344
Bhyb_B_c35067_g3_i1_chr1_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0165500.1	98.973	974	7	2	1	971	762	1735	0	1740
	Brahy.D02G0655700.1	95.572	971	41	1	1	969	973	1943	0	1554
Bhyb_B_c35170_g1_i1_Chr05_Bhyb	Brahy.S05G0140400.1	98.901	1274	12	2	1	1272	54	1327	0	2274
	Brahy.D04G0439500.1	98.116	1274	22	2	1	1272	51	1324	0	2218
Bhyb_B_c35230_g1_i2_Chr07_Bhyb	Brahy.S07G0040500.1	99.441	1430	5	3	1	1427	2233	804	0	2593
	Brahy.D01G0657800.1	95.79	1449	39	5	1	1427	2232	784	0	2318
Bhyb_B_c35395_g1_i1_Chr02_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0138100.1	98.629	2261	3	7	2	2234	1	2261	0	3978

	Brahy.D01G0915600.1	96.508	2262	51	10	1	2234	2	2263	0	3714
Bhyb_B_c35406_g1_i1_Chr01_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0059600.1	98.61	1151	16	0	1	1151	632	1782	0	2037
	Brahy.D02G0772900.1	98.349	1151	19	0	1	1151	592	1742	0	2021
Bhyb_B_c35418_g1_i1_Chr10_Bhyb	Brahy.S10G0183100.1	97.914	2013	15	14	1	1986	293	2305	0	3459
	Brahy.D04G0184800.1	97.765	2013	17	17	1	1986	284	2295	0.00E+00	3443
Bhyb_B_c35666_g2_i11_Chr06_Bhyb	Brahy.S06G0218200.1	99.545	879	4	0	1	879	645	1523	0.00E+00	1602
	Brahy.D01G0758700.1	96.818	880	27	1	1	879	611	1490	0	1469
Bhyb_B_c35806_g1_i2_Chr01_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0056900.1	99.355	1860	4	5	1	1852	53	1912	0	3362
	Brahy.D02G0776300.1	96.683	1839	54	3	21	1852	1	1839	0	3051
Bhyb_B_c35892_g1_i1_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.S06G0203200.1	95.982	1767	48	8	1	1746	6	1770	0	2848
	Brahy.D01G0742300.1	97.39	1801	29	3	1	1783	32	1832	0	3049
Bhyb_B_c35980_g2_i2_Chr05_Bhyb	Brahy.S05G0250000.1	98.548	1515	8	7	51	1551	286	1800	0	2663
	Brahy.D04G0563900.1	98.275	1275	22	0	277	1551	625	1899	0	2233
	Brahy.D04G0563900.1	96.104	231	4	3	1	226	341	571	1.30E-101	372
Bhyb_B_c36229_g1_i1_Chr09_Bhyb	Brahy.S09G0076800.1	98.877	1247	13	1	1	1246	2633	1387	0	2224
	Brahy.D05G0122600.1	96.234	1248	45	2	1	1246	2636	1389	0	2043
Bhyb_B_c36425_g1_i5_Chr05_Bhyb	Brahy.S05G0245200.1	100	167	0	0	1	167	1270	1436	9.75E-84	309
	Brahy.D04G0559100.1	98.802	167	2	0	1	167	1347	1513	2.11E-80	298
Bhyb_B_c36638_g1_i1_Chr06_Bhyb	Brahy.S06G0049500.1	99.774	1328	3	0	1	1328	496	1823	0	2436
	Brahy.D01G0269700.1	96.536	1328	46	0	1	1328	508	1835	0	2198
Bhyb_B_c36752_g1_i6_Chr02_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0136400.1	99.648	568	2	0	1	568	1265	1832	0	1038
	Brahy.D01G0917200.1	95.775	568	24	0	1	568	1201	1768	0	917
Bhyb_B_c36782_g2_i10_Chr04_Bhyb	Brahy.S04G0356700.1	98.17	1038	9	4	49	1076	1171	134	0	1803
	Brahy.D03G0013900.1	96.313	1085	31	6	1	1076	1285	201	0	1773
Bhyb_B_c36830_g1_i2_Chr06_Bhyb	Brahy.S06G0010200.1	95.936	2682	6	40	1	2589	797	3468	0	4253
	Brahy.D01G0225000.1	91.461	2588	120	37	1	2505	798	3367	0	3461
Bhyb_B_c36894_g1_i1_Chr03_Bhyb	Brahy.S03G0085000.1	98.059	1649	10	9	1	1637	1719	3357	0	2848
	Brahy.D03G0289100.1	95.576	1650	60	6	1	1637	1976	3625	0	2630
Bhyb_B_c36955_g4_i3_Chr02_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0371600.1	99.278	1108	6	2	1	1106	722	1829	0	2001
	Brahy.D01G0058900.1	97.292	1108	28	2	1	1106	647	1754	0	1879

Bhyb_B_c37046_g1_i1_Chr09_Bhyb	Brahy.S09G0124700.1	99.462	2043	4	6	22	2057	103	2145	0	3705
	Brahy.D05G0178500.1	96.967	2044	54	7	22	2057	101	2144	0	3424
Bhyb_B_c37097_g1_i1_Chr03_Bhyb	Brahy.S03G0336300.1	99.77	1739	4	0	1	1739	2263	525	0	3190
	Brahy.D03G0170800.1	95.7	1744	68	4	1	1739	2277	536	0	2798
Bhyb_B_c37203_g1_i1_Chr03_Bhyb	Brahy.S03G0015000.1	98.617	2313	17	8	1	2299	27	2338	0	4080
	Brahy.D03G0236800.1	96.862	2326	46	6	1	2299	31	2356	0	3866
Bhyb_B_c37236_g1_i1_Chr07_Bhyb	Brahy.S07G0191900.1	99.177	972	3	4	1	967	406	1377	0	1746
	Brahy.S07G0191900.1	91.667	168	2	4	967	1122	1408	1575	1.00E-56	222
	Brahy.D01G0481900.1	96.811	972	23	5	1	967	375	1343	0.00E+00	1616
	Brahy.D01G0481900.1	90.476	168	4	5	967	1122	1374	1541	2.16E-53	211
Bhyb_B_c37259_g1_i12_Chr06_Bhyb	Brahy.S06G0268900.1	98.803	1086	5	6	1	1078	1509	424	0	1927
	Brahy.D01G0820400.1	94.751	1086	49	6	1	1078	1505	420	0	1683
Bhyb_B_c37344_g2_i1_Chr08_Bhyb	Brahy.S08G0074100.1	98.05	1487	24	2	1	1484	1091	2575	0	2580
	Brahy.D02G0286800.1	97.377	1487	36	1	1	1484	1301	2787	0	2527
Bhyb_B_c37440_g2_i1_Chr04_Bhyb	Brahy.S04G0368700.1	99.833	1794	3	0	253	2046	1	1794	0.00E+00	3297
	Brahy.D03G0790200.1	95.487	2393	86	10	7	2383	8	2394	0.00E+00	3801
Bhyb_B_c37479_g1_i3_Chr06_Bhyb	Brahy.S06G0136700.1	97.53	1660	15	5	1	1634	416	2075	0	2815
	Brahy.D01G0360100.1	95.811	1671	33	7	1	1634	427	2097	0	2663
Bhyb_B_c37540_g2_i1_Chr02_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0268300.1	98.788	825	4	3	1	819	1250	2074	0	1463
	Brahy.D01G0171800.1	96.727	825	21	2	1	819	1165	1989	0	1369
Bhyb_B_c37559_g1_i1_Chr06_Bhyb	Brahy.S06G0216900.1	98.09	2042	25	9	1	2028	657	2698	0	3542
	Brahy.D01G0756100.1	97.794	2040	33	7	1	2028	763	2802	0	3507
Bhyb_B_c37611_g1_i2_Chr01_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0098300.1	99.387	2610	4	4	5	2602	136	2745	0	4721
	Brahy.D02G0729900.1	95.367	2633	91	6	1	2602	128	2760	0	4157
Bhyb_B_c37615_g1_i1_Chr05_Bhyb	Brahy.S05G0037400.1	99.715	2453	7	0	1	2453	4406	6858	0.00E+00	4492
	Brahy.D04G0339400.1	97.883	2456	49	1	1	2453	4405	6860	0	4244
Bhyb_B_c37627_g2_i2_Chr03_Bhyb	Brahy.S03G0314600.1	99.904	1042	0	1	1	1041	1895	2936	0	1917
	Brahy.D03G0564300.1	96.746	1045	30	2	1	1041	1742	2786	0	1738
Bhyb_B_c37649_g1_i2_Chr01_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0377600.1	98.327	2152	36	0	7	2158	617	2768	0	3775
	Brahy.D02G0070200.1	98.426	2160	32	2	1	2158	612	2771	0	3799

Bhyb_B_c37673_g1_i1_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.S03G0306400.1	98.184	1872	18	11	1	1856	887	2758	0	3254
	Brahy.D03G0554700.1	96.858	1878	37	11	1	1856	905	2782	0	3121
Bhyb_B_c37690_g2_i1_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.S03G0049100.1	98.636	2200	9	9	1	2179	210	2409	0	3877
	Brahy.D03G0191600.1	95.727	2200	70	9	4	2179	240	2439	0	3520
Bhyb_B_c37718_g1_i1_chr1_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0241600.1	99.577	1420	6	0	1	1420	1119	2538	0	2590
	Brahy.D02G0571800.1	98.592	1420	20	0	1	1420	649	2068	0	2512
	Brahy.D02G0571800.1	100	30	0	0	364	393	982	1011	1.36E-06	56.5
Bhyb_B_c37839_g2_i1_Bd4_Bhyb	Brahy.S05G0255400.1	98.992	2282	23	0	1	2282	38	2319	0	4087
	Brahy.D04G0569300.1	98.116	2282	43	0	1	2282	15	2296	0	3976
Bhyb_B_c37927_g1_i1_Chr08_Bhyb	Brahy.S08G0145700.1	99.703	1681	5	0	1	1681	194	1874	0	3077
	Brahy.D03G0465700.1	96.882	1668	45	5	1	1662	215	1881	0	2785
Bhyb_B_c37969_g1_i2_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0114000.1	98.74	1826	17	4	1	1820	282	2107	0	3240
	Brahy.D01G0944600.1	97.922	1829	29	5	1	1820	298	2126	0	3158
Bhyb_B_c38028_g2_i1_Chr04_Bhyb	Brahy.S04G0125300.1	99.005	2813	23	1	1	2808	2897	85	0	5035
	Brahy.D03G0696900.1	97.159	2816	53	4	1	2808	2820	24	0	4732
Bhyb_B_c38060_g1_i3_Chr02_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0027600.1	98.383	2350	17	7	1	2335	414	2757	0	4109
	Brahy.D01G1042800.1	95.074	2355	73	23	1	2335	399	2730	0	3666
Bhyb_B_c38091_g2_i2_Chr02_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0040700.1	95.935	984	6	19	1	950	2062	3045	0	1565
	Brahy.D01G1029400.1	90.142	984	51	25	1	950	2040	3011	0	1238
Bhyb_B_c38252_g1_i1_Chr01_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0007700.1	99.373	1754	10	1	1	1753	1026	2779	0	3177
	Brahy.D01G0811700.1	97.32	1754	46	1	1	1753	952	2705	0	2977
Bhyb_B_c38277_g1_i4_Chr02_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0290100.1	97.406	1388	13	6	1	1365	1432	2819	0	2342
	Brahy.D01G0151500.1	97.926	1302	18	3	1	1296	1363	2661	0	2246
Bhyb_B_c38310_g1_i1_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.S03G0250600.1	97.992	2241	34	4	1	2230	628	2868	0	3879
	Brahy.D03G0487600.1	96.974	2247	51	6	1	2230	641	2887	0	3757
Bhyb_B_c38315_g1_i3_Chr05_Bhyb	Brahy.S05G0303500.1	99.67	3030	5	3	1	3025	518	3547	0	5535
	Brahy.D04G0623300.1	97.328	3031	75	2	1	3025	546	3576	0	5144
Bhyb_B_c38334_g1_i11_Chr08_Bhyb	Brahy.S08G0142800.1	99.374	3035	5	2	1	3021	29	3063	0	5487
	Brahy.D02G0375100.1	94.485	3046	138	9	7	3022	1	3046	0.00E+00	4667
Bhyb_B_c38367_g2_i2_Chr06_Bhyb	Brahy.S06G0044200.1	99.587	1937	6	1	1	1935	348	2284	0	3531

	Brahy.D01G0264000.1	95.199	1937	90	1	1	1934	24	1960	0	3059
Bhyb_B_c38377_g1_i2_Chr04_Bhyb	Brahy.S04G0330200.1	97.49	1673	31	9	1	1662	1023	2695	0	2846
	Brahy.D03G0044200.1	97.733	1676	27	9	1	1665	1508	3183	0	2874
Bhyb_B_c38414_g1_i1_Chr02_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0189100.1	99.541	2614	8	4	1	2610	98	2711	0	4758
	Brahy.D01G0861000.1	97.706	2615	55	5	1	2610	81	2695	0	4492
Bhyb_B_c38472_g1_i2_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0163600.1	99.894	2834	3	0	1	2834	22	2855	0	5217
	Brahy.D01G0886600.1	97.314	2829	74	2	7	2834	28	2855	0	4802
Bhyb_B_c38488_g1_i1_Chr08_Bhyb	Brahy.S08G0021000.1	97.764	1118	10	6	1	1103	632	1749	0	1912
	Brahy.D02G0223900.1	97.138	1118	17	5	1	1103	619	1736	0	1873
Bhyb_B_c38589_g1_i2_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0054800.1	97.236	1411	8	23	1	1380	140	1550	0	2361
	Brahy.D02G0779000.1	95.309	1407	39	20	1	1380	190	1596	0	2207
Bhyb_B_c38597_g2_i1_Chr08_Bhyb	Brahy.S08G0013700.1	98.91	1559	11	1	1	1553	1326	2884	0	2780
	Brahy.D02G0215000.1	98.461	1559	18	2	1	1553	1314	2872	0	2741
Bhyb_B_c38616_g3_i1_Chr09_Bhyb	Brahy.S09G0136600.1	97.186	1244	12	8	1	1221	483	1726	0	2082
	Brahy.D05G0193900.1	97.184	1243	11	8	1	1219	504	1746	0	2080
Bhyb_B_c38662_g3_i1_Chr08_Bhyb	Brahy.S08G0262200.1	98.236	907	4	5	36	930	2889	1983	0	1576
	Brahy.D02G0522100.1	93.763	946	40	11	1	930	2853	1911	0	1402
Bhyb_B_c38775_g3_i1_Chr02_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0047100.1	100	264	0	0	1	264	21	284	1.95E-137	488
	Brahy.D01G1021500.1	91.386	267	20	2	1	264	84	350	1.23E-99	363
Bhyb_B_c38808_g4_i1_Chr10_Bhyb	Brahy.S10G0016800.1	98.623	2034	15	8	1	2021	370	2403	0	3589
	Brahy.D04G0020500.1	97.356	2042	27	8	1	2021	409	2444	0	3446
Bhyb_B_c38816_g1_i1_Chr03_Bhyb	Brahy.S03G0182300.1	99.493	2369	9	1	1	2366	63	2431	0	4305
	Brahy.D03G0405100.1	96.084	2375	47	9	1	2366	338	2675	0	3831
Bhyb_B_c38844_g1_i1_Chr06_Bhyb	Brahy.S06G0247400.1	99.174	2180	17	1	1	2180	2523	4701	0	3925
	Brahy.D01G0796400.1	95.367	2180	101	0	1	2180	2479	4658	0	3467
Bhyb_B_c38845_g1_i2_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0062700.1	98.375	923	13	1	1	921	1249	2171	0	1620
	Brahy.D01G1003300.1	98.592	923	11	1	1	921	1217	2139	0	1631
Bhyb_B_c38847_g1_i1_Chr01_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0422300.1	97.897	1807	32	2	1	1801	125	1931	0	3121
	Brahy.D02G0017500.1	97.398	1806	44	2	1	1803	122	1927	0	3072
Bhyb_B_c38883_g1_i2_Chr04_Bhyb	Brahy.S04G0009700.1	99.386	2117	8	2	1	2112	483	2599	0	3832

	Brahy.D03G0823000.1	95.66	2120	84	4	1	2112	485	2604	0	3398
Bhyb_B_c38919_g1_i1_Ch05_Bhyb	Brahy.S05G0328700.1	99.25	2800	21	0	1	2800	1045	3844	0	5055
	Brahy.D04G0648300.1	96.536	2800	97	0	1	2800	1001	3800	0	4634
Bhyb_B_c38927_g1_i3_Ch04_Bhyb	Brahy.S04G0318200.1	99.368	3167	20	0	1032	4198	1017	4183	0	5738
	Brahy.S04G0318200.1	98.645	1033	13	1	1	1032	24	1056	0	1829
	Brahy.D03G0057700.1	98.863	3166	36	0	1033	4198	1164	4329	0	5648
	Brahy.D03G0057700.1	94.767	1032	53	1	1	1031	170	1201	0	1605
Bhyb_B_c38958_g1_i1_Ch01_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0142800.1	99.283	2231	5	6	1	2220	1545	3775	0	4021
	Brahy.D02G0681500.1	98.025	2228	36	4	1	2220	1586	3813	0	3864
Bhyb_B_c38990_g1_i2_Ch05_Bhyb	Brahy.D04G0448500.1	97.053	3156	81	7	1	3144	12	3167	0	5302
	Brahy.D04G0447600.1	96.825	3150	86	8	1	3144	42	3183	0	5251
Bhyb_B_c38998_g1_i2_Ch02_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0142500.1	98.884	4930	27	11	3	4906	4958	31	0.00E+00	8774
	Brahy.D01G0909500.1	97.152	4916	105	10	6	4906	4940	45	0	8270
Bhyb_B_c39032_g1_i1_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0968100.1	96.056	2409	83	3	1	2406	1917	4316	0	3912
	Brahy.D01G0968100.1	89.374	687	31	6	2405	3052	4359	5042	0	826
Bhyb_B_c39059_g1_i2_Ch01_Bhyb	Brahy.S01G0315700.1	99.295	567	2	1	1	565	381	947	0	1024
	Brahy.D02G0137800.1	94.32	581	14	9	1	565	492	1069	0	872
Bhyb_B_c39062_g1_i2_Ch03_Bhyb	Brahy.S03G0157500.1	98.938	1600	1	3	1	1584	2739	4338	0	2846
	Brahy.D03G0374100.1	96.619	1597	41	2	1	1584	2799	4395	0	2638
Bhyb_B_c39122_g2_i2_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.S08G0271400.1	92.523	2033	126	15	1	2008	3097	1066	0	2889
	Brahy.D02G0532900.1	91.88	2032	141	14	1	2008	3101	1070	0	2817
Bhyb_B_c39392_g1_i1_Ch07_Bhyb	Brahy.S07G0095500.1	98.49	1788	23	3	1	1784	2323	536	0	3149
	Brahy.D01G0590100.1	93.16	1769	106	12	22	1784	1818	59	0	2582
Bhyb_B_c39660_g1_i1_Ch04_Bhyb	Brahy.S04G0161500.1	92.871	505	3	13	1	472	718	1222	0	702
	Brahy.D03G0657500.1	87.692	520	16	21	1	472	686	1205	2.12E-159	562
Bhyb_D_c17170_g1_i1_Bd4_Bhyb	Brahy.D04G0567900.1	99.788	472	1	0	1	472	1684	1213	0.00E+00	867
	Brahy.S05G0253900.1	94.068	472	28	0	1	472	1670	1199	0.00E+00	717
Bhyb_D_c23560_g1_i1_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0900600.1	99.496	595	3	0	1	595	3296	3890	0	1083
	Brahy.S02G0149500.1	98.487	595	9	0	1	595	1603	2197	0	1050
Bhyb_D_c25015_g2_i1_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0279400.1	98.378	370	3	3	1	367	1396	1765	0.00E+00	647

	Brahy.S03G0077300.1	88.021	384	27	15	3	367	1300	1683	1.02E-121	436
Bhyb_D_c25832_g1_i1_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0802300.1	98.539	616	1	5	1	608	290	905	0	1081
	Brahy.S01G0032700.1	89.379	612	56	8	1	608	287	893	0	761
Bhyb_D_c26076_g1_i2_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0836000.1	96.38	1326	6	11	3	1297	108	1422	0	2145
	Brahy.S02G0211900.1	93.682	1203	48	10	119	1293	202	1404	0	1775
	Brahy.S02G0211900.1	93.333	120	7	1	1	119	50	169	9.14E-43	176
Bhyb_D_c26509_g1_i2_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0423800.1	98.347	363	5	1	1	362	173	535	0	636
	Brahy.S03G0197200.1	96.143	363	13	1	1	362	220	582	2.04E-168	592
Bhyb_D_c26716_g1_i1_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0684700.1	98.643	221	0	3	14	231	386	166	1.76E-107	388
	Brahy.S07G0017900.1	94.57	221	9	3	14	231	439	219	1.80E-92	339
Bhyb_D_c28645_g1_i1_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0667700.1	98.207	781	0	10	1	767	767	1547	0	1352
	Brahy.S07G0032400.1	93.086	781	40	10	1	767	817	1597	0	1131
Bhyb_D_c29171_g1_i1_Bd5_Bhyb	Brahy.D05G0219600.1	99.033	517	1	3	1	513	192	708	0	924
	Brahy.S09G0156000.1	96.304	514	15	3	1	510	223	736	0	841
Bhyb_D_c29292_g1_i1_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0573700.1	99.272	687	3	2	1	685	406	1092	0	1240
	Brahy.S01G0240300.1	97.962	687	12	2	1	685	418	1104	0	1190
Bhyb_D_c29519_g1_i1_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0178700.1	99.316	877	3	1	1	874	639	1515	0	1583
	Brahy.S02G0261500.1	95.955	717	26	1	1	717	589	1302	0	1160
Bhyb_D_c29541_g1_i4_Bd4_Bhyb	Brahy.D04G0003700.1	99.577	946	3	1	1	945	765	1710	0	1724
	Brahy.S10G0003900.1	93.122	916	60	3	1	914	915	1	0	1339
Bhyb_D_c30103_g2_i2_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0678900.1	99.63	540	1	1	1	539	518	1057	0	985
	Brahy.S07G0014900.1	94.259	540	30	1	1	539	574	1113	0	824
Bhyb_D_c30253_g1_i2_Ch02_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0093600.1	99.744	390	0	1	1	389	881	492	0.00E+00	713
	Brahy.S02G0343400.1	97.179	390	10	1	1	389	1229	840	0	658
Bhyb_D_c30456_g1_i1_Bd4_Bhyb	Brahy.D04G0024900.1	93.868	424	9	6	1	407	698	1121	8.18E-178	623
	Brahy.S10G0020700.1	93.632	424	10	7	1	407	700	1123	3.81E-176	617
Bhyb_D_c31312_g1_i2_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0185600.1	99.574	1175	2	1	1	1172	93	1267	0	2139
	Brahy.S02G0254000.1	95.041	1210	60	0	1	1210	93	1302	0	1903
Bhyb_D_c31475_g1_i2_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0675700.1	99.246	928	5	1	1	926	2106	3033	0	1674
	Brahy.S04G0144200.1	97.845	928	18	1	1	926	2083	3010	0	1602

Bhyb_D_c31603_g1_i1_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0552100.1	97.619	294	1	6	1	288	1020	727	9.91E-141	499
	Brahy.S03G0304000.1	95.139	288	14	0	1	288	965	678	2.17E-127	455
Bhyb_D_c31769_g1_i1_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0740300.1	99.496	992	2	2	1	989	309	1300	0	1801
	Brahy.S04G0085200.1	98.488	992	12	2	1	989	465	1456	0	1746
Bhyb_D_c31892_g1_i2_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0210800.1	99.664	1191	4	0	58	1248	1	1191	0	2178
	Brahy.S02G0229400.1	94.514	1440	60	7	1	1424	55	1491	0	2204
Bhyb_D_c32171_g1_i1_Bd4_Bhyb	Brahy.D04G0123200.1	98.7	846	3	1	1	838	417	1262	0	1495
	Brahy.S10G0110200.1	95.585	838	37	0	1	838	392	1229	0	1343
Bhyb_D_c32352_g1_i1_Chr01_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0622400.1	97.933	774	10	1	1	768	785	12	0	1336
	Brahy.S01G0197400.1	97.005	768	20	1	1	768	773	9	0	1288
Bhyb_D_c32660_g1_i3_Bd5_Bhyb	Brahy.D05G0061600.1	98.374	1107	6	6	1	1095	735	1841	0	1934
	Brahy.S09G0041100.1	96.025	1107	32	6	1	1095	822	1928	0	1790
Bhyb_D_c32707_g3_i4_Chr08_Bhyb	Brahy.D04G0083100.1	85.13	269	34	3	1	266	2832	2567	4.34E-71	270
	Brahy.S10G0074500.1	81.818	253	41	5	1	251	772	1021	3.45E-52	207
Bhyb_D_c32774_g1_i2_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0315700.1	98.684	608	7	1	1	607	1259	1866	0	1077
	Brahy.S06G0091800.1	96.865	606	18	1	3	607	1267	1872	0	1013
Bhyb_D_c32841_g1_i1_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0916900.1	99.549	887	3	1	1	886	622	1508	0	1615
	Brahy.S02G0136700.1	96.622	888	28	1	1	886	709	1596	0	1472
Bhyb_D_c32905_g1_i1_Chr01_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0543900.1	97.849	1116	9	2	1	1101	420	1535	0	1914
	Brahy.S01G0435200.1	96.15	1117	27	3	1	1101	90	1206	0	1810
Bhyb_D_c32917_g2_i1_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0765500.1	97.756	1337	13	10	1	1320	1103	2439	0	2287
	Brahy.S04G0061800.1	97.307	1337	19	10	1	1320	984	2320	0	2254
Bhyb_D_c33039_g1_i1_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0554800.1	99.111	450	1	2	1	447	424	873	0	806
	Brahy.S01G0446600.1	94.107	543	14	7	1	525	514	1056	0	809
Bhyb_D_c33278_g1_i1_Bd5_Bhyb	Brahy.D05G0200800.1	98.099	789	0	11	1	774	933	1721	0	1360
	Brahy.S09G0141800.1	94.636	783	23	13	1	765	996	1777	0	1195
Bhyb_D_c33292_g1_i1_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0582800.1	99.326	1631	11	0	1	1631	1820	190	0	2952
	Brahy.S07G0101400.1	96.252	1654	43	10	1	1639	1669	20	0	2693
Bhyb_D_c3335_g1_i1_Bd4_Bhyb	Brahy.D04G0607100.1	99.245	265	1	1	1	264	1775	2039	4.22E-134	477
	Brahy.S05G0291000.1	98.113	265	4	1	1	264	1817	2081	4.25E-129	460

Bhyb_D_c33483_g1_i1_Bd4_Bhyb	Brahy.D04G0445700.1	98.905	1279	14	0	1	1279	468	1746	0	2285
	Brahy.S05G0146300.1	98.749	1279	16	0	1	1279	503	1781	0	2274
Bhyb_D_c33531_g1_i2_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0119000.1	99.799	993	2	0	1	993	201	1193	0	1823
	Brahy.S02G0320900.1	97.704	1350	23	3	1	1342	211	1560	0	2314
Bhyb_D_c33551_g1_i1_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0521500.1	98.175	1096	10	4	1	1086	1220	2315	0	1905
	Brahy.S08G0261500.1	95.978	1094	33	6	1	1086	978	2068	0	1766
Bhyb_D_c33573_g1_i1_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0590300.1	99.771	875	0	2	1	873	375	1249	0	1604
	Brahy.S04G0219600.1	98.057	875	15	2	1	873	432	1306	0	1520
Bhyb_D_c33683_g1_i2_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0046100.1	99.042	313	3	0	1	313	428	740	1.36E-159	562
	Brahy.S01G0399900.1	96.486	313	11	0	1	313	545	857	2.99E-146	518
Bhyb_D_c33783_g1_i1_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0085600.1	97.905	859	5	7	1	848	1386	530	0	1474
	Brahy.S04G0293400.1	92.925	848	42	11	15	848	1452	609	0	1218
Bhyb_D_c33797_g1_i1_Bd4_Bhyb	Brahy.D04G0425900.1	99.083	1309	7	3	1	1304	370	1678	0	2346
	Brahy.S05G0127900.1	95.406	1306	39	6	1	1304	354	1640	0	2060
Bhyb_D_c33829_g1_i1_Chr03_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0196400.1	99.085	984	4	2	1	979	294	1277	0.00E+00	1762
	Brahy.S03G0044900.1	98.059	979	19	0	1	979	319	1297	0	1703
Bhyb_D_c33856_g2_i1_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G1024400.1	98.168	1638	8	13	1	1616	153	1790	0	2839
	Brahy.S02G0045100.1	95.602	1637	48	12	2	1616	143	1777	0	2603
Bhyb_D_c33876_g1_i2_Chr04_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0016400.1	95.812	788	18	8	1	775	1443	658	0	1258
	Brahy.S04G0354200.1	96.518	718	13	7	70	775	1363	646	0	1177
Bhyb_D_c33966_g2_i1_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0767300.1	98.391	808	2	7	1	798	1246	2052	0	1410
	Brahy.S04G0060600.1	90.024	822	52	16	1	800	1630	2443	0	1037
Bhyb_D_c34204_g1_i1_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0086500.1	99.61	1795	4	2	1	1792	127	1921	0	3273
	Brahy.S01G0362900.1	95.962	1808	52	11	1	1791	155	1958	0	2915
Bhyb_D_c34487_g1_i3_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G1044900.1	98.416	1894	14	8	1	1878	64	1957	0	3317
	Brahy.S02G0025500.1	94.093	1913	74	16	1	1878	39	1947	0	2870
Bhyb_D_c34622_g1_i2_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0301000.1	98.523	1151	9	6	1	1143	383	1533	0	2025
	Brahy.S06G0077500.1	98.175	1151	13	7	1	1143	377	1527	0	2002
Bhyb_D_c34646_g1_i1_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0736600.1	99.471	1701	8	1	1	1700	125	1825	0	3090
	Brahy.S01G0092300.1	94.65	1701	83	4	7	1700	169	1868	0	2630

Bhyb_D_c34665_g1_i1_Bd5_Bhyb	Brahy.D05G0110200.1	98.274	1159	14	2	1	1153	222	1380	0	2025
	Brahy.S09G0067200.1	97.668	1158	21	4	1	1152	231	1388	0	1984
Bhyb_D_c34888_g2_i2_Chr02_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0118400.1	99.356	1554	10	0	30	1583	74	1627	0	2815
	Brahy.S02G0321700.1	98.407	1569	22	3	18	1583	55	1623	0	2756
Bhyb_D_c35067_g4_i1_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0655700.1	100	560	0	0	1	560	1166	1725	0	1035
	Brahy.S01G0165500.1	96.429	560	20	0	1	560	955	1514	0	924
Bhyb_D_c35202_g1_i1_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0408900.1	98.921	1390	2	3	1	1386	1548	168	0.00E+00	2471
	Brahy.S03G0185400.1	93.414	1397	70	6	3	1386	1585	198	0	2050
Bhyb_D_c35309_g1_i1_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0366500.1	98.737	2138	3	9	1	2114	5	2142	0	3777
	Brahy.S08G0137700.1	94.056	2002	100	9	1	1987	9	2006	0	3020
	Brahy.S08G0137700.1	95.699	93	4	0	1997	2089	2044	2136	9.11E-35	150
Bhyb_D_c35587_g1_i1_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0631400.1	98.632	1754	6	9	1	1736	588	2341	0	3090
	Brahy.S01G0188300.1	94.266	1744	90	7	1	1736	577	2318	0	2658
Bhyb_D_c35857_g1_i1_Bd4_Bhyb	Brahy.D04G0274300.1	99.247	1726	9	3	1	1722	60	1785	0	3112
	Brahy.S05G0075500.1	96.998	1699	48	2	27	1722	68	1766	0	2852
Bhyb_D_c35880_g1_i2_Chr05_Bhyb	Brahy.D04G0428900.1	98.825	2128	14	4	1	2117	561	2688	0	3781
	Brahy.S05G0130500.1	96.62	2130	61	4	1	2119	778	2907	0	3524
Bhyb_D_c35928_g1_i4_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0054700.1	99.794	970	2	0	1	970	1107	138	0	1781
	Brahy.S01G0392000.1	97.11	969	28	0	1	969	1122	154	0	1635
Bhyb_D_c36040_g1_i3_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0771700.1	98.246	1995	4	7	1	1964	2006	12	0	3461
	Brahy.S04G0056300.1	95.338	1995	61	6	1	1964	2015	22	0	3140
Bhyb_D_c36166_g1_i1_Chr10_Bhyb	Brahy.D04G0029300.1	99.051	1581	14	1	1	1580	2604	4184	0	2835
	Brahy.S10G0023800.1	98.355	1581	25	1	1	1580	3103	4683	0	2774
Bhyb_D_c36183_g1_i1_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0769400.1	99.252	1203	6	3	1	1200	966	2168	0	2169
	Brahy.S01G0063200.1	95.677	1203	45	5	1	1200	1293	2491	0	1927
Bhyb_D_c36212_g2_i1_chr9_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0454600.1	99.301	1717	5	4	1	1710	114	1830	0	3097
	Brahy.S07G0216000.1	96.115	1673	61	3	1	1669	347	2019	0	2726
Bhyb_D_c36376_g1_i1_Bd5_Bhyb	Brahy.D05G0280000.1	99.091	1870	14	2	1	1867	304	2173	0	3356
	Brahy.S09G0205800.1	97.109	1868	53	1	1	1867	313	2180	0	3149
Bhyb_D_c36378_g1_i1_Bd5_Bhyb	Brahy.D05G0166000.1	99.838	1235	0	1	1	1233	319	1553	0	2268

	Brahy.S09G0113600.1	95.867	1234	49	1	2	1233	380	1613	0	1995
Bhyb_D_c36383_g2_i1_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0071600.1	99.197	1370	11	0	1	1370	217	1586	0	2470
	Brahy.S04G0305800.1	98.759	1370	17	0	1	1370	166	1535	0	2436
Bhyb_D_c36483_g1_i2_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0508600.1	98.84	1466	9	4	1	1458	425	1890	0	2606
	Brahy.S07G0167800.1	95.848	1469	50	3	1	1458	254	1722	0	2364
Bhyb_D_c36562_g1_i1_Ch02_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0206900.1	99.247	1594	1	8	27	1609	1	1594	0	2867
	Brahy.S02G0233200.1	95.314	1622	60	7	1	1609	17	1635	0	2560
Bhyb_D_c36599_g3_i1_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0588300.1	98.528	951	11	1	1	948	1616	666	0	1676
	Brahy.S01G0226800.1	97.574	948	23	0	1	948	1604	657	0	1624
Bhyb_D_c36607_g1_i2_Bd5_Bhyb	Brahy.D05G0346000.1	95.301	915	3	15	1	875	935	1849	0	1415
	Brahy.S09G0266900.1	86.484	910	84	22	1	875	923	1828	0	963
Bhyb_D_c36956_g1_i2_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0800900.1	98.601	1430	5	14	2	1416	1492	2921	0	2516
	Brahy.S01G0034000.1	94.13	1431	69	15	1	1416	1483	2913	0	2163
Bhyb_D_c37000_g1_i2_Ch04_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0616000.1	98.339	1264	8	6	1	1251	87	1350	0	2206
	Brahy.S04G0199400.1	96.216	1242	34	6	12	1240	1	1242	0	2021
Bhyb_D_c37100_g1_i1_Ch02_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0027400.1	99.32	1471	6	3	1	1467	514	1984	0	2658
	Brahy.S02G0402600.1	96.682	1477	39	5	1	1467	490	1966	0	2447
Bhyb_D_c37194_g1_i3_Ch03_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0378300.1	99.218	2046	10	4	1	2042	14	2057	0	3685
	Brahy.S03G0161800.1	96.691	2055	53	7	1	2042	7	2059	0	3404
Bhyb_D_c37525_g3_i1_Ch09_Bhyb	Brahy.D05G0225700.1	98.095	630	2	7	1	620	895	1524	0	1088
	Brahy.S09G0160300.1	95.192	624	26	3	1	620	885	1508	0	983
Bhyb_D_c37605_g2_i1_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0718400.1	98.671	1129	14	1	1	1128	858	1986	0	2001
	Brahy.S06G0164400.1	97.52	1129	27	1	1	1128	863	1991	0	1929
Bhyb_D_c37659_g1_i1_Bd4_Bhyb	Brahy.D04G0080500.1	96.818	1477	47	0	1	1477	849	2325	0	2468
	Brahy.S10G0069600.1	97.164	1481	38	2	1	1477	851	2331	0	2499
Bhyb_D_c37754_g1_i8_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0425500.1	98.94	283	3	0	1	283	760	1042	5.81E-143	507
	Brahy.S08G0187200.1	97.436	273	7	0	2	274	894	1166	9.86E-131	466
Bhyb_D_c37784_g2_i2_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0255800.1	98.57	1399	3	7	1	1382	84	1482	0.00E+00	2457
	Brahy.S06G0036300.1	95.926	1399	40	7	1	1382	95	1493	0	2252
Bhyb_D_c38004_g1_i1_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0143400.1	99.39	2624	7	3	18	2632	3096	473	0	4748

	Brahy.S01G0310200.1	96.19	2625	90	5	18	2632	3106	482	0	4285
Bhyb_D_c38036_g1_i1_Chr06_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0313300.1	99.613	2845	8	3	1	2842	209	3053	0	5190
	Brahy.S06G0089300.1	98.067	2845	52	3	1	2842	229	3073	0	4946
Bhyb_D_c38093_g1_i3_Chr04_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0787300.1	99.525	2107	7	3	1	2104	221	2327	0.00E+00	3832
	Brahy.S04G0041700.1	95.297	2190	82	9	1	2176	359	2541	0.00E+00	3454
Bhyb_D_c38106_g1_i2_Bd3_Bhyb	Brahy.D03G0793100.1	99.048	1365	8	4	1	1360	1026	2390	0	2444
	Brahy.S04G0036700.1	95.029	1368	63	4	1	1363	1051	2418	0	2145
Bhyb_D_c38112_g1_i6_Bd5_Bhyb	Brahy.D05G0219100.1	98.5	1067	1	5	1	1052	2021	3087	0	1868
	Brahy.S09G0155100.1	95.154	1073	31	11	1	1052	2036	3108	0	1674
Bhyb_D_c38117_g2_i1_Bd5_Bhyb	Brahy.D05G0131500.1	97.85	1070	1	16	11	1058	2982	4051	0	1829
	Brahy.S09G0085500.1	93.197	1073	48	17	11	1058	3133	4205	0	1554
Bhyb_D_c38120_g1_i3_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0369200.1	99.08	2717	12	7	1	2704	208	2924	0	4867
	Brahy.S06G0145000.1	95.694	2717	101	7	1	2704	188	2901	0	4355
Bhyb_D_c38142_g1_i1_Chr01_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0710800.1	99.113	2481	22	0	1	2481	365	2845	0	4460
	Brahy.S01G0115100.1	95.628	2493	76	11	1	2481	381	2852	0	3969
	Brahy.S01G0115100.1	98.413	63	1	0	2419	2481	2850	2912	5.05E-23	111
	Brahy.S01G0115100.1	98.413	63	1	0	2419	2481	2910	2972	5.05E-23	111
Bhyb_D_c38174_g1_i1_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0613200.1	99.774	1326	0	1	1	1323	1100	2425	0	2429
	Brahy.D02G0613200.1	98.841	604	2	2	1323	1921	2458	3061	0	1072
	Brahy.S01G0205100.1	95.27	1332	54	4	1	1323	1056	2387	0	2102
	Brahy.S01G0205100.1	93.475	613	25	7	1323	1921	2420	3031	0	896
Bhyb_D_c38380_g1_i1_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0870400.1	99.456	1839	4	2	1	1833	1327	3165	0	3336
	Brahy.S02G0178600.1	97.882	1558	33	0	1	1558	1322	2879	0	2695
	Brahy.S02G0178600.1	93.64	283	11	3	1557	1833	3002	3283	7.04E-115	416
Bhyb_D_c38491_g1_i5_Bd5_Bhyb	Brahy.D05G0202000.1	98.613	1298	3	3	1	1283	932	2229	0	2283
	Brahy.S09G0142600.1	97.589	1286	28	1	1	1283	870	2155	0	2200
Bhyb_D_c38545_g1_i1_Bd4_Bhyb	Brahy.D04G0098100.1	98.195	3103	47	4	1	3097	3100	1	0	5411
	Brahy.S10G0086400.1	97.393	3491	72	11	1	3474	3525	37	0	5925
Bhyb_D_c38839_g1_i3_chr7_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0595900.1	98.596	1425	17	1	1	1422	1240	2664	0	2518
	Brahy.S07G0091300.1	98.101	1422	27	0	1	1422	1394	2815	0	2477

Bhyb_D_c38887_g2_i1_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0118500.1	99.621	1321	4	1	1	1320	7472	8792	0.00E+00	2410
	Brahy.D01G0118500.1	97.167	353	1	4	1321	1664	8908	9260	1.28E-166	588
	Brahy.S02G0321500.1	96.593	1321	44	1	1	1320	7502	8822	0.00E+00	2189
	Brahy.S02G0321500.1	96.034	353	5	4	1321	1664	8938	9290	5.99E-160	566
Bhyb_D_c38922_g1_i2_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0639700.1	99.531	2556	12	0	1	2556	703	3258	0	4654
	Brahy.S01G0180900.1	96.014	2559	99	1	1	2556	465	3023	0	4157
Bhyb_D_c38969_g1_i3_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.D01G0546700.1	99.294	4535	28	4	1	4531	339	4873	0	8194
	Brahy.D01G0546700.1	98.305	59	1	0	4512	4570	4873	4931	1.57E-20	104
	Brahy.S07G0131000.1	96.017	4595	145	16	1	4570	293	4874	0	7437
Bhyb_D_c38989_g1_i1_Chr01_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0552200.1	98.987	2567	24	1	1	2565	984	3550	0	4595
	Brahy.S01G0443600.1	98.714	2567	31	1	1	2565	1056	3622	0	4556
Bhyb_D_c39037_g3_i1_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0284700.1	95.671	2356	8	50	1	2262	277	2632	0	3699
	Brahy.S08G0071600.1	92.954	2356	63	51	1	2262	300	2646	0	3336
Bhyb_D_c39048_g1_i1_Bd1_Bhyb	Brahy.S02G0300700.1	97.773	1392	19	6	1	1380	1162	2553	0	2388
Bhyb_D_c39108_g4_i2_Bd2_Bhyb	Brahy.D02G0383700.1	99.327	2824	13	4	1	2818	762	3585	0	5105
	Brahy.S08G0150400.1	97.66	2821	63	3	1	2818	636	3456	0	4841

Data S3. Blastn between the *B. stacei* TE4.3 and *B. hybridum* BdTR6g assembled genes that encode the nuclear validated core transcript used in this study and the annotated genes of their respective reference genomes. **(a)** 322 *B. stacei* TE4.3 genes were used as query to match the corresponding annotated genes of the *B. stacei* ABR114 reference genome (only 321 genes could be searched as one gene was not annotated in the *B. stacei* ABR114 genome). **(b)** 222 *B. hybridum* BdTR6g genes were used as query to match the corresponding annotated genes of the *B. hybridum* ABR113 reference genome. Values highlighted in bold indicate the best match for each query. In *B. hybridum*, values with red and blue background colors correspond to *B. stacei* and *B. distachyon* subgenomic matches respectively.

(a) *B. stacei*

Query (321 assembled genes of <i>B. stacei</i> TE4.3)	Database (<i>B. stacei</i> ABR114 genes)	percentage of identical matches	alignment length (sequence overlap)	number of mismatches	number of gap openings	start of alignment in query	end of alignment in query	start of alignment in subject	end of alignment in subject	expect value	bit score
TE4.3_Brast01G006800	Brast01G006800	99.575	3531	15	0	1	3531	1	3531	0	6438
	Brast04G188200	83.036	112	12	6	358	462	244	355	7.10E-18	95.3
TE4.3_Brast01G029800	Brast01G029800	100	1472	0	0	1	1472	1	1472	0	2719
TE4.3_Brast01G031100	Brast01G031100	99.662	8587	29	0	1	8587	1	8587	0	15697
	Brast06G026000	96.748	123	3	1	3973	4095	9018	8897	2.76E-50	204
TE4.3_Brast01G035700	Brast01G035700	99.814	3225	6	0	1	3225	1	3225	0	5923
TE4.3_Brast01G050500	Brast01G050500	99.88	4170	5	0	1	4170	1	4170	0	7673
TE4.3_Brast01G052700	Brast01G052700	99.884	5162	6	0	1	5162	1	5162	0	9500
	Brast02G291000	92.208	154	10	2	2270	2422	3144	2992	2.13E-54	217
TE4.3_Brast01G053400	Brast01G053400	98.745	5577	70	0	1	5577	1	5577	0	10028
	Brast01G053400	94.737	38	2	0	1671	1708	1708	1671	4.10E-07	60.2
	Brast01G107700	97.458	118	3	0	729	846	3588	3471	6.45E-50	202
	Brast01G107700	83.471	121	13	6	730	846	1749	1632	5.20E-21	106
TE4.3_Brast01G055100	Brast01G055100	99.366	2999	19	0	1	2999	1	2999	0	5433
TE4.3_Brast01G055200	Brast01G055200	99.049	7362	70	0	1	7362	1	7362	0	13208

	Brast01G055200	85.965	114	12	4	3012	3123	3123	3012	8.82E-25	119
	Brast01G055200	100	28	0	0	5719	5746	5658	5631	9.07E-05	52.8
	Brast10G027100	96	125	4	1	5624	5747	1648	1772	8.51E-50	202
	Brast10G027100	100	28	0	0	5719	5746	1682	1655	9.07E-05	52.8
TE4.3_Brast01G058700	Brast01G058700	99.005	6834	68	0	1	6834	1	6834	0	12358
	Brast01G058700	91.358	81	5	2	1985	2064	2064	1985	4.93E-22	110
	Brast02G126300	94.167	120	7	0	4491	4610	2269	2150	2.86E-44	183
TE4.3_Brast01G058900	Brast01G058900	99.949	3915	2	0	1	3915	1	3915	0	7219
TE4.3_Brast01G070400	Brast01G070400	99.86	2848	4	0	1	2848	1	2848	0	5240
TE4.3_Brast01G082400	Brast01G082400	99.922	7649	6	0	1	7649	1	7649	0	14092
	Brast01G082500	100	1596	0	0	6054	7649	4388	2793	0	2948
TE4.3_Brast01G086800	Brast01G086800	99.928	6928	5	0	1	6928	1	6928	0	12767
	Brast08G191700	95.402	174	8	0	884	1057	4360	4187	1.29E-72	278
TE4.3_Brast01G092400	Brast01G092400	99.876	4825	6	0	1	4825	1	4825	0	8877
TE4.3_Brast01G095400	Brast01G095400	99.932	4404	3	0	1	4404	1	4404	0	8117
	Brast09G208400	95	220	8	3	1	219	95	312	2.87E-92	342
TE4.3_Brast01G098900	Brast01G098900	99.437	5324	30	0	1	5324	1	5324	0	9666
	Brast01G108400	99.799	5481	11	0	1	5481	1	5481	0	10061
	Brast01G108400	98.413	63	1	0	5065	5127	5005	5067	1.10E-22	111
	Brast01G108400	96.825	63	2	0	5005	5067	5065	5127	5.11E-21	106
	Brast01G108400	83.607	122	10	2	2590	2709	2460	2573	5.11E-21	106
	Brast01G108400	83.607	122	10	2	2460	2573	2590	2709	5.11E-21	106
	Brast02G109800	81.93	570	58	24	2209	2749	1852	1299	1.23E-121	440
TE4.3_Brast01G126500	Brast01G126500	98.534	20058	294	0	1	20058	1	20058	0	35905
	Brast01G126500	99.92	7486	6	0	20745	28230	20745	28230	0	13791
	Brast09G037100	90.282	3046	259	11	13701	16709	919	3964	0	4109
TE4.3_Brast01G134000	Brast01G134000	99.969	9531	3	0	1	9531	1	9531	0	17584
	Brast01G133900	100	686	0	0	8846	9531	1698	1013	0	1267
TE4.3_Brast01G154700	Brast01G154700	100	1455	0	0	1	1455	1	1455	0	2687
	Brast05G202600	90.723	1466	117	9	1	1455	64	1521	0	1936

	Brast01G155300	99.915	2343	2	0	1	2343	1	2343	0	4316
TE4.3_Brast01G155300	Brast01G155300	87.156	109	14	0	906	1014	1194	1302	5.99E-27	124
	Brast01G155300	86.239	109	15	0	1194	1302	906	1014	2.79E-25	119
	Brast05G293100	78.501	707	128	17	1365	2059	712	1406	1.46E-122	442
TE4.3_Brast01G166800	Brast01G166800	99.637	1379	5	0	1	1379	1	1379	0	2519
TE4.3_Brast01G169800	Brast01G169800	99.757	6592	16	0	1	6592	1	6592	0	12085
	Brast07G230700	95.763	118	5	0	2257	2374	11391	11274	1.65E-46	191
TE4.3_Brast01G177000	Brast01G177000	99.464	2800	15	0	1	2800	1	2800	0	5088
TE4.3_Brast01G179700	Brast01G179700	99.682	3778	12	0	1	3778	1	3778	0	6911
	Brast10G132900	94.737	171	9	0	2646	2816	4280	4450	1.52E-69	267
TE4.3_Brast01G185500	Brast01G185500	99.815	4335	8	0	1	4335	1	4335	0	7962
	Brast08G169800	86.047	129	9	4	919	1039	5228	5101	2.39E-28	130
TE4.3_Brast01G188800	Brast01G188800	99.922	8947	7	0	1	8947	1	8947	0	16484
	Brast07G221600	94.068	118	7	0	5777	5894	1161	1044	4.85E-43	180
TE4.3_Brast01G192600	Brast01G192600	99.799	9466	19	0	1	9466	1	9466	0	17376
	Brast09G184000	89.744	78	4	4	8745	8818	4252	4329	5.32E-18	97.1
TE4.3_Brast01G206100	Brast01G206100	99.786	9817	21	0	1	9817	1	9817	0	18013
	Brast01G206100	79.412	136	22	5	8603	8736	8250	8119	2.57E-16	91.6
	Brast01G206100	79.699	133	21	5	8122	8250	8733	8603	2.57E-16	91.6
	Brast05G120900	94.783	115	6	0	1768	1882	2678	2792	5.33E-43	180
TE4.3_Brast01G208000	Brast01G208000	99.878	3268	4	0	1	3268	1	3268	0	6013
	Brast01G208000	97.297	37	0	1	1112	1148	1078	1113	6.66E-08	62.1
	Brast01G208000	97.297	37	0	1	1078	1113	1112	1148	6.66E-08	62.1
	Brast01G207800	79.009	424	87	2	2613	3035	1743	2165	2.81E-76	289
TE4.3_Brast01G212000	Brast01G212000	99.97	3322	1	0	1	3322	1	3322	0	6130
	Brast01G212000	87.356	87	5	1	354	440	276	356	6.68E-18	95.3
	Brast01G212000	87.356	87	5	1	276	356	354	440	6.68E-18	95.3
	Brast04G094900	83.19	1279	170	22	1873	3142	866	2108	0	1129
	Brast04G094900	88.679	265	27	3	1573	1836	540	802	1.01E-85	320
TE4.3_Brast01G224500	Brast01G224500	99.644	5893	21	0	1	5893	1	5893	0	10767

	Brast01G332700	95.968	124	3	1	4864	4985	3766	3643	2.45E-49	200
TE4.3_Brast01G225600	Brast01G225600	99.96	4987	2	0	1	4987	1	4987	0	9199
TE4.3_Brast01G238100	Brast01G238100	99.91	1107	1	0	1	1107	1	1107	0	2039
TE4.3_Brast01G240600	Brast01G240600	99.892	4636	5	0	1	4636	1	4636	0	8534
TE4.3_Brast01G242400	Brast01G242400	99.781	7754	17	0	1	7754	1	7754	0	14229
	Brast05G111200	86.111	180	12	7	4913	5087	4822	4993	1.17E-43	182
TE4.3_Brast01G248300	Brast01G248300	98.656	3571	48	0	3431	7001	3431	7001	0	6410
	Brast01G248300	98.343	1690	28	0	1	1690	1	1690	0	3013
	Brast05G048400	98.515	404	5	1	1288	1690	3058	3461	0	721
	Brast05G048400	93.798	129	8	0	779	907	2517	2645	1.74E-51	207
TE4.3_Brast01G259600	Brast01G259600	99.664	5365	18	0	1	5365	1	5365	0	9821
	Brast03G142100	88.034	234	20	6	3557	3789	4008	3782	1.68E-70	270
TE4.3_Brast01G262700	Brast01G262700	100	2600	0	0	1	2600	1	2600	0	4802
TE4.3_Brast01G281300	Brast01G281300	99.967	6133	2	0	1	6133	1	6133	0	11315
	Brast02G191200	91.794	524	25	5	2307	2818	2218	2735	0	713
TE4.3_Brast01G291400	Brast01G291400	99.335	5712	38	0	1	5712	1	5712	0	10394
	Brast07G103400	95.205	2732	81	21	1	2708	94	2799	0	4320
	Brast07G103400	94.556	698	32	3	3094	3791	3083	3774	0	1081
	Brast07G103400	90.227	573	41	10	4499	5068	4094	4654	0	734
	Brast07G103400	94.226	381	17	2	5082	5462	4713	5088	2.61E-163	579
	Brast07G103400	93.357	286	17	2	4143	4428	3788	4071	4.66E-116	422
	Brast07G103400	94.845	97	5	0	2884	2980	2986	3082	6.74E-35	152
	Brast07G103400	94.898	98	4	1	2788	2885	2795	2891	6.74E-35	152
TE4.3_Brast01G298200	Brast01G298200	99.562	7988	35	0	1	7988	1	7988	0	14608
	Brast01G298200	87.671	146	16	2	1825	1969	1386	1530	9.37E-40	169
	Brast01G298200	87.671	146	16	2	1386	1530	1825	1969	9.37E-40	169
	Brast01G298200	79.352	247	29	13	1093	1323	1323	1563	2.62E-35	154
	Brast01G298200	78.862	246	32	11	1323	1563	1093	1323	1.22E-33	148
	Brast01G298200	89.61	77	7	1	1693	1768	1487	1563	4.49E-18	97.1
	Brast01G298200	89.61	77	7	1	1487	1563	1693	1768	4.49E-18	97.1

	Brast01G298200	76.608	171	22	10	1776	1945	1118	1271	1.62E-12	78.7
	Brast01G298200	76.608	171	22	10	1118	1271	1776	1945	1.62E-12	78.7
	Brast08G009400	89.39	377	35	5	5671	6045	3106	3479	1.37E-132	477
TE4.3_Brast01G302900	Brast01G302900	99.782	2289	5	0	1	2289	1	2289	0	4200
	Brast01G312500	99.928	11073	8	0	1	11073	1	11073	0	20413
TE4.3_Brast01G312500	Brast01G312500	87.356	87	11	0	2013	2099	2099	2013	4.81E-19	100
	Brast08G104200	93.571	420	22	5	5830	6248	698	1113	1.38E-178	630
	Brast01G321900	99.939	4905	3	0	1	4905	1	4905	0	9042
TE4.3_Brast01G321900	Brast03G042200	85.088	3353	461	27	1351	4690	478	3804	0	3386
	Brast01G347600	99.984	6229	1	0	1	6229	1	6229	0	11498
TE4.3_Brast01G347600	Brast02G236800	88.04	301	11	6	20	320	377	102	2.45E-89	333
	Brast01G359700	99.878	20446	25	0	1	20446	1	20446	0	37619
TE4.3_Brast01G359700	Brast05G261500	100	403	0	0	5175	5577	2714	2312	0	745
	Brast05G261500	99.751	402	1	0	5175	5576	7802	7401	0	737
	Brast05G261500	82.5	120	15	6	706	822	8268	8152	8.89E-19	100
	Brast01G361100	99.547	5522	25	0	1	5522	1	5522	0	10059
TE4.3_Brast01G361100	Brast04G296600	94.815	135	6	1	1961	2094	6899	6765	3.81E-52	209
	Brast01G381600	99.949	3888	2	0	1	3888	1	3888	0	7169
TE4.3_Brast01G381600	Brast03G165800	95.238	273	10	3	687	959	4129	3860	1.89E-118	429
	Brast01G401300	99.97	3353	1	0	1	3353	1	3353	0	6187
TE4.3_Brast01G401300	Brast01G402700	99.78	3178	7	0	1	3178	1	3178	0	5830
TE4.3_Brast01G402700	Brast01G402600	89.463	1955	170	24	1121	3062	1060	2991	0	2436
	Brast01G402600	79.545	308	43	15	1	295	20	320	3.66E-50	202
	Brast02G020300	99.273	11003	80	0	1	11003	1	11003	0	19876
TE4.3_Brast02G020300	Brast02G020300	100	40	0	0	9688	9727	9625	9664	2.90E-11	75
	Brast02G020300	100	40	0	0	9625	9664	9688	9727	2.90E-11	75
	Brast02G395700	83.628	226	21	9	3652	3866	9569	9349	1.65E-48	198
	Brast02G395700	77.6	250	34	17	3630	3864	9327	9569	1.70E-28	132
	Brast02G023800	99.784	4161	9	0	1	4161	1	4161	0	7635
TE4.3_Brast02G023800	Brast05G006900	87.302	63	8	0	1985	2047	2552	2614	3.93E-11	73.1

	Brast02G025800	99.236	5107	39	0	1	5107	1	5107	0	9215
TE4.3_Brast02G025800	Brast02G025800	86.735	98	13	0	3964	4061	4061	3964	3.68E-22	110
	Brast02G025900	100	104	0	0	5004	5107	1896	1793	3.55E-47	193
TE4.3_Brast02G031200	Brast02G031200	99.062	7140	67	0	1	7140	1	7140	0	12815
TE4.3_Brast02G038300	Brast02G038300	99.93	4260	3	0	1	4260	1	4260	0	7851
	Brast02G042300	99.974	3908	1	0	1	3908	1	3908	0	7212
TE4.3_Brast02G042300	Brast02G132200	79.904	209	31	8	1305	1510	5886	6086	2.77E-32	143
TE4.3_Brast02G044300	Brast02G044300	99.717	6009	17	0	1	6009	1	6009	0	11027
TE4.3_Brast02G047600	Brast02G047600	99.802	6063	12	0	1	6063	1	6063	0	11130
	Brast02G058800	99.917	4797	4	0	1	4797	1	4797	0	8837
TE4.3_Brast02G058800	Brast06G016000	93.478	92	5	1	3844	3935	2355	2445	5.70E-30	135
	Brast06G016000	89.535	86	7	2	3844	3928	2436	2352	1.24E-21	108
	Brast02G070900	99.81	5254	10	0	1	5254	1	5254	0	9648
TE4.3_Brast02G070900	Brast02G070800	99.593	1227	5	0	1	1227	20	1246	0	2242
	Brast02G070800	97.996	998	9	2	2054	3050	1252	2239	0	1733
	Brast02G079800	99.577	6863	29	0	1	6863	1	6863	0	12539
TE4.3_Brast02G079800	Brast06G096200	97.436	234	3	1	5788	6018	2383	2150	9.43E-109	398
	Brast02G089900	99.89	11795	13	0	1	11795	1	11795	0	21710
TE4.3_Brast02G089900	Brast02G089900	94.872	117	6	0	8527	8643	4390	4506	4.95E-44	183
	Brast02G089900	94.872	117	6	0	4390	4506	8527	8643	4.95E-44	183
	Brast02G299400	90	230	23	0	10241	10470	8073	7844	1.69E-78	298
TE4.3_Brast02G100100	Brast02G100100	99.961	10149	4	0	1	10149	1	10149	0	18720
	Brast02G101400	99.793	7740	16	0	1	7740	1	7740	0	14205
TE4.3_Brast02G101400	Brast04G161800	94.215	363	10	2	4181	4543	902	1253	1.29E-152	544
	Brast04G161800	100	29	0	0	4204	4232	962	990	2.65E-05	54.7
	Brast02G108600	99.33	5520	37	0	1	5520	1	5520	0	10026
TE4.3_Brast02G108600	Brast01G269400	87.5	112	14	0	3920	4031	2726	2615	3.05E-28	130
	Brast01G269400	87.5	64	7	1	3920	3982	2308	2371	5.22E-11	73.1
	Brast02G111400	99.887	6190	7	0	1	6190	1	6190	0	11393
TE4.3_Brast02G111400	Brast04G254100	90.909	88	8	0	4353	4440	4708	4795	7.41E-25	119

TE4.3_Brast02G129400	Brast02G129400	99.704	1687	5	0	1	1687	1	1687	0	3090
TE4.3_Brast02G130000	Brast02G130000	99.94	3318	2	0	1	3318	1	3318	0	6117
	Brast05G075200	87.356	174	19	3	1578	1750	3832	4003	1.78E-48	196
TE4.3_Brast02G130300	Brast02G130300	99.941	3391	2	0	1	3391	1	3391	0	6252
	Brast04G262400	92.373	236	16	2	775	1009	5229	4995	3.69E-90	335
TE4.3_Brast02G131500	Brast02G131500	99.808	5208	10	0	1	5208	1	5208	0	9563
TE4.3_Brast02G132600	Brast02G132600	99.663	2373	8	0	1	2373	1	2373	0	4338
	Brast02G217200	95.745	47	2	0	2327	2373	6604	6650	1.72E-12	76.8
TE4.3_Brast02G134900	Brast02G134900	99.784	4627	10	0	1	4627	1	4627	0	8490
	Brast01G238600	96.8	125	4	0	1625	1749	2060	1936	3.19E-52	209
TE4.3_Brast02G135800	Brast02G135800	99.258	8893	66	0	1	8893	1	8893	0	16172
	Brast02G136100	90.594	202	19	0	4076	4277	4	205	1.00E-69	268
TE4.3_Brast02G142700	Brast02G142700	99.923	3899	3	0	1	3899	1	3899	0	7184
TE4.3_Brast02G155800	Brast02G155800	99.783	7847	17	0	1	7847	1	7847	0	14397
	Brast03G278100	96.124	129	5	0	799	927	2218	2090	1.51E-52	211
	Brast03G278100	93.162	117	8	0	807	923	1029	913	7.12E-41	172
TE4.3_Brast02G170000	Brast02G170000	99.89	3650	4	0	1	3650	1	3650	0	6719
TE4.3_Brast02G179700	Brast02G179700	99.884	13852	16	0	1	13852	1	13852	0	25492
	Brast02G179700	93.878	49	2	1	10163	10210	10117	10165	1.31E-10	73.1
	Brast02G179700	93.878	49	2	1	10117	10165	10163	10210	1.31E-10	73.1
	Brast01G237100	98.276	116	2	0	10433	10548	4494	4379	4.46E-50	204
	Brast01G237100	94.737	114	6	0	10435	10548	11917	12030	2.70E-42	178
	Brast01G237100	91.964	112	9	0	10437	10548	14490	14601	3.52E-36	158
	Brast01G237100	94.643	56	3	0	10435	10490	14434	14489	4.69E-15	87.9
TE4.3_Brast02G201200	Brast02G201200	100	1801	0	0	1	1801	1	1801	0	3326
	Brast02G201400	79.331	329	51	12	530	856	775	1088	2.65E-54	215
	Brast02G201400	79.221	154	27	4	281	433	519	668	2.15E-20	102
TE4.3_Brast02G201600	Brast02G201600	99.965	2873	1	0	1	2873	1	2873	0	5301
	Brast02G201700	80.414	531	85	16	1642	2165	804	1322	8.51E-106	387
TE4.3_Brast02G207000	Brast02G207000	99.941	13580	8	0	1	13580	1	13580	0	25034

	Brast02G207100	100	351	0	0	1642	1992	351	1	0	649
TE4.3_Brast02G213000	Brast02G213000	100	1487	0	0	1	1487	1	1487	0	2747
	Brast02G215700	99.833	6592	11	0	1	6592	1	6592	0	12113
TE4.3_Brast02G215700	Brast07G230700	93.913	115	7	0	1130	1244	11386	11272	1.66E-41	174
TE4.3_Brast02G218400	Brast02G218400	99.844	1923	3	0	1	1923	1	1923	0	3535
	Brast02G219700	99.529	4879	23	0	1	4879	1	4879	0	8883
	Brast02G219700	97.561	41	0	1	2208	2247	1711	1751	5.96E-10	69.4
	Brast02G219700	97.561	41	0	1	1711	1751	2208	2247	5.96E-10	69.4
TE4.3_Brast02G219700	Brast02G219700	86.364	66	2	2	3669	3734	3607	3665	7.71E-09	65.8
	Brast02G219700	86.364	66	2	2	3607	3665	3669	3734	7.71E-09	65.8
	Brast06G111700	77.554	646	137	8	2209	2850	515	1156	1.87E-104	383
	Brast06G111700	81	200	32	6	353	549	231	427	1.60E-35	154
TE4.3_Brast02G225400	Brast02G225400	99.809	11521	22	0	1	11521	1	11521	0	21160
	Brast02G345800	86.667	255	33	1	3327	3581	1433	1686	1.67E-73	281
TE4.3_Brast02G226100	Brast02G226100	99.899	1977	2	0	1	1977	1	1977	0	3640
	Brast08G131800	76.63	552	116	12	1128	1671	1024	1570	1.31E-77	292
TE4.3_Brast02G239200	Brast02G239200	99.311	1597	11	0	1	1597	1	1597	0	2889
TE4.3_Brast02G245400	Brast02G245400	99.883	1709	2	0	1	1709	1	1709	0	3145
	Brast02G252100	99.849	6601	10	0	1	6601	1	6601	0	12135
TE4.3_Brast02G252100	Brast02G283900	91.892	74	5	1	3767	3839	2088	2015	7.97E-20	102
	Brast02G262200	99.889	6287	7	0	1	6287	1	6287	0	11572
TE4.3_Brast02G262200	Brast04G262400	92.614	176	9	4	1895	2069	5058	5230	2.56E-64	250
TE4.3_Brast02G271200	Brast02G271200	99.813	9099	17	0	1	9099	1	9099	0	16709
	Brast02G272100	100	3301	0	0	1	3301	1	3301	0	6096
TE4.3_Brast02G272100	Brast05G095700	79.487	195	27	5	190	380	121	306	2.35E-27	126
	Brast02G277100	99.857	5589	8	0	1	5589	1	5589	0	10277
TE4.3_Brast02G277100	Brast06G062300	93.103	58	3	1	2342	2398	1441	1384	2.44E-14	84.2
	Brast02G280800	99.928	17981	13	0	1	17981	1	17981	0	33137
TE4.3_Brast02G280800	Brast07G245100	88.77	187	13	6	3256	3434	11436	11622	1.60E-55	222
TE4.3_Brast02G281800	Brast02G281800	99.957	4649	2	0	1	4649	1	4649	0	8575

	Brast03G022900	87.153	288	31	3	3677	3964	4448	4167	3.95E-86	322
TE4.3_Brast02G299100	Brast02G299100	99.846	4532	7	0	1	4532	1	4532	0	8331
	Brast02G299000	100	242	0	0	1	242	242	1	6.09E-124	448
TE4.3_Brast02G299700	Brast02G299700	99.872	17973	23	0	1	17973	1	17973	0	33063
TE4.3_Brast02G299800	Brast02G299800	99.844	4475	7	0	1	4475	1	4475	0	8226
	Brast02G306600	99.861	11487	16	0	1	11487	1	11487	0	21124
TE4.3_Brast02G306600	Brast02G306600	94.118	68	0	3	7404	7469	7469	7404	4.99E-19	100
	Brast02G306600	97.059	34	1	0	4751	4784	4872	4905	3.05E-06	58.4
	Brast02G137200	92.857	140	8	2	10567	10705	2763	2901	1.33E-49	202
TE4.3_Brast02G319800	Brast02G319800	99.975	3937	1	0	1	3937	1	3937	0	7267
	Brast02G245700	93.103	87	6	0	840	926	1537	1451	7.82E-28	128
TE4.3_Brast02G339200	Brast02G339200	99.6	3750	15	0	1	3750	1	3750	0	6844
	Brast02G340900	99.946	7435	4	0	1	7435	1	7435	0	13708
TE4.3_Brast02G340900	Brast02G340900	84.615	91	14	0	1103	1193	4419	4329	1.94E-16	91.6
	Brast02G340900	88.732	71	8	0	4352	4422	1170	1100	2.51E-15	87.9
	Brast04G262500	99.18	122	1	0	4329	4450	5605	5484	2.37E-55	220
	Brast04G262500	84.211	95	13	2	1077	1170	5489	5582	1.94E-16	91.6
TE4.3_Brast02G346000	Brast02G346000	99.887	4441	5	0	1	4441	1	4441	0	8174
TE4.3_Brast02G346000	Brast06G184000	75.149	837	163	34	1424	2236	1716	2531	4.81E-95	351
TE4.3_Brast02G364300	Brast02G364300	99.952	4200	2	0	1	4200	1	4200	0	7745
	Brast02G375500	99.937	6352	4	0	1	6352	1	6352	0	11708
TE4.3_Brast02G375500	Brast02G375500	97.143	70	1	1	2735	2804	2671	2739	2.74E-24	117
	Brast02G375500	97.143	70	1	1	2671	2739	2735	2804	2.74E-24	117
TE4.3_Brast02G380400	Brast02G380400	99.389	4090	25	0	1	4090	1	4090	0	7415
	Brast06G144400	82.559	969	166	2	1098	2063	1065	2033	0	850
TE4.3_Brast03G013700	Brast03G013700	99.518	9550	46	0	1	9550	1	9550	0	17431
	Brast05G250400	94.175	103	5	1	8703	8805	663	562	8.73E-36	156
TE4.3_Brast03G028200	Brast03G028200	99.988	8049	1	0	1	8049	1	8049	0	14859
	Brast03G028200	97.143	70	2	0	3573	3642	3358	3427	9.65E-25	119
	Brast03G028200	97.143	70	2	0	3358	3427	3573	3642	9.65E-25	119

	Brast06G164600	97.189	249	6	1	2481	2729	192	439	2.36E-115	420
	Brast03G036300	99.394	3632	22	0	6059	9690	6059	9690	0	6589
	Brast03G036300	99.14	3138	27	0	1	3138	1	3138	0	5651
	Brast03G036300	99.749	398	1	0	7268	7665	2143	2540	0	730
	Brast03G036300	99.5	400	2	0	2143	2542	7268	7667	0	730
TE4.3_Brast03G036300	Brast03G036300	100	28	0	0	7767	7794	7705	7678	1.20E-04	52.8
	Brast03G036300	100	28	0	0	7678	7705	7794	7767	1.20E-04	52.8
	Brast06G166200	95.712	1609	68	1	6059	7667	4422	2815	0	2595
	Brast06G166200	94.584	997	49	3	2143	3138	7995	7003	0	1543
	Brast06G166200	96.5	400	14	0	2143	2542	3214	2815	0	665
	Brast06G166200	93.766	401	20	3	7268	7667	7995	7599	1.22E-168	597
TE4.3_Brast03G040400	Brast03G040400	99.693	2929	9	0	1	2929	1	2929	0	5360
	Brast06G098100	85.787	197	15	11	1530	1718	1893	1702	1.57E-48	196
TE4.3_Brast03G041500	Brast03G041500	99.73	4080	11	0	1	4080	1	4080	0	7474
	Brast07G059600	96.842	95	1	2	3295	3387	3321	3415	1.03E-36	158
TE4.3_Brast03G045500	Brast03G045500	99.805	5138	10	0	1	5138	1	5138	0	9433
	Brast03G061600	98.96	1442	15	0	1	1442	1	1442	0	2580
TE4.3_Brast03G061600	Brast02G295300	88.976	381	36	5	802	1176	810	1190	5.28E-130	466
	Brast02G295300	84.104	346	49	3	11	351	6	350	7.23E-89	329
	Brast02G295300	90.64	203	19	0	500	702	494	696	4.44E-71	270
TE4.3_Brast03G063800	Brast03G063800	99.762	5051	12	0	1	5051	1	5051	0	9262
	Brast09G197100	76.935	633	103	36	3183	3804	3764	4364	1.54E-85	320
	Brast09G197100	76.037	434	85	16	1915	2343	2767	3186	1.25E-51	207
TE4.3_Brast03G066900	Brast03G066900	99.921	3803	3	0	1	3803	1	3803	0	7007
TE4.3_Brast03G070500	Brast03G070500	99.722	2880	8	0	1	2880	1	2880	0	5275
	Brast01G082100	85.185	54	5	1	1153	1206	2558	2608	3.53E-05	52.8
TE4.3_Brast03G077600	Brast03G077600	99.858	7031	10	0	1	7031	1	7031	0	12929
	Brast03G077600	100	28	0	0	1513	1540	1478	1505	8.66E-05	52.8
	Brast03G077600	100	28	0	0	1478	1505	1513	1540	8.66E-05	52.8
	Brast08G078200	84.099	1893	269	23	4726	6600	2707	4585	0	1799

	Brast08G078200	87.368	95	8	3	1349	1439	708	614	6.56E-21	106
	Brast03G129300	97.604	8430	202	0	1	8430	1	8430	0	14781
TE4.3_Brast03G129300	Brast01G269100	85.03	1503	162	27	4349	5821	3647	2178	0	1640
	Brast01G269100	88.012	659	60	6	3263	3921	4312	3673	0	826
	Brast01G269100	90.351	456	34	7	5819	6267	1905	1453	1.37E-172	610
	Brast01G269100	89.097	321	25	8	2944	3260	4652	4338	6.93E-111	405
TE4.3_Brast03G137200	Brast03G137200	99.814	8044	15	0	1	8044	1	8044	0	14772
	Brast06G141800	92.019	213	16	1	1	213	32	243	1.15E-78	298
TE4.3_Brast03G139800	Brast03G139800	99.783	13801	30	0	1	13801	1	13801	0	25320
	Brast03G130800	98.227	282	4	1	35	315	7	288	8.47E-137	492
TE4.3_Brast03G144000	Brast03G144000	99.802	8585	17	0	1	8585	1	8585	0	15762
	Brast03G144000	94.382	89	5	0	4088	4176	4173	4085	2.84E-30	137
	Brast03G190200	86.997	323	26	7	6428	6739	3037	3354	3.35E-94	350
	Brast03G190200	85.246	122	8	4	5920	6041	2061	2172	3.70E-24	117
TE4.3_Brast03G145700	Brast03G145700	99.866	6718	9	0	1	6718	1	6718	0	12362
	Brast03G145700	88.412	233	22	2	2965	3197	3060	3287	3.49E-73	279
	Brast03G145700	87.983	233	23	2	3060	3287	2965	3197	5.84E-71	272
	Brast03G145700	87.069	232	24	5	3633	3861	4260	4032	4.55E-67	259
	Brast03G145700	87.069	232	24	5	4032	4260	3861	3633	1.64E-66	257
	Brast03G145700	97.297	37	1	0	615	651	72	108	3.83E-08	63.9
	Brast03G145700	97.297	37	1	0	72	108	615	651	3.83E-08	63.9
	Brast03G145800	89.108	1570	153	10	4327	5888	11008	12567	0	1936
Brast03G145800	79.781	183	31	3	103	279	88	270	1.34E-27	128	
TE4.3_Brast03G163900	Brast03G163900	99.917	10806	9	0	1	10806	1	10806	0	19906
	Brast02G258500	93.213	221	15	0	8279	8499	1411	1631	7.12E-87	326
TE4.3_Brast03G166800	Brast03G166800	98.381	2038	33	0	1	2038	1	2038	0	3640
	Brast08G213800	74.227	291	67	6	277	560	212	501	6.73E-26	121
TE4.3_Brast03G177800	Brast03G177800	99.407	9789	58	0	1	9789	1	9789	0	17850
	Brast03G177900	100	713	0	0	5905	6617	1	713	0	1317
TE4.3_Brast03G185000	Brast03G185000	100	4552	0	0	1	4552	1	4552	0	8407

	Brast04G244700	76.248	581	130	8	825	1401	1231	1807	5.04E-80	302
TE4.3_Brast03G185200	Brast03G185200	99.951	2046	1	0	1	2046	1	2046	0	3773
	Brast03G216200	99.798	3968	8	0	1	3968	1	3968	0	7284
TE4.3_Brast03G216200	Brast10G113400	94.444	54	0	2	1053	1106	1350	1400	2.24E-13	80.5
	Brast03G228000	99.98	9781	2	0	1	9781	1	9781	0	18052
	Brast03G228000	99.01	101	1	0	3257	3357	3156	3256	1.48E-43	182
	Brast03G228000	99.01	101	1	0	3156	3256	3257	3357	1.48E-43	182
TE4.3_Brast03G228000	Brast03G036300	96.61	118	4	0	5725	5842	8453	8336	5.27E-48	196
	Brast03G036300	100	32	0	0	8616	8647	7678	7709	7.21E-07	60.2
	Brast03G036300	100	30	0	0	8611	8640	8331	8360	9.33E-06	56.5
	Brast03G036300	100	29	0	0	8615	8643	7795	7767	3.36E-05	54.7
	Brast03G266900	99.885	6959	8	0	1	6959	1	6959	0	12807
TE4.3_Brast03G266900	Brast04G045600	90.826	109	10	0	578	686	537	645	3.82E-33	147
TE4.3_Brast03G278800	Brast03G278800	99.85	2000	3	0	1	2000	1	2000	0	3677
	Brast03G280600	99.809	7346	14	0	1	7346	1	7346	0	13489
TE4.3_Brast03G280600	Brast03G280600	94.872	39	1	1	732	769	699	737	5.41E-07	60.2
	Brast03G280600	94.872	39	1	1	699	737	732	769	5.41E-07	60.2
	Brast02G377500	95.082	122	6	0	1852	1973	4095	3974	5.11E-47	193
TE4.3_Brast03G284400	Brast03G284400	99.25	2535	19	0	1	2535	1	2535	0	4577
	Brast03G288800	99.83	12356	21	0	1	12356	1	12356	0	22701
TE4.3_Brast03G288800	Brast03G288800	97.778	45	1	0	5805	5849	5760	5804	2.52E-12	78.7
	Brast03G288800	97.778	45	1	0	5760	5804	5805	5849	2.52E-12	78.7
	Brast03G288700	99.864	738	1	0	11619	12356	5319	4582	0	1358
TE4.3_Brast03G292800	Brast03G292800	99.422	4325	25	0	1	4325	1	4325	0	7849
	Brast03G309200	99.913	4586	4	0	1	4586	1	4586	0	8447
TE4.3_Brast03G309200	Brast04G052200	84.951	206	31	0	156	361	176	381	3.16E-52	209
TE4.3_Brast04G008200	Brast04G008200	98.781	7384	90	0	1	7384	1	7384	0	13278
	Brast04G012400	99.671	3647	12	0	1	3647	1	3647	0	6669
TE4.3_Brast04G012400	Brast07G089600	83.523	704	91	20	48	734	146	841	3.50E-180	634
TE4.3_Brast04G024000	Brast04G024000	100	2886	0	0	1	2886	1	2886	0	5330

TE4.3_Brast04G034600	Brast04G034600	99.882	5102	6	0	1	5102	1	5102	0	9389
	Brast04G036600	99.51	11644	57	0	2532	14175	2532	14175	0	21232
	Brast04G036600	99.187	2582	8	1	2532	5100	11356	13937	0	4639
	Brast04G036600	99.148	2582	9	1	11356	13937	2532	5100	0	4634
	Brast04G036600	99.88	1673	2	0	1	1673	1	1673	0	3079
	Brast04G036600	96.599	1029	23	5	645	1673	9313	10329	0	1701
	Brast04G036600	96.404	1029	25	5	9313	10329	645	1673	0	1690
TE4.3_Brast04G036600	Brast04G036600	96.124	387	12	3	8862	9247	33	417	6.36E-178	628
	Brast04G036600	95.866	387	13	3	33	417	8862	9247	2.96E-176	623
	Brast04G036600	98.507	67	1	0	496	562	9244	9310	1.70E-24	119
	Brast04G036600	97.015	67	2	0	9244	9310	496	562	7.92E-23	113
	Brast04G036600	88.372	86	10	0	563	648	648	563	4.76E-20	104
	Brast04G036800	100	2792	0	0	2542	5333	1	2792	0	5156
	Brast04G036800	99.145	2572	9	1	11366	13937	1	2559	0	4615
TE4.3_Brast04G038900	Brast04G038900	99.728	6256	17	0	1	6256	1	6256	0	11459
	Brast04G052800	99.883	5978	7	0	1	5978	1	5978	0	11001
TE4.3_Brast04G052800	Brast04G052700	100	341	0	0	5638	5978	1620	1280	7.44E-179	630
TE4.3_Brast04G053800	Brast04G053800	99.887	3541	4	0	1	3541	1	3541	0	6517
TE4.3_Brast04G054000	Brast04G054000	99.581	6929	29	0	1	6929	1	6929	0	12661
TE4.3_Brast04G057100	Brast04G057100	99.789	3794	8	0	1	3794	1	3794	0	6962
TE4.3_Brast04G058400	Brast04G058400	99.355	4958	32	0	1	4958	1	4958	0	8979
TE4.3_Brast04G067800	Brast04G067800	99.858	4938	7	0	1	4938	1	4938	0	9081
	Brast04G080500	99.909	5524	5	0	1	5524	1	5524	0	10174
TE4.3_Brast04G080500	Brast04G236600	91.25	160	9	4	614	770	702	545	2.95E-53	213
	Brast04G084800	99.83	4696	8	0	1	4696	1	4696	0	8628
TE4.3_Brast04G084800	Brast08G094600	87.362	1907	116	67	2824	4696	185	2000	0	2071
TE4.3_Brast04G089100	Brast04G089100	99.907	2154	2	0	1	2154	1	2154	0	3967
	Brast04G118300	99.826	9793	17	0	1	9793	1	9793	0	17991
TE4.3_Brast04G118300	Brast09G072500	81.043	422	33	17	3944	4327	4277	3865	6.54E-77	292
	Brast09G072500	88.421	95	11	0	840	934	1460	1366	1.52E-23	115

TE4.3_Brast04G127800	Brast04G127800	98.878	6060	68	0	1	6060	1	6060	0	10890
	Brast03G165300	91.566	166	14	0	3248	3413	1845	1680	3.21E-58	230
TE4.3_Brast04G133600	Brast04G133600	99.483	7743	40	0	1	7743	1	7743	0	14144
	Brast04G133700	99.905	1054	1	0	2373	3426	1054	1	0	1941
TE4.3_Brast04G136400	Brast04G136400	99.828	10437	18	0	1	10437	1	10437	0	19174
	Brast05G257200	95.041	121	6	0	8511	8631	1513	1393	2.62E-46	191
TE4.3_Brast04G140500	Brast04G140500	99.755	4493	11	0	1	4493	1	4493	0	8237
	Brast09G132900	76.264	910	203	9	3316	4223	4100	4998	3.58E-131	472
	Brast09G132900	85.135	444	54	8	260	694	412	852	7.80E-123	444
TE4.3_Brast04G151100	Brast04G151100	99.857	2805	4	0	1	2805	1	2805	0	5158
	Brast04G102800	100	42	0	0	1801	1842	3210	3251	5.68E-13	78.7
TE4.3_Brast04G152900	Brast04G152900	99.37	5397	34	0	1	5397	1	5397	0	9821
	Brast04G152900	96.703	91	3	0	3845	3935	3563	3653	6.37E-35	152
	Brast04G152900	96.703	91	3	0	3563	3653	3845	3935	6.37E-35	152
	Brast04G096000	92.373	118	7	2	3201	3318	906	1021	2.27E-39	167
TE4.3_Brast04G185800	Brast04G185800	99.852	2701	4	0	1	2701	1	2701	0	4966
	Brast04G185800	91.509	212	16	2	1652	1862	1862	1652	6.45E-77	291
	Brast04G143400	90.498	221	15	5	1641	1860	1005	1220	8.34E-76	287
	Brast04G143400	85.238	210	25	6	1654	1861	1219	1014	5.16E-53	211
TE4.3_Brast04G206600	Brast04G206600	99.782	6889	15	0	1	6889	1	6889	0	12639
	Brast04G206600	91.753	194	13	1	4302	4492	3151	3344	2.78E-69	267
	Brast03G234300	87.77	1251	129	16	3025	4268	4263	3030	0	1443
	Brast03G234300	91.343	335	27	2	3012	3345	3076	2743	1.54E-126	457
	Brast03G234300	89.175	194	17	4	4302	4492	4138	3946	1.69E-61	241
TE4.3_Brast04G208500	Brast04G208500	99.657	15455	53	0	1	15455	1	15455	0	28262
	Brast04G208500	93.939	66	3	1	14222	14287	14186	14250	2.42E-18	99
	Brast04G208500	93.939	66	3	1	14186	14250	14222	14287	2.42E-18	99
	Brast02G261900	86.036	222	28	2	3812	4030	1637	1858	1.77E-59	235
	Brast02G261900	78.148	270	50	5	3791	4053	1880	1613	8.45E-38	163
TE4.3_Brast04G211400	Brast04G211400	99.843	6382	10	0	1	6382	1	6382	0	11738

	Brast04G211400	83.495	103	13	4	1766	1866	1863	1763	4.63E-17	93.5
	Brast06G202800	92.857	112	8	0	1752	1863	10194	10305	3.48E-38	163
	Brast06G202800	87	100	11	2	1765	1863	10306	10208	1.28E-22	111
	Brast04G236400	99.972	17978	5	0	1	17978	1	17978	0	33172
	Brast04G236400	79.435	248	26	12	15372	15616	15632	15857	2.13E-34	152
	Brast04G236400	79.032	248	27	12	15632	15857	15372	15616	9.90E-33	147
TE4.3_Brast04G236400	Brast04G236400	100	76	0	0	10676	10751	10600	10675	4.61E-31	141
	Brast04G236400	100	76	0	0	10600	10675	10676	10751	4.61E-31	141
	Brast04G236400	100	32	0	0	8354	8385	8230	8261	1.33E-06	60.2
	Brast02G012800	97.581	124	3	0	11074	11197	1448	1571	9.62E-53	213
	Brast04G270900	99.715	4913	14	0	1	4913	1	4913	0	8997
TE4.3_Brast04G270900	Brast03G027900	96.719	640	17	2	1577	2216	1037	1672	0	1064
	Brast04G283100	99.918	9798	8	0	1	9798	1	9798	0	18050
TE4.3_Brast04G283100	Brast06G141000	90.306	196	18	1	8824	9018	1021	1216	8.58E-66	255
	Brast06G141000	79.268	164	20	9	5561	5713	1056	1216	1.18E-19	102
TE4.3_Brast04G287900	Brast04G287900	99.924	2642	2	0	1	2642	1	2642	0	4868
	Brast04G290000	99.856	4853	7	0	1	4853	1	4853	0	8924
	Brast04G290000	96.429	84	3	0	3417	3500	3331	3414	4.46E-31	139
TE4.3_Brast04G290000	Brast04G290000	96.429	84	3	0	3331	3414	3417	3500	4.46E-31	139
	Brast04G290000	98.684	76	1	0	3226	3301	3171	3246	5.76E-30	135
	Brast04G289800	100	150	0	0	4704	4853	2996	2847	9.05E-73	278
	Brast04G294800	99.873	17321	22	0	1	17321	1	17321	0	31874
TE4.3_Brast04G294800	Brast04G294800	100	29	0	0	11338	11366	11761	11733	5.95E-05	54.7
	Brast04G171400	76.527	622	107	26	5242	5834	773	1384	5.35E-80	303
	Brast04G305500	99.681	8162	26	0	1	8162	1	8162	0	14929
TE4.3_Brast04G305500	Brast09G243900	95.96	99	3	1	3441	3538	9810	9908	5.76E-37	159
	Brast09G243900	85.859	99	13	1	3441	3538	9908	9810	2.74E-20	104
	Brast04G307600	99.744	8588	22	0	1	8588	1	8588	0	15738
TE4.3_Brast04G307600	Brast04G307600	82.653	98	17	0	7920	8017	8017	7920	2.90E-15	87.9
	Brast04G307500	99.664	298	1	0	8291	8588	1939	1642	3.99E-153	545

TE4.3_Brast04G311100	Brast04G311100	99.532	3632	17	0	1	3632	1	3632	0	6613
TE4.3_Brast04G328600	Brast04G328600	99.599	3493	14	0	1	3493	1	3493	0	6373
TE4.3_Brast04G329600	Brast04G329600	99.815	3778	7	0	1	3778	1	3778	0	6942
TE4.3_Brast04G332100	Brast04G332100	99.947	1889	1	0	1	1889	1	1889	0	3485
	Brast09G084700	80.952	210	23	10	2	201	238	440	7.95E-35	150
TE4.3_Brast05G013800	Brast05G013800	99.948	5741	3	0	1	5741	1	5741	0	10586
	Brast05G013700	87.819	1568	143	32	14	1558	3	1545	0	1794
	Brast05G013700	83.927	1039	157	10	1900	2936	1823	2853	0	985
	Brast05G013700	82.424	330	43	12	5409	5737	5420	5735	1.39E-71	274
	Brast05G013700	85.47	234	29	1	1590	1818	1544	1777	5.06E-61	239
TE4.3_Brast05G023500	Brast05G023500	96.71	2675	84	4	1	2673	1	2673	0	4460
	Brast02G211200	94.872	117	6	0	2109	2225	3706	3590	1.11E-44	183
TE4.3_Brast05G034500	Brast05G034500	99.111	10573	94	0	1	10573	1	10573	0	19004
TE4.3_Brast05G040500	Brast05G040500	99.638	3594	13	0	1	3594	1	3594	0	6573
TE4.3_Brast05G079500	Brast05G079500	99.844	6397	10	0	1	6397	1	6397	0	11758
TE4.3_Brast05G086700	Brast05G086700	99.796	10307	21	0	1	10307	1	10307	0	18921
	Brast05G086700	95.023	221	9	1	8367	8585	8257	8477	1.45E-93	348
	Brast05G086700	95.023	221	9	1	8257	8477	8367	8585	1.45E-93	348
	Brast05G086700	93.277	119	5	2	8477	8592	8257	8375	9.36E-41	172
	Brast05G086700	94.595	111	4	1	8257	8367	8477	8585	3.37E-40	171
	Brast02G287500	92.771	249	16	2	4736	4983	3283	3036	6.69E-97	359
TE4.3_Brast05G105700	Brast05G105700	99.732	6348	17	0	1	6348	1	6348	0	11629
	Brast05G246800	99.187	123	1	0	3806	3928	10758	10880	5.63E-56	222
TE4.3_Brast05G112600	Brast05G112600	100	1962	0	0	1	1962	1	1962	0	3624
TE4.3_Brast05G114900	Brast05G114900	99.865	3692	5	0	1	3692	1	3692	0	6791
TE4.3_Brast05G124200	Brast05G124200	99.864	4401	6	0	1	4401	1	4401	0	8094
	Brast03G081800	92.202	218	17	0	1931	2148	1494	1711	2.91E-82	309
TE4.3_Brast05G129600	Brast05G129600	99.609	5366	21	0	1	5366	1	5366	0	9799
TE4.3_Brast05G131800	Brast05G131800	99.942	5207	3	0	1	5207	1	5207	0	9601
	Brast05G131700	99.514	5140	8	3	72	5207	1	5127	0	9337

	Brast05G139400	99.791	3829	8	0	1	3829	1	3829	0	7036
TE4.3_Brast05G139400	Brast04G067500	94.808	1483	64	5	421	1897	15	1490	0	2300
	Brast04G067500	88.795	1892	135	39	1932	3797	1584	3424	0	2248
	Brast05G144800	99.751	6034	15	0	1	6034	1	6034	0	11060
	Brast05G144800	91.525	118	6	3	4770	4883	1371	1488	4.26E-37	159
TE4.3_Brast05G144800	Brast05G144800	91.525	118	6	3	1371	1488	4770	4883	4.26E-37	159
	Brast08G168700	97.541	122	3	0	1372	1493	2122	2243	4.17E-52	209
	Brast08G168700	93.162	117	4	1	4771	4883	2122	2238	7.08E-40	169
TE4.3_Brast05G152400	Brast05G152400	99.924	1316	1	0	1	1316	1	1316	0	2425
	Brast05G213600	98.741	5641	71	0	1	5641	1	5641	0	10131
TE4.3_Brast05G213600	Brast05G213600	97.024	168	5	0	4135	4302	3927	4094	2.26E-74	283
	Brast05G213600	95.238	168	8	0	3927	4094	4135	4302	1.36E-71	274
	Brast05G222500	99.485	5048	26	0	1	5048	1	5048	0	9178
TE4.3_Brast05G222500	Brast01G185900	78.756	193	31	8	2259	2447	1366	1552	1.68E-25	121
TE4.3_Brast05G227300	Brast05G227300	99.825	5156	9	0	1	5156	1	5156	0	9472
	Brast05G230800	99.689	3211	10	0	1	3211	1	3211	0	5875
TE4.3_Brast05G230800	Brast05G279200	86.861	137	12	4	540	676	8462	8332	4.88E-34	148
	Brast05G232400	99.827	9830	17	0	1	9830	1	9830	0	18081
TE4.3_Brast05G232400	Brast05G232400	91.102	236	19	2	1193	1427	1424	1190	1.08E-84	318
	Brast02G325600	93.818	275	14	3	3845	4117	5403	5676	1.74E-112	411
TE4.3_Brast05G246400	Brast05G246400	99.793	5321	11	0	1	5321	1	5321	0	9766
	Brast05G260800	99.817	7637	12	2	1	7636	1	7636	0	14024
TE4.3_Brast05G260800	Brast08G142600	89.137	313	27	3	5139	5445	1623	1934	2.94E-104	383
	Brast05G265400	99.85	5336	8	0	1	5336	1	5336	0	9810
TE4.3_Brast05G265400	Brast01G386000	90.164	244	23	1	3947	4189	2039	1796	1.26E-86	324
	Brast01G386000	90.476	84	6	2	4078	4161	2019	1938	3.84E-22	110
	Brast05G276700	99.781	6399	14	0	1	6399	1	6399	0	11740
TE4.3_Brast05G276700	Brast05G276700	100	69	0	0	2403	2471	2334	2402	1.27E-27	128
	Brast05G276700	98.551	69	1	0	2334	2402	2403	2471	5.93E-26	122
TE4.3_Brast05G300300	Brast05G300300	99.833	7207	12	0	1	7207	1	7207	0	13243

	Brast06G009700	99.491	4515	23	0	1	4515	1	4515	0	8242
TE4.3_Brast06G009700	Brast02G167400	93.229	192	11	2	1717	1907	1696	1886	6.51E-74	281
	Brast02G167400	79.947	379	46	18	354	732	453	801	1.42E-65	254
	Brast02G167400	87.079	178	18	3	1462	1635	1436	1612	2.42E-48	196
	Brast02G167400	86.301	146	20	0	2220	2365	2190	2335	3.18E-37	159
TE4.3_Brast06G031600	Brast06G031600	99.879	1657	2	0	1	1657	1	1657	0	3049
TE4.3_Brast06G034800	Brast06G034800	99.753	2831	7	0	1	2831	1	2831	0	5190
	Brast06G042100	99.79	10015	21	0	1	10015	1	10015	0	18378
TE4.3_Brast06G042100	Brast06G042100	96.307	352	11	2	4524	4874	4696	5046	1.65E-162	577
	Brast06G042100	95.455	352	14	2	4696	5046	4524	4874	1.66E-157	560
	Brast06G042100	92.265	181	12	2	4524	4703	4867	5046	8.78E-66	255
	Brast06G042100	89.848	197	16	4	4852	5046	4509	4703	4.08E-64	250
	Brast02G311700	98.413	126	2	0	7136	7261	5357	5232	8.90E-56	222
TE4.3_Brast06G047400	Brast06G047400	99.795	5370	11	0	1	5370	1	5370	0	9856
	Brast06G065900	99.955	4437	2	0	1	4437	1	4437	0	8183
TE4.3_Brast06G065900	Brast06G065900	86.207	58	7	1	1656	1712	1548	1605	9.07E-08	62.1
	Brast06G065900	86.207	58	7	1	1548	1605	1656	1712	9.07E-08	62.1
	Brast09G044700	95.349	43	2	0	1957	1999	6161	6203	5.42E-10	69.4
	Brast06G074200	99.681	8473	27	0	1	8473	1	8473	0	15501
TE4.3_Brast06G074200	Brast01G205500	92.661	109	8	0	3978	4086	4673	4781	2.15E-36	158
	Brast06G085500	99.775	17303	39	0	1	17303	1	17303	0	31737
TE4.3_Brast06G085500	Brast06G085500	89.516	124	13	0	10388	10511	7398	7521	4.40E-36	158
	Brast06G085500	89.516	124	13	0	7398	7521	10388	10511	4.40E-36	158
	Brast06G085500	85.915	142	8	10	10587	10722	10722	10587	4.43E-31	141
	Brast06G085500	86.179	123	13	4	7405	7525	1733	1853	9.60E-28	130
	Brast06G085500	86.179	123	13	4	1733	1853	7405	7525	9.60E-28	130
	Brast06G085500	83.942	137	11	9	10365	10494	1701	1833	5.78E-25	121
	Brast06G085500	83.942	137	11	9	1701	1833	10365	10494	5.78E-25	121
	Brast03G245500	85.054	368	39	11	10233	10589	6780	6418	3.13E-97	361
	Brast03G245500	92.913	127	8	1	9345	9470	5491	5365	7.26E-44	183

	Brast03G245500	91.15	113	10	0	7410	7522	10089	9977	5.69E-35	154
	Brast03G245500	87.069	116	11	4	7411	7524	5475	5362	3.45E-27	128
	Brast03G245500	83.2	125	21	0	7399	7523	6623	6499	2.69E-23	115
	Brast03G245500	84.874	119	13	5	1733	1849	10093	9978	2.69E-23	115
TE4.3_Brast06G087600	Brast06G087600	99.888	5361	6	0	1	5361	1	5361	0	9867
	Brast01G131300	93.204	103	6	1	4283	4385	4223	4324	2.28E-34	150
TE4.3_Brast06G098800	Brast06G098800	99.753	6080	15	0	1	6080	1	6080	0	11145
	Brast03G073900	94.637	317	16	1	4628	4943	2643	2327	1.34E-136	490
TE4.3_Brast06G105900	Brast06G105900	99.923	5227	4	0	1	5227	1	5227	0	9631
	Brast06G105700	81.923	520	53	20	4386	4883	1641	2141	5.55E-110	401
TE4.3_Brast06G108800	Brast06G108800	99.842	5688	9	0	1	5688	1	5688	0	10464
	Brast06G108800	100	34	0	0	1054	1087	988	1021	3.24E-08	63.9
	Brast06G108800	100	34	0	0	988	1021	1054	1087	3.24E-08	63.9
	Brast08G168700	89.313	131	7	7	4100	4223	5052	5182	1.44E-36	158
TE4.3_Brast06G112800	Brast06G112800	98.423	3552	56	0	1	3552	1	3552	0	6342
	Brast02G273400	90.11	91	8	1	778	868	1936	1847	1.18E-25	121
TE4.3_Brast06G119500	Brast06G119500	99.852	6062	9	0	1	6062	1	6062	0	11145
	Brast08G056000	96	125	5	0	2948	3072	5324	5448	1.95E-50	204
TE4.3_Brast06G128900	Brast06G128900	99.969	6367	2	0	1	6367	1	6367	0	11747
	Brast06G128800	82.971	875	108	21	1238	2103	1827	2669	0	752
TE4.3_Brast06G137000	Brast06G137000	99.977	12875	3	0	1	12875	1	12875	0	23760
	Brast09G069000	99.145	117	1	0	11896	12012	2461	2345	2.48E-52	211
	Brast09G069000	91.406	128	8	2	11895	12022	2934	2810	1.17E-40	172
TE4.3_Brast06G146400	Brast06G146400	99.757	6573	16	0	1	6573	1	6573	0	12050
	Brast06G146400	97.059	34	1	0	5918	5951	5854	5887	1.74E-06	58.4
	Brast06G146400	97.059	34	1	0	5854	5887	5918	5951	1.74E-06	58.4
	Brast07G065000	92.486	173	13	0	4658	4830	2471	2299	9.63E-64	248
TE4.3_Brast06G159100	Brast06G159100	99.895	9501	10	0	1	9501	1	9501	0	17490
	Brast06G159100	100	55	0	0	316	370	264	318	1.15E-19	102
	Brast06G159100	100	55	0	0	264	318	316	370	1.15E-19	102

	Brast02G265400	89.437	142	9	6	4861	4999	2542	2404	2.40E-41	174
TE4.3_Brast06G166300	Brast06G166300	99.776	5791	13	0	1	5791	1	5791	0	10623
	Brast02G335000	87.083	240	28	3	5553	5790	881	643	6.51E-70	268
TE4.3_Brast06G187300	Brast06G187300	99.929	1408	1	0	1	1408	1	1408	0	2595
	Brast07G094400	89.666	987	102	0	271	1257	259	1245	0	1258
	Brast06G193200	99.938	6452	4	0	1	6452	1	6452	0	11893
	Brast06G193200	88.372	129	6	1	1786	1914	1551	1670	3.55E-33	147
TE4.3_Brast06G193200	Brast06G193200	88.372	129	6	1	1551	1670	1786	1914	3.55E-33	147
	Brast04G201000	83.24	179	26	4	1475	1649	3852	4030	1.27E-37	161
	Brast04G201000	85.345	116	11	1	1784	1899	3927	4036	1.00E-23	115
TE4.3_Brast06G194800	Brast06G194800	99.788	1886	4	0	1	1886	1	1886	0	3461
	Brast06G199700	99.9	7002	7	0	1	7002	1	7002	0	12899
TE4.3_Brast06G199700	Brast05G048400	90.637	534	42	5	475	1005	4560	5088	0	710
	Brast05G048400	85.714	140	14	5	1522	1659	5332	5467	4.98E-32	143
	Brast06G200900	99.832	9552	16	0	1	9552	1	9552	0	17551
TE4.3_Brast06G200900	Brast06G200900	82.018	228	29	12	7426	7647	7647	7426	4.01E-44	183
	Brast10G171900	99.231	130	1	0	6361	6490	729	858	1.09E-59	235
	Brast06G206800	99.646	4797	17	0	1	4797	1	4797	0	8794
TE4.3_Brast06G206800	Brast02G335300	76.88	532	104	13	2904	3425	2720	3242	1.92E-74	283
	Brast06G228000	99.834	15042	25	0	1	15042	1	15042	0	27639
TE4.3_Brast06G228000	Brast06G228100	100	552	0	0	14491	15042	1	552	0	1020
TE4.3_Brast06G247000	Brast06G247000	99.556	4951	22	0	1	4951	1	4951	0	9022
	Brast07G011300	99.857	4192	6	0	1	4192	1	4192	0	7709
TE4.3_Brast07G011300	Brast05G095500	85.897	78	4	5	1053	1126	1752	1678	3.06E-12	76.8
TE4.3_Brast07G014100	Brast07G014100	99.694	1962	6	0	1	1962	1	1962	0	3591
TE4.3_Brast07G016900	Brast07G016900	96.95	918	28	0	1	918	1	918	0	1591
	Brast07G030200	99.942	1733	1	0	1	1733	1	1733	0	3195
TE4.3_Brast07G030200	Brast01G336800	86.463	229	19	4	50	278	125	341	4.20E-62	241
	Brast07G037900	99.827	4632	8	0	1	4632	1	4632	0	8510
TE4.3_Brast07G037900	Brast07G037900	100	30	0	0	2822	2851	2719	2748	4.41E-06	56.5

	Brast07G037900	100	30	0	0	2719	2748	2822	2851	4.41E-06	56.5
	Brast04G062300	95.082	122	6	0	1860	1981	4472	4351	3.22E-47	193
TE4.3_Brast07G074800	Brast07G074800	99.895	2856	3	0	1	2856	1	2856	0	5258
	Brast07G084200	99.976	12369	3	0	1	12369	1	12369	0	22825
TE4.3_Brast07G084200	Brast07G084200	87.129	101	13	0	1494	1594	1591	1491	1.92E-23	115
	Brast06G082600	99	100	1	0	1494	1593	3518	3419	6.71E-43	180
	Brast06G082600	88.889	99	11	0	1494	1592	3421	3519	1.15E-25	122
	Brast07G088100	99.936	4666	3	0	1	4666	1	4666	0	8600
TE4.3_Brast07G088100	Brast07G088100	100	65	0	0	2107	2171	2044	2108	1.55E-25	121
	Brast07G088100	100	65	0	0	2044	2108	2107	2171	1.55E-25	121
	Brast02G197100	96.154	104	4	0	1764	1867	2765	2868	1.52E-40	171
	Brast02G197100	92.233	103	7	1	1767	1868	9985	9883	9.21E-33	145
TE4.3_Brast07G093700	Brast07G093700	99.808	5733	11	0	1	5733	1	5733	0	10527
	Brast06G162800	93.846	65	3	1	3996	4060	6534	6597	3.22E-18	97.1
TE4.3_Brast07G096400	Brast07G096400	99.472	5871	31	0	1	5871	1	5871	0	10719
	Brast07G096600	100	759	0	0	5113	5871	3690	2932	0	1402
TE4.3_Brast07G104800	Brast07G104800	99.807	3109	6	0	1	3109	1	3109	0	5709
	Brast07G104800	86.316	95	13	0	1641	1735	1732	1638	1.04E-20	104
	Brast01G309300	91.166	283	15	5	39	315	40	318	1.99E-102	375
	Brast07G119600	99.444	21389	119	0	1	21389	1	21389	0	39039
	Brast07G119600	97.033	337	6	2	10486	10821	5226	5559	5.90E-160	569
	Brast07G119600	97.329	337	5	2	5226	5559	10486	10821	5.90E-160	569
	Brast07G119600	97	100	3	0	6792	6891	6754	6853	2.51E-39	169
	Brast07G119600	97	100	3	0	6754	6853	6792	6891	2.51E-39	169
TE4.3_Brast07G119600	Brast07G119600	96.774	62	2	0	6830	6891	6754	6815	7.19E-20	104
	Brast07G119600	96.774	62	2	0	6754	6815	6830	6891	7.19E-20	104
	Brast01G362300	94.064	2089	104	3	8458	10542	4890	2818	0	3193
	Brast01G362300	91.525	1593	101	3	6868	8435	6584	5001	0	2207
	Brast01G362300	90.84	1572	87	21	5226	6777	8095	6561	0	2065
	Brast01G362300	88.406	345	12	7	10486	10821	8095	7770	1.06E-107	396

	Brast01G362300	90.816	294	9	1	10525	10818	2759	2484	1.77E-105	388
	Brast01G362300	89.42	293	10	2	5265	5554	2759	2485	3.87E-97	361
TE4.3_Brast07G125000	Brast07G125000	99.973	7511	2	0	1	7511	1	7511	0	13860
	Brast07G117600	95.2	125	6	0	4197	4321	2886	3010	1.12E-48	198
TE4.3_Brast07G150700	Brast07G150700	99.603	5294	21	0	1	5294	1	5294	0	9673
	Brast07G150200	79.584	1778	265	65	3451	5170	2681	4418	0	1182
TE4.3_Brast07G171900	Brast07G171900	99.791	3834	8	0	1	3834	1	3834	0	7036
	Brast04G086200	84.375	160	23	2	425	583	282	440	3.49E-36	156
TE4.3_Brast07G181000	Brast07G181000	99.853	6810	10	0	1	6810	1	6810	0	12521
	Brast04G088100	100	28	0	0	4947	4974	4361	4334	8.39E-05	52.8
TE4.3_Brast07G194200	Brast07G194200	99.838	3087	5	0	1	3087	1	3087	0	5674
	Brast04G302700	75.162	2009	439	49	645	2617	188	2172	0	891
TE4.3_Brast07G195600	Brast07G195600	95.415	1963	90	0	1	1963	1	1963	0	3286
	Brast07G130800	80.303	132	26	0	523	654	364	495	6.53E-21	104
TE4.3_Brast07G211900	Brast07G211900	99.28	6668	48	0	1	6668	1	6668	0	12048
TE4.3_Brast07G212900	Brast07G212900	99.962	5324	2	0	1	5324	1	5324	0	9821
TE4.3_Brast07G213600	Brast07G213600	99.927	4123	3	0	1	4123	1	4123	0	7598
	Brast04G285900	78.14	645	126	12	3178	3810	2379	3020	2.03E-108	396
TE4.3_Brast07G239800	Brast07G239800	99.911	3362	3	0	1	3362	1	3362	0	6192
TE4.3_Brast08G012900	Brast08G012900	99.673	7957	26	0	1	7957	1	7957	0	14550
	Brast08G013100	99.63	541	2	0	1	541	541	1	0	989
TE4.3_Brast08G019600	Brast08G019600	99.908	3251	3	0	1	3251	1	3251	0	5987
TE4.3_Brast08G020300	Brast08G020300	99.633	14722	54	0	1	14722	1	14722	0	26899
	Brast08G020300	89.796	98	8	2	12235	12331	12331	12235	3.80E-26	124
	Brast08G020200	84.398	673	92	6	8071	8742	1510	850	0	649
	Brast08G020200	81.39	403	54	13	11128	11525	859	1245	9.77E-82	309
TE4.3_Brast08G036300	Brast08G036300	99.85	3330	5	0	1	3330	1	3330	0	6122
	Brast06G153700	90.237	717	43	6	476	1192	1428	2117	0	911
	Brast06G153700	93.37	362	22	2	1357	1717	2118	2478	3.33E-150	534
TE4.3_Brast08G047200	Brast08G047200	99.868	5299	7	0	1	5299	1	5299	0	9747

	Brast08G047200	86.179	123	11	6	4009	4127	2865	2745	1.05E-27	128
	Brast08G047200	86.179	123	11	6	2745	2865	4127	4009	1.05E-27	128
	Brast10G178100	95.276	127	3	3	4003	4127	661	786	7.92E-49	198
	Brast10G178100	86.806	144	11	8	2738	2877	792	653	1.74E-35	154
TE4.3_Brast08G068300	Brast08G068300	99.572	12161	52	0	1	12161	1	12161	0	22173
	Brast09G180800	96	125	4	1	7095	7219	5031	4908	3.92E-50	204
TE4.3_Brast08G070500	Brast08G070500	99.805	6653	13	0	1	6653	1	6653	0	12214
	Brast01G122700	77.813	951	173	26	572	1494	680	1620	1.84E-155	553
	Brast01G122700	77.583	571	112	11	5267	5822	3720	4289	9.41E-89	331
TE4.3_Brast08G091700	Brast08G091700	99.815	8112	15	0	1	8112	1	8112	0	14898
	Brast08G091700	98.182	55	1	0	7278	7332	7224	7278	4.56E-18	97.1
	Brast08G091700	98.182	55	1	0	7224	7278	7278	7332	4.56E-18	97.1
	Brast08G112100	79.775	178	29	5	7335	7510	4652	4480	7.52E-26	122
TE4.3_Brast08G119000	Brast08G119000	99.786	2341	5	0	1	2341	1	2341	0	4296
TE4.3_Brast08G119400	Brast08G119400	99.863	2928	4	0	1	2928	1	2928	0	5385
	Brast06G059200	91.667	60	5	0	1603	1662	607	666	1.27E-14	84.2
TE4.3_Brast08G129600	Brast08G129600	100	2191	0	0	1	2191	1	2191	0	4047
TE4.3_Brast08G132400	Brast08G132400	99.745	9405	24	0	1	9405	1	9405	0	17250
	Brast08G132400	82	100	12	6	3545	3641	3641	3545	5.32E-13	80.5
	Brast01G269900	96.117	103	4	0	3545	3647	8936	9038	1.10E-39	169
	Brast01G269900	83.168	101	11	6	3545	3642	9032	8935	3.18E-15	87.9
TE4.3_Brast08G134200	Brast08G134200	99.844	8328	13	0	1	8328	1	8328	0	15307
	Brast09G151200	96.875	32	1	0	6880	6911	1646	1677	2.86E-05	54.7
TE4.3_Brast08G134300	Brast08G134300	99.808	3648	7	0	1	3648	1	3648	0	6698
	Brast01G198400	79.048	105	18	4	391	493	196	298	4.45E-10	69.4
TE4.3_Brast08G137200	Brast08G137200	99.8	3997	8	0	1	3997	1	3997	0	7337
	Brast10G058100	97.541	122	3	0	1094	1215	1007	886	2.75E-52	209
TE4.3_Brast08G141800	Brast08G141800	99.955	11069	5	0	1	11069	1	11069	0	20413
	Brast02G316500	96.212	132	3	2	9690	9820	3013	3143	1.65E-53	215
TE4.3_Brast08G165900	Brast08G165900	99.919	6153	5	0	1	6153	1	6153	0	11335

	Brast02G091500	93.478	92	3	2	5154	5244	7202	7113	2.63E-29	134
TE4.3_Brast08G169600	Brast08G169600	99.949	5868	3	0	1	5868	1	5868	0	10820
	Brast05G282800	93.471	291	18	1	3712	4001	2419	2709	7.95E-119	431
	Brast08G173900	99.633	6273	23	0	1	6273	1	6273	0	11490
TE4.3_Brast08G173900	Brast08G173900	94.382	89	3	2	4614	4701	4701	4614	7.46E-30	135
	Brast03G082500	93.269	104	3	4	4615	4714	415	518	2.66E-34	150
	Brast08G188700	99.939	3301	2	0	1	3301	1	3301	0	6085
TE4.3_Brast08G188700	Brast10G118800	93.976	83	4	1	666	748	1203	1284	8.47E-27	124
	Brast08G204500	99.79	9511	20	0	1	9511	1	9511	0	17453
TE4.3_Brast08G204500	Brast08G204500	98.485	66	1	0	3909	3974	4009	4074	4.10E-24	117
	Brast07G017500	96.491	57	1	1	3978	4034	1080	1025	6.91E-17	93.5
TE4.3_Brast08G226300	Brast08G226300	99.602	5533	22	0	1	5533	1	5533	0	10096
TE4.3_Brast08G232200	Brast08G232200	99.614	3110	12	0	1	3110	1	3110	0	5698
TE4.3_Brast08G232800	Brast08G232800	99.213	6230	49	0	1	6230	1	6230	0	11234
TE4.3_Brast08G240700	Brast08G240700	99.922	3843	3	0	1	3843	1	3843	0	7081
	Brast08G241300	99.586	7721	32	0	1	7721	1	7721	0	14122
TE4.3_Brast08G241300	Brast10G049400	91.026	624	42	9	1711	2333	1	611	0	830
	Brast08G249700	99.918	9759	8	0	1	9759	1	9759	0	17978
TE4.3_Brast08G249700	Brast03G102000	79.441	715	111	22	4792	5501	4920	5603	2.17E-131	473
TE4.3_Brast09G003400	Brast09G003400	99.558	3848	17	0	1	3848	1	3848	0	7012
	Brast09G037900	99.065	5349	50	0	1	5349	1	5349	0	9601
TE4.3_Brast09G037900	Brast09G037900	100	30	0	0	1331	1360	1275	1304	5.09E-06	56.5
TE4.3_Brast09G066800	Brast09G066800	99.944	3540	2	0	1	3540	1	3540	0	6527
	Brast09G067600	99.894	7575	8	0	1	7575	1	7575	0	13945
TE4.3_Brast09G067600	Brast09G067700	100	1302	0	0	3024	4325	1	1302	0	2405
	Brast09G072000	99.811	5291	10	0	1	5291	1	5291	0	9716
TE4.3_Brast09G072000	Brast05G061500	98.312	237	4	0	3099	3335	920	1156	2.01E-114	416
TE4.3_Brast09G076500	Brast09G076500	99.887	5308	6	0	1	5308	1	5308	0	9769
TE4.3_Brast09G084700	Brast09G084700	99.804	8653	17	0	1	8653	1	8653	0	15886

	Brast01G276100	86.649	367	17	19	208	544	95	459	1.55E-102	377
	Brast09G101500	99.928	8356	6	0	1	8356	1	8356	0	15398
	Brast09G101500	94.175	103	6	0	1444	1546	1342	1444	2.12E-36	158
TE4.3_Brast09G101500	Brast09G101500	94.175	103	6	0	1342	1444	1444	1546	2.12E-36	158
	Brast02G196600	90.688	247	16	2	57	302	55	295	7.11E-86	322
	Brast02G196600	97.222	36	1	0	125	160	82	117	1.71E-07	62.1
	Brast09G111700	99.958	9591	4	0	1	9591	1	9591	0	17690
TE4.3_Brast09G111700	Brast02G126300	93.6	125	8	0	4593	4717	2147	2271	3.11E-45	187
	Brast09G122000	99.959	4881	2	0	1	4881	1	4881	0	9003
	Brast09G122000	80.828	652	101	16	944	1583	838	1477	1.07E-136	490
	Brast09G122000	80.828	652	101	16	838	1477	944	1583	1.07E-136	490
	Brast09G122000	83.925	479	62	11	1156	1627	838	1308	8.48E-123	444
TE4.3_Brast09G122000	Brast09G122000	83.925	479	62	11	838	1308	1156	1627	8.48E-123	444
	Brast09G122000	83.144	439	53	14	1048	1477	838	1264	6.75E-104	381
	Brast09G122000	83.028	436	59	9	838	1264	1048	1477	6.75E-104	381
	Brast09G122000	84.532	278	30	8	1310	1583	890	1158	2.55E-68	263
	Brast09G122000	84.532	278	30	8	890	1158	1310	1583	2.55E-68	263
	Brast09G133400	99.877	4073	5	0	1	4073	1	4073	0	7494
TE4.3_Brast09G133400	Brast04G259500	94.828	116	4	1	2736	2849	19154	19269	2.20E-43	180
	Brast09G138700	99.867	6778	9	0	1	6778	1	6778	0	12467
TE4.3_Brast09G138700	Brast10G140200	92.969	128	7	2	1244	1369	2275	2148	7.90E-45	185
	Brast09G139600	99.828	9888	17	0	1	9888	1	9888	0	18166
	Brast09G139600	91.579	95	8	0	9635	9729	3465	3371	1.52E-28	132
	Brast09G139600	91.579	95	8	0	3371	3465	9729	9635	1.52E-28	132
	Brast09G139600	90.476	84	8	0	4360	4443	4116	4199	1.98E-22	111
TE4.3_Brast09G139600	Brast09G139600	90.476	84	8	0	4116	4199	4360	4443	1.98E-22	111
	Brast09G139600	100	28	0	0	9634	9661	7819	7846	1.22E-04	52.8
	Brast09G139600	100	28	0	0	7819	7846	9634	9661	1.22E-04	52.8
	Brast09G125600	86.257	342	35	6	4106	4443	4847	4514	1.78E-97	361
	Brast09G125600	93.333	120	7	1	3346	3465	2516	2634	6.94E-42	176

	Brast09G125600	93.22	118	7	1	9635	9752	2131	2247	8.98E-41	172
	Brast09G125600	95.402	87	4	0	4116	4202	4597	4511	9.10E-31	139
	Brast09G125600	84.615	130	15	5	3342	3468	2255	2128	2.55E-26	124
TE4.3_Brast09G145600	Brast09G145600	99.673	11310	37	0	1	11310	1	11310	0	20709
	Brast02G168500	97.541	244	6	0	180	423	47	290	1.19E-114	418
TE4.3_Brast09G147200	Brast09G147200	99.774	1767	4	0	1	1767	1	1767	0	3241
	Brast09G147500	77.16	1458	269	46	119	1541	17	1445	0	789
TE4.3_Brast09G148500	Brast09G148500	99.922	1288	1	0	1	1288	1	1288	0	2374
	Brast04G128400	86.102	590	78	4	318	905	619	1206	4.38E-180	632
	Brast09G151100	98.88	15262	171	0	1	15262	1	15262	0	27470
	Brast09G151100	81.977	688	104	15	4203	4880	4880	4203	8.98E-167	592
TE4.3_Brast09G151100	Brast09G151100	87.755	49	6	0	15091	15139	6728	6680	4.05E-06	58.4
	Brast08G160800	90.379	686	58	7	4202	4883	4428	3747	0	924
	Brast08G160800	84.448	688	91	13	4201	4880	3748	4427	0	689
TE4.3_Brast09G151900	Brast09G151900	99.74	2689	7	0	1	2689	1	2689	0	4927
	Brast09G156200	99.871	4654	6	0	1	4654	1	4654	0	8562
TE4.3_Brast09G156200	Brast04G181000	77.729	229	45	5	1197	1422	1429	1654	5.53E-30	135
	Brast09G166200	99.767	10723	25	0	1	10723	1	10723	0	19697
	Brast09G166200	88.462	52	3	1	3994	4042	3909	3960	7.91E-07	60.2
TE4.3_Brast09G166200	Brast09G166200	88.462	52	3	1	3909	3960	3994	4042	7.91E-07	60.2
	Brast09G166400	100	3657	0	0	4340	7996	3657	1	0	6754
TE4.3_Brast09G182700	Brast09G182700	99.891	1842	2	0	1	1842	1	1842	0	3391
	Brast09G189000	99.914	1164	1	0	1	1164	1	1164	0	2145
TE4.3_Brast09G189000	Brast04G098600	81.26	603	78	20	32	624	412	989	9.19E-127	455
	Brast04G098600	85.897	78	11	0	1058	1135	1411	1488	5.00E-15	84.2
	Brast09G198900	99.837	7969	13	0	1	7969	1	7969	0	14645
TE4.3_Brast09G198900	Brast01G369800	90.61	213	12	6	6534	6744	4282	4076	5.36E-72	276
TE4.3_Brast09G211100	Brast09G211100	99.907	3236	3	0	1	3236	1	3236	0	5962
TE4.3_Brast09G211200	Brast09G211200	99.726	2924	8	0	1	2924	1	2924	0	5356
TE4.3_Brast09G220600	Brast09G220600	99.871	6197	8	0	1	6197	1	6197	0	11400

	Brast09G220600	100	47	0	0	2535	2581	2489	2535	2.09E-15	87.9
	Brast09G220600	97.872	47	1	0	2489	2535	2535	2581	9.74E-14	82.4
TE4.3_Brast09G239000	Brast09G239000	98.986	3058	31	0	1	3058	1	3058	0	5478
	Brast09G255900	99.775	2223	5	0	1	2223	1	2223	0	4078
TE4.3_Brast09G255900	Brast05G210200	73.321	1117	226	49	901	1990	885	1956	1.11E-93	346
TE4.3_Brast09G256500	Brast09G256500	99.9	4984	5	0	1	4984	1	4984	0	9177
	Brast09G260300	99.856	4864	7	0	1	4864	1	4864	0	8944
TE4.3_Brast09G260300	Brast02G060800	98.039	102	1	1	3850	3951	3653	3553	3.40E-42	176
	Brast10G003400	99.748	1587	4	0	1	1587	1	1587	0	2909
TE4.3_Brast10G003400	Brast10G003100	86.404	1471	182	14	47	1514	32	1487	0	1592
	Brast10G004000	99.511	5731	28	0	1	5731	1	5731	0	10429
TE4.3_Brast10G004000	Brast05G148000	94.928	138	3	3	2646	2780	11069	10933	3.06E-53	213
TE4.3_Brast10G005800	Brast10G005800	99.896	5768	6	0	1	5768	1	5768	0	10619
	Brast10G009600	99.27	7125	52	0	1	7125	1	7125	0	12870
TE4.3_Brast10G009600	Brast02G116800	88.971	136	6	3	5546	5676	4174	4305	5.03E-37	159
	Brast10G016100	99.53	6597	31	0	1	6597	1	6597	0	12011
TE4.3_Brast10G016100	Brast07G132100	97.479	119	2	1	5378	5495	4401	4519	7.63E-50	202
	Brast10G018900	99.966	2955	1	0	1	2955	1	2955	0	5452
TE4.3_Brast10G018900	Brast01G291400	91.753	97	2	1	3393	3483	2799	2703	3.99E-28	130
TE4.3_Brast10G019800	Brast10G019800	99.806	7203	14	0	1	7203	1	7203	0	13224
TE4.3_Brast10G023000	Brast10G023000	99.794	8256	17	0	1	8256	1	8256	0	15152
TE4.3_Brast10G064900	Brast10G064900	100	2525	0	0	1	2525	1	2525	0	4663
TE4.3_Brast10G067900	Brast10G067900	99.741	1928	5	0	1	1928	1	1928	0	3533
	Brast10G080000	99.731	7069	19	0	1	7069	1	7069	0	12957
TE4.3_Brast10G080000	Brast04G195300	89.011	546	58	2	5057	5600	4597	4052	0	682
	Brast04G195300	89.888	89	7	2	5594	5680	4025	3937	3.94E-23	113
	Brast10G083200	98.206	4962	89	0	1	4962	1	4962	0	8671
TE4.3_Brast10G083200	Brast10G083200	89.796	98	10	0	3669	3766	3766	3669	3.55E-27	126
	Brast01G178100	91.228	171	14	1	1849	2018	6406	6236	7.31E-59	231

	Brast10G107400	99.903	4104	4	0	1	4104	1	4104	0	7557
TE4.3_Brast10G107400	Brast04G080300	96.774	124	2	1	1275	1396	3375	3498	3.66E-51	206
	Brast04G080300	90.598	117	9	2	1280	1394	3828	3944	1.34E-35	154
TE4.3_Brast10G164100	Brast10G164100	99.975	4065	1	0	1	4065	1	4065	0	7502

(b) *B. hybridum*

Query (222 assembled genes of <i>B. hybridum</i> BdTR6g)	Database (<i>B. hybridum</i> ABR113 genes)	percentage of identical matches	alignment length (sequence overlap)	number of mismatches	number of gap openings	start of alignment in query	end of alignment in query	start of alignment in subject	end of alignment in subject	expect value	bit score
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0007700	Brahy.S01G0007700	99.887	3552	4	0	1	3552	1	3552	0	6545
	Brahy.D01G0811700	93.919	2845	146	16	723	3551	331	3164	0	4277
	Brahy.D01G0811700	97.872	47	1	0	645	691	283	329	1.16E-13	82.4
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0038900	Brahy.S01G0038900	100	3193	0	0	1	3193	1	3193	0	5897
	Brahy.D01G0318000	84.516	3242	252	109	23	3138	37	3154	0	2976
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0054800	Brahy.S01G0054800	99.599	4238	17	0	1	4238	1	4238	0	7757
	Brahy.D02G0779000	92.502	2894	144	35	15	2877	65	2916	0	4074
	Brahy.D02G0779000	91.873	1292	86	15	2917	4203	2918	4195	0	1810
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0056900	Brahy.S01G0056900	99.657	5241	18	0	1	5241	1	5241	0	9603
	Brahy.D02G0776300	94.712	1456	60	7	3526	4976	3106	4549	0	2248
	Brahy.D02G0776300	95.428	1028	38	5	1269	2292	1126	2148	0	1629
	Brahy.D02G0776300	94.632	1006	53	1	74	1078	1	1006	0	1557
	Brahy.D02G0776300	95.203	813	31	5	2628	3433	2298	3109	0	1279
	Brahy.D02G0776300	98.413	63	1	0	1120	1182	1003	1065	2.19E-22	111
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0075600	Brahy.S01G0075600	99.824	2833	5	0	1	2833	1	2833	0	5204
	Brahy.D02G0755000	94.952	2833	125	14	7	2833	6	2826	0	4423
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0098300	Brahy.S01G0098300	99.027	4728	46	0	1	4728	1	4728	0	8556
	Brahy.D02G0729900	94.123	3131	120	23	22	3104	1	3115	0	4704
	Brahy.D02G0729900	88.235	442	24	17	3100	3515	3139	3578	2.79E-140	503
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0101700	Brahy.S01G0101700	99.886	4397	5	0	1	4397	1	4397	0	8093
	Brahy.D02G0726300	94.123	3233	106	31	1220	4397	1619	4822	0	4841
	Brahy.D02G0726300	88.324	865	57	14	211	1033	109	971	0	998
	Brahy.D02G0726300	98.83	171	2	0	1028	1198	1319	1489	7.86E-81	305
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0142800	Brahy.S01G0142800	99.895	9519	10	0	1	9519	1	9519	0	17523

	Brahy.D02G0681500	92.537	4221	160	65	3241	7356	3709	7879	0	5906
	Brahy.D02G0681500	91.469	2696	160	37	587	3241	959	3625	0	3640
	Brahy.D02G0681500	93.201	1912	80	23	7359	9256	8052	9927	0	2765
	Brahy.D02G0681500	95.442	373	17	0	1	373	45	417	9.04E-168	595
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0164700	Brahy.S01G0164700	100	1455	0	0	1	1455	1	1455	0	2687
	Brahy.D02G0656500	96.632	1455	49	0	1	1455	763	2217	0	2416
	Brahy.S01G0165500	99.742	2325	6	0	1	2325	1	2325	0	4261
	Brahy.S01G0165500	87.156	109	14	0	924	1032	1212	1320	1.24E-26	124
	Brahy.S01G0165500	86.239	109	15	0	1212	1320	924	1032	5.78E-25	119
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0165500	Brahy.D02G0655700	92.982	1482	85	6	860	2323	1333	2813	0	2143
	Brahy.D02G0655700	87.696	829	79	9	505	1333	872	1677	0	944
	Brahy.D02G0655700	87.81	525	21	17	1	498	190	698	2.85E-162	575
	Brahy.D02G0655700	88.525	122	13	1	1212	1333	1274	1394	2.65E-33	147
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0177800	Brahy.S01G0177800	98.722	1722	22	0	1	1722	1	1722	0	3099
	Brahy.D02G0643100	95.94	936	35	2	171	1103	1	936	0	1519
	Brahy.S01G0191200	99.867	3764	5	0	1	3764	1	3764	0	6931
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0191200	Brahy.D02G0629200	93.264	2509	130	15	146	2635	1	2489	0	3661
	Brahy.D02G0629200	91.829	820	39	10	2973	3764	2506	3325	0	1118
	Brahy.S01G0219700	99.778	9892	22	0	1	9892	1	9892	0	18146
	Brahy.S01G0219700	79.412	136	22	5	8603	8736	8250	8119	5.40E-16	91.6
	Brahy.S01G0219700	79.699	133	21	5	8122	8250	8733	8603	5.40E-16	91.6
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0219700	Brahy.D02G0595800	90.679	4656	322	42	2858	7482	2654	7228	0	6091
	Brahy.D02G0595800	90.009	1071	53	17	745	1780	772	1823	0	1336
	Brahy.D02G0595800	84.277	1272	114	48	7533	8782	7237	8444	0	1162
	Brahy.D02G0595800	88.81	840	52	17	1892	2694	1822	2656	0	992
	Brahy.D02G0595800	91.017	757	31	20	7	743	1	740	0	987
	Brahy.D02G0595800	85.523	898	72	26	8933	9808	8445	9306	0	885
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0241600	Brahy.S01G0241600	99.939	4944	3	0	1	4944	1	4944	0	9114
	Brahy.D02G0571800	94.635	4977	175	34	30	4944	1	4947	0	7627
	Brahy.D02G0571800	100	30	0	0	2283	2312	2213	2242	9.83E-06	56.5

BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0266700	Brahy.S01G0266700	100	5332	0	0	1	5332	1	5332	0	9847
	Brahy.D02G0192800	94.783	1495	53	8	656	2128	1327	2818	0	2305
	Brahy.D02G0192800	96.306	785	28	1	4523	5306	5501	6285	0	1288
	Brahy.D02G0192800	95.126	677	19	7	1	664	122	797	0	1055
	Brahy.D02G0192800	91.382	731	30	11	3799	4525	4710	5411	0	970
	Brahy.D02G0192800	92.035	452	22	4	2647	3088	3801	4248	2.32E-176	623
	Brahy.D02G0192800	92.048	415	15	10	2138	2535	3391	3804	1.10E-159	568
	Brahy.D02G0192800	92.327	404	20	6	3172	3570	4334	4731	1.43E-158	564
	Brahy.D02G0192800	93.182	88	5	1	3046	3133	4248	4334	2.22E-27	128
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0315700	Brahy.S01G0315700	99.377	2247	14	0	1	2247	1	2247	0	4072
	Brahy.D02G0137800	90.946	1226	46	30	1073	2247	1683	2894	0	1589
	Brahy.D02G0137800	91.667	756	46	8	1	748	494	1240	0	1031
	Brahy.D02G0137800	96.552	87	3	0	837	923	1478	1564	9.21E-33	145
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0326700	Brahy.S01G0326700	99.209	10997	87	0	1	10997	1	10997	0	19856
	Brahy.S01G0326700	88.506	87	10	0	1856	1942	1942	1856	2.15E-20	106
	Brahy.D02G0126100	91.604	2132	83	38	6092	8164	5117	7211	0	2857
	Brahy.D02G0126100	92.739	1639	82	22	9306	10930	8409	10024	0	2333
	Brahy.D02G0126100	90.601	1681	97	25	4002	5670	3484	5115	0	2172
	Brahy.D02G0126100	94.714	1135	53	7	8161	9294	7303	8431	0	1757
	Brahy.D02G0126100	90.363	1349	56	20	1	1317	12	1318	0	1703
	Brahy.D02G0126100	90.947	1204	65	23	1943	3137	1611	2779	0	1580
	Brahy.D02G0126100	94.568	718	34	4	3166	3880	2774	3489	0	1105
	Brahy.D02G0126100	93.893	262	13	2	1598	1856	1348	1609	1.47E-106	392
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0422300	Brahy.S01G0422300	99.433	3173	18	0	1	3173	1	3173	0	5760
	Brahy.D02G0017500	90.392	3216	192	68	1	3173	1	3142	0	4119
BdTR6g_Brahy.S01G0446600	Brahy.S01G0446600	99.733	1125	3	0	1	1125	1	1125	0	2067
	Brahy.D02G0554800	96.005	876	23	4	97	963	1	873	0	1413
BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0027600	Brahy.S02G0027600	99.802	5041	10	0	1	5041	1	5041	0	9254
	Brahy.S02G0027600	87.755	98	12	0	3879	3976	3976	3879	1.63E-23	115
	Brahy.D01G1042800	93.042	2817	158	19	4	2805	1	2794	0	4082

	Brahy.D01G1042800	93.739	1102	57	7	2785	3880	2809	3904	0	1642
	Brahy.D01G1042800	87.978	915	45	29	4147	5041	4122	4991	0	1020
BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0040700	Brahy.S02G0040700	99.884	4295	5	0	1	4295	1	4295	0	7904
	Brahy.D01G1029400	93.766	4299	189	37	43	4295	1	4266	0	6381
BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0047100	Brahy.S02G0047100	99.748	5961	15	0	1	5961	1	5961	0	10925
	Brahy.D01G1021500	93.166	5853	266	63	21	5804	84	5871	0	8469
	Brahy.S02G0075400	99.009	5249	52	0	1	5249	1	5249	0	9406
	Brahy.D01G0989300	89.595	1999	137	43	662	2619	689	2657	0	2473
	Brahy.D01G0989300	89.947	756	39	11	4012	4764	3677	4398	0	941
	Brahy.D01G0989300	89.911	674	36	8	3352	4003	3050	3713	0	839
BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0075400	Brahy.D01G0989300	93.213	442	25	3	4808	5245	4408	4848	0	645
	Brahy.D01G0989300	88.785	321	23	7	2654	2973	2655	2963	1.52E-103	381
	Brahy.D01G0989300	90.659	182	16	1	668	849	477	297	2.69E-61	241
	Brahy.D01G0989300	100	30	0	0	619	648	617	646	1.04E-05	56.5
	Brahy.S02G0111200	99.11	5506	49	0	1	5506	1	5506	0	9961
	Brahy.D01G0947800	92.147	1770	66	29	1697	3448	1308	3022	0	2436
	Brahy.D01G0947800	93.838	714	29	7	67	778	1	701	0	1061
	Brahy.D01G0947800	92.25	671	31	6	4834	5489	3911	4575	0	931
BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0111200	Brahy.D01G0947800	88.906	640	47	8	851	1488	703	1320	0	798
	Brahy.D01G0947800	94.19	327	17	2	4483	4807	3591	3917	1.51E-138	497
	Brahy.D01G0947800	96.825	189	5	1	3552	3739	3321	3509	1.64E-83	315
	Brahy.D01G0947800	91.667	132	10	1	3436	3567	3126	3256	1.73E-43	182
	Brahy.D01G0947800	94.444	54	3	0	3848	3901	3507	3560	5.02E-14	84.2
	Brahy.S02G0136400	99.785	3263	7	0	1	3263	1	3263	0	5987
	Brahy.D01G0917200	93.152	1358	62	17	497	1833	391	1738	0	1964
BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0136400	Brahy.D01G0917200	92.453	477	33	3	2786	3262	2469	2942	0	678
	Brahy.D01G0917200	86.278	583	48	22	1924	2489	1932	2499	5.12E-171	604
	Brahy.D01G0917200	93.684	380	20	4	71	447	2	380	2.42E-159	566
BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0138100	Brahy.S02G0138100	99.942	5217	3	0	1	5217	1	5217	0	9618
	Brahy.D01G0915600	96.073	5246	148	22	1	5217	3	5219	0	8493

BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0141500	Brahy.S02G0141500	99.868	4532	6	0	1	4532	1	4532	0	8336
	Brahy.D01G0910600	94.616	1393	64	4	1704	3094	1551	2934	0	2146
	Brahy.D01G0910600	91.235	1312	67	16	3175	4476	2930	4203	0	1742
	Brahy.D01G0910600	92.741	675	40	4	863	1536	864	1530	0	966
	Brahy.D01G0910600	91.896	617	34	7	66	674	64	672	0	848
	Brahy.D01G0910600	92	75	6	0	710	784	765	839	8.82E-21	106
BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0142500	Brahy.S02G0142500	99.808	8874	17	0	1	8874	1	8874	0	16294
	Brahy.D01G0909500	91.516	2593	151	42	2140	4704	2466	5017	0	3506
	Brahy.D01G0909500	95.425	1683	54	6	7189	8871	6970	8629	0	2660
	Brahy.D01G0909500	94.778	1551	67	8	5375	6925	5267	6803	0	2403
	Brahy.D01G0909500	89.953	1055	55	25	1	1031	16	1043	0	1314
	Brahy.D01G0909500	87.208	813	76	11	1084	1882	1057	1855	0	900
Brahy.D01G0909500	90.206	194	13	2	1956	2148	1968	2156	2.72E-63	248	
BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0163600	Brahy.S02G0163600	99.962	7923	3	0	1	7923	1	7923	0	14615
	Brahy.D01G0886600	94.323	3206	119	27	3842	7034	2571	5726	0	4854
	Brahy.D01G0886600	91.436	1915	93	32	1936	3843	595	2445	0	2562
	Brahy.D01G0886600	92.308	728	40	14	7095	7816	5752	6469	0	1020
	Brahy.D01G0886600	91.79	609	28	9	1	604	4	595	0	828
BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0189100	Brahy.S02G0189100	99.812	13836	26	0	1	13836	1	13836	0	25407
	Brahy.S02G0189100	96.078	51	2	0	10162	10212	10116	10166	1.27E-13	84.2
	Brahy.S02G0189100	96.078	51	2	0	10116	10166	10162	10212	1.27E-13	84.2
	Brahy.S02G0189100	76.471	102	21	3	3029	3129	3450	3351	3.57E-04	52.8
	Brahy.D01G0861000	90.467	2161	116	41	915	3030	1022	3137	0	2767
	Brahy.D01G0861000	92.503	1814	89	18	4800	6606	4820	6593	0	2553
	Brahy.D01G0861000	93.885	1439	68	14	11781	13205	11562	12994	0	2152
	Brahy.D01G0861000	92.288	1154	36	23	10548	11667	10428	11562	0	1589
	Brahy.D01G0861000	93.488	906	43	7	11	914	1	892	0	1332
	Brahy.D01G0861000	92.705	891	53	7	7325	8213	7292	8172	0	1275
	Brahy.D01G0861000	91.648	886	35	16	4056	4910	3938	4815	0	1190
Brahy.D01G0861000	93.134	670	36	6	8908	9575	8994	9655	0	974	

	Brahy.D01G0861000	91.433	607	29	7	13236	13836	13100	13689	0	811
	Brahy.D01G0861000	88.379	697	43	22	9747	10434	9734	10401	0	804
	Brahy.D01G0861000	91.438	584	34	10	3449	4030	3372	3941	0	787
	Brahy.D01G0861000	91.667	504	28	8	6779	7271	6792	7292	0	686
	Brahy.D01G0861000	86.685	368	19	11	8210	8550	8369	8733	4.01E-103	381
	Brahy.D01G0861000	93.724	239	8	1	3124	3355	3135	3373	3.14E-94	351
	Brahy.D01G0861000	90.256	195	8	8	8672	8859	8729	8919	5.49E-62	244
	Brahy.D01G0861000	88.66	97	1	3	6608	6704	6678	6764	2.09E-21	110
	Brahy.S02G0217300	99.653	13562	47	0	1	13562	1	13562	0	24821
	Brahy.D01G0830100	94.412	4671	164	47	5970	10595	5348	9966	0	7090
	Brahy.D01G0830100	96.893	2414	66	6	3561	5968	2858	5268	0	4034
	Brahy.D01G0830100	94.713	1551	70	5	2020	3562	1210	2756	0	2399
	Brahy.D01G0830100	89.39	1131	68	23	332	1432	118	1226	0	1376
BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0217300	Brahy.D01G0830100	95.569	835	35	2	11274	12107	10616	11449	0	1336
	Brahy.D01G0830100	95.597	795	28	3	12771	13562	12128	12918	0	1267
	Brahy.D01G0830100	91.469	633	30	5	10598	11228	10009	10619	0	848
	Brahy.D01G0830100	84.906	371	16	10	12134	12502	11804	12136	2.40E-90	339
	Brahy.D01G0830100	88.732	71	3	3	144	209	1	71	4.46E-13	82.4
	Brahy.D01G0830100	100	36	0	0	12033	12068	11765	11800	1.25E-08	67.6
	Brahy.S02G0229400	99.551	1560	7	0	1	1560	1	1560	0	2852
BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0229400	Brahy.D01G0210800	96.558	1191	41	0	110	1300	1	1191	0	1975
	Brahy.S02G0232900	99.955	2216	1	0	1	2216	1	2216	0	4087
BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0232900	Brahy.D01G0207100	96.641	2084	68	2	29	2111	149	2231	0	3459
	Brahy.D01G0207100	95.146	103	5	0	2114	2216	2286	2388	2.51E-38	163
	Brahy.S02G0268300	99.911	6707	6	0	1	6707	1	6707	0	12353
	Brahy.D01G0171800	95.177	3794	149	12	74	3861	1	3766	0	5962
BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0268300	Brahy.D01G0171800	95.289	1486	60	6	5227	6705	5902	7384	0	2348
	Brahy.D01G0171800	92.336	1083	49	13	4166	5229	4772	5839	0	1509
	Brahy.D01G0171800	88.955	335	13	4	3858	4169	4077	4410	8.96E-107	392
BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0290100	Brahy.S02G0290100	99.901	9137	9	0	1	9137	1	9137	0	16824

	Brahy.D01G0151500	94.393	2693	101	16	6478	9137	6161	8836	0	4091
	Brahy.D01G0151500	93.32	2051	75	19	1317	3339	615	2631	0	2972
	Brahy.D01G0151500	91.535	1583	85	25	3871	5442	3139	4683	0	2135
	Brahy.D01G0151500	93.625	1004	47	6	5477	6464	4681	5683	0	1483
	Brahy.D01G0151500	94.805	616	22	4	70	685	9	614	0	952
	Brahy.D01G0151500	95.143	453	17	3	3341	3789	2667	3118	0	710
BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0300700	Brahy.S02G0300700	96.504	18106	633	0	1	18106	1	18106	0	31071
	Brahy.D01G0145300	96.517	804	18	2	1	800	798	1	0	1323
BdTR6g_Brahy.S02G0321700	Brahy.S02G0321700	99.933	4473	3	0	1	4473	1	4473	0	8244
	Brahy.D01G0118400	92.791	4536	201	55	4	4459	2	4491	0	6449
	Brahy.S03G0015000	99.475	9527	50	0	1	9527	1	9527	0	17385
	Brahy.D03G0236800	90.184	2883	169	58	6677	9478	6008	8857	0	3651
	Brahy.D03G0236800	93.821	1408	70	8	733	2138	973	2365	0	2102
	Brahy.D03G0236800	90.136	1247	62	24	2963	4181	2357	3570	0	1565
BdTR6g_Brahy.S03G0015000	Brahy.D03G0236800	93.019	1017	41	5	4213	5224	3570	4561	0	1458
	Brahy.D03G0236800	93.777	707	31	6	5944	6649	5329	6023	0	1050
	Brahy.D03G0236800	94.251	661	28	3	5229	5886	4679	5332	0	1002
	Brahy.D03G0236800	91.071	728	46	9	1	718	1	719	0	966
	Brahy.S03G0031000	99.409	8287	49	0	1	8287	1	8287	0	15047
	Brahy.S03G0031000	97.143	70	2	0	3812	3881	3597	3666	2.08E-24	119
	Brahy.S03G0031000	97.143	70	2	0	3597	3666	3812	3881	2.08E-24	119
	Brahy.D03G0216100	92.817	3536	130	45	3813	7290	2576	6045	0	5009
BdTR6g_Brahy.S03G0031000	Brahy.D03G0216100	88.895	1783	98	36	702	2426	199	1939	0	2104
	Brahy.D03G0216100	96.301	784	22	5	7503	8284	6431	7209	0	1280
	Brahy.D03G0216100	92.029	552	23	7	3120	3666	2109	2644	0	756
	Brahy.D03G0216100	85.167	209	10	7	7288	7491	6260	6452	3.35E-47	195
	Brahy.D03G0216100	90.141	142	7	4	2585	2720	1960	2100	3.38E-42	178
	Brahy.S03G0044900	99.58	4281	18	0	1	4281	1	4281	0	7812
BdTR6g_Brahy.S03G0044900	Brahy.D03G0196400	91.689	1841	107	26	809	2638	742	2547	0	2516
	Brahy.D03G0196400	92.976	840	47	5	3411	4244	3211	4044	0	1214

	Brahy.D03G0196400	94.772	746	29	6	26	763	1	744	0	1153
	Brahy.D03G0196400	91.654	659	32	8	2673	3310	2553	3209	0	891
BdTR6g_Brahy.S03G0049100	Brahy.S03G0049100	99.883	5140	6	0	1	5140	1	5140	0	9459
	Brahy.D03G0191600	95.311	2751	109	11	2398	5140	2588	5326	0	4348
	Brahy.D03G0191600	88.468	1925	136	49	1	1865	6	1904	0	2246
	Brahy.D03G0191600	88.108	555	40	9	1868	2396	1963	2517	2.87E-180	636
BdTR6g_Brahy.S03G0067400	Brahy.S03G0067400	98.823	1444	17	0	1	1444	1	1444	0	2573
	Brahy.D03G0266600	86.137	642	63	16	65	701	72	692	0	669
	Brahy.D03G0266600	88.937	461	40	7	803	1259	770	1223	1.77E-157	558
BdTR6g_Brahy.S03G0072900	Brahy.S03G0072900	99.898	3906	4	0	1	3906	1	3906	0	7191
	Brahy.D03G0274300	89.673	2566	189	40	1387	3896	1479	4024	0	3201
	Brahy.D03G0274300	88.31	864	59	21	38	881	26	867	0	998
	Brahy.D03G0274300	91.887	530	38	4	867	1393	882	1409	0	736
BdTR6g_Brahy.S03G0077300	Brahy.S03G0077300	99.642	2796	10	0	1	2796	1	2796	0	5108
	Brahy.D03G0279400	87.01	1532	141	31	1292	2796	1449	2949	0	1674
	Brahy.D03G0279400	82.289	463	37	20	1	434	75	521	3.77E-97	359
	Brahy.D03G0279400	79.189	567	48	36	570	1124	740	1248	2.95E-88	329
BdTR6g_Brahy.S03G0085000	Brahy.S03G0085000	99.905	7349	7	0	1	7349	1	7349	0	13537
	Brahy.S03G0085000	100	28	0	0	1619	1646	1584	1611	1.89E-04	52.8
	Brahy.S03G0085000	100	28	0	0	1584	1611	1619	1646	1.89E-04	52.8
	Brahy.D03G0289100	93.203	2413	124	16	4832	7218	4508	6906	0	3511
	Brahy.D03G0289100	89.762	1680	142	12	2409	4077	2298	3958	0	2122
	Brahy.D03G0289100	93.548	558	29	3	4189	4740	3955	4511	0	824
	Brahy.D03G0289100	88.393	336	26	7	2073	2406	1893	2217	9.82E-107	392
	Brahy.D03G0289100	81.654	387	36	15	671	1042	1016	1382	1.33E-75	289
	Brahy.D03G0289100	79.193	322	30	17	206	511	466	766	1.38E-45	189
	Brahy.D03G0289100	90.551	127	10	2	1618	1744	1586	1710	6.48E-39	167
	Brahy.D03G0289100	92.473	93	6	1	1454	1546	1688	1597	2.36E-28	132
BdTR6g_Brahy.S03G0157500	Brahy.S03G0157500	99.942	13791	8	0	1	13791	1	13791	0	25423
	Brahy.D03G0374100	90.128	2421	129	54	11307	13650	11181	13568	0	3046

	Brahy.D03G0374100	91.351	1769	101	32	9366	11120	9314	11044	0	2372
	Brahy.D03G0374100	89.69	1775	122	27	7623	9374	7242	8978	0	2207
	Brahy.D03G0374100	91.979	1147	72	13	5805	6939	5480	6618	0	1591
	Brahy.D03G0374100	90.938	938	69	8	3319	4246	2950	3881	0	1247
	Brahy.D03G0374100	88.113	816	56	11	4731	5527	4687	5480	0	931
	Brahy.D03G0374100	94.305	597	30	3	6903	7496	6625	7220	0	911
	Brahy.D03G0374100	88.12	766	57	20	1142	1903	1299	2034	0	880
	Brahy.D03G0374100	93.296	537	25	9	2739	3270	2422	2952	0	782
	Brahy.D03G0374100	83.816	760	71	28	478	1215	574	1303	0	675
	Brahy.D03G0374100	87.701	374	42	4	1933	2303	2035	2407	1.09E-118	433
	Brahy.D03G0374100	85.205	365	37	10	4349	4699	4135	4496	1.87E-96	359
	Brahy.D03G0374100	90.833	120	9	2	2301	2420	13566	13683	2.04E-36	159
	Brahy.D03G0374100	85.455	110	13	1	4612	4718	4508	4617	5.79E-22	111
	Brahy.D03G0374100	81.034	116	6	7	4250	4351	3938	4051	5.87E-12	78.7
	Brahy.S03G0163500	99.5	6201	31	0	1	6201	1	6201	0	11280
	Brahy.S03G0163500	89.177	231	22	2	2964	3194	3057	3284	1.45E-74	285
	Brahy.S03G0163500	88.745	231	23	3	3057	3284	2964	3194	6.73E-73	279
	Brahy.S03G0163500	86.638	232	25	5	4029	4257	3858	3630	1.47E-64	252
	Brahy.S03G0163500	85.776	232	27	6	3630	3858	4257	4029	3.17E-61	241
	Brahy.S03G0163500	97.297	37	1	0	614	650	72	108	7.38E-08	63.9
	Brahy.S03G0163500	97.297	37	1	0	72	108	614	650	7.38E-08	63.9
BdTR6g_Brahy.S03G0163500	Brahy.D03G0380900	91.574	1792	121	18	4258	6048	2302	4064	0	2446
	Brahy.D03G0380900	90.31	743	46	10	1258	1990	1107	1833	0	950
	Brahy.D03G0380900	79.395	694	48	35	384	1051	332	956	1.38E-109	401
	Brahy.D03G0380900	87.571	354	23	13	2	354	1	334	2.98E-106	390
	Brahy.D03G0380900	88.757	169	14	3	1059	1222	936	1104	1.50E-49	202
	Brahy.D03G0380900	89.516	124	11	2	6078	6201	4056	4177	1.18E-35	156
	Brahy.D03G0380900	100	37	0	0	614	650	62	98	1.59E-09	69.4
	Brahy.S03G0182300	99.136	10649	92	0	1	10649	1	10649	0	19156
BdTR6g_Brahy.S03G0182300	Brahy.D03G0405100	93.565	4025	179	21	1200	5184	1553	5537	0	5925
	Brahy.D03G0405100	93.842	1218	49	11	6885	8097	6662	7858	0	1810

	Brahy.D03G0405100	91.754	1237	78	17	9412	10639	9379	10600	0	1698
	Brahy.D03G0405100	89.391	1216	68	20	1	1204	276	1442	0	1476
	Brahy.D03G0405100	93.28	878	41	7	8545	9413	8156	9024	0	1279
	Brahy.D03G0405100	92.179	895	37	15	5188	6073	5623	6493	0	1234
	Brahy.D03G0405100	90.96	177	7	2	6195	6371	6489	6656	1.18E-57	230
	Brahy.S03G0250600	99.651	9744	34	0	1	9744	1	9744	0	17806
	Brahy.S03G0250600	99.01	101	1	0	3226	3326	3125	3225	3.07E-43	182
	Brahy.S03G0250600	99.01	101	1	0	3125	3225	3226	3326	3.07E-43	182
BdTR6g_Brahy.S03G0250600	Brahy.D03G0487600	92.564	2367	117	24	785	3121	802	3139	0	3341
	Brahy.D03G0487600	89.88	2500	162	43	3234	5695	3269	5715	0	3131
	Brahy.D03G0487600	86.987	1560	132	41	5909	7413	5780	7323	0	1690
	Brahy.D03G0487600	93.526	865	46	6	8786	9642	8867	9729	0	1279
	Brahy.D03G0487600	97.381	611	15	1	1	611	14	623	0	1038
	Brahy.D03G0487600	87.5	520	29	17	7726	8220	7823	8331	2.02E-159	568
	Brahy.D03G0487600	86.124	209	21	5	8373	8576	8455	8660	2.34E-54	219
	Brahy.D03G0487600	80.876	251	30	9	7438	7688	7322	7554	3.07E-43	182
	Brahy.D03G0487600	91.489	94	7	1	3133	3225	3269	3362	4.06E-27	128
		Brahy.S03G0306400	99.905	7341	7	0	1	7341	1	7341	0
	Brahy.S03G0306400	94.872	39	1	1	697	735	730	767	1.13E-06	60.2
BdTR6g_Brahy.S03G0306400	Brahy.D03G0554700	96.526	2274	69	4	1977	4243	1887	4157	0	3753
	Brahy.D03G0554700	89.83	2763	142	43	4612	7341	4735	7391	0	3417
	Brahy.D03G0554700	87.898	1917	136	43	1	1854	7	1890	0	2167
	Brahy.D03G0554700	92.674	273	14	3	4240	4510	4187	4455	1.27E-105	388
	Brahy.S03G0314600	99.861	10782	15	0	248	11029	248	11029	0	19828
	Brahy.S03G0314600	100	175	0	0	1	175	1	175	5.46E-86	324
	Brahy.S03G0314600	97.778	45	1	0	4539	4583	4494	4538	4.69E-12	78.7
BdTR6g_Brahy.S03G0314600	Brahy.S03G0314600	97.778	45	1	0	4494	4538	4539	4583	4.69E-12	78.7
	Brahy.D03G0564300	90.097	4110	256	64	248	4289	71	4097	0	5195
	Brahy.D03G0564300	91.824	2385	134	25	8679	11029	7905	10262	0	3267
	Brahy.D03G0564300	91.958	1629	85	24	6952	8565	6306	7903	0	2241

	Brahy.D03G0564300	89.878	899	58	13	5515	6394	5310	6194	0	1125
	Brahy.D03G0564300	91.895	765	38	11	4539	5288	4187	4942	0	1048
	Brahy.D03G0564300	94.815	135	7	0	4402	4536	4095	4229	4.43E-52	211
	Brahy.D03G0564300	96.154	78	3	0	5419	5496	4929	5006	4.59E-27	128
	Brahy.S03G0336300	99.869	4574	6	0	1	4574	1	4574	0	8414
BdTR6g_Brahy.S03G0336300	Brahy.D03G0170800	93.931	2735	114	22	1868	4574	1698	4408	0	4084
	Brahy.D03G0170800	89.94	1511	79	24	1	1455	10	1503	0	1881
	Brahy.S04G0009700	99.783	7379	16	0	1	7379	1	7379	0	13538
	Brahy.D03G0823000	90.371	2399	183	20	2459	4848	2585	4944	0	3107
	Brahy.D03G0823000	91.992	1486	78	17	732	2188	851	2324	0	2047
BdTR6g_Brahy.S04G0009700	Brahy.D03G0823000	89.29	1522	125	23	5849	7348	5969	7474	0	1873
	Brahy.D03G0823000	89.93	993	82	10	4845	5822	4983	5972	0	1264
	Brahy.D03G0823000	92.633	733	42	7	3	726	1	730	0	1044
	Brahy.S04G0013900	99.699	3652	11	0	1	3652	1	3652	0	6684
BdTR6g_Brahy.S04G0013900	Brahy.D03G0818400	90.954	2034	105	34	1613	3635	1698	3663	0	2663
	Brahy.D03G0818400	93.246	1688	74	17	9	1664	19	1698	0	2449
	Brahy.S04G0025400	99.636	2475	9	0	1	2475	1	2475	0	4521
BdTR6g_Brahy.S04G0025400	Brahy.D03G0805400	95.531	2484	96	5	1	2475	181	2658	0	3958
	Brahy.S04G0125300	99.794	6801	14	0	3083	9883	3083	9883	0	12482
	Brahy.S04G0125300	99.769	3027	7	0	1	3027	1	3027	0	5552
	Brahy.D03G0696900	94.973	2546	93	15	7362	9883	7249	9783	0	3960
	Brahy.D03G0696900	92.751	2566	122	27	4423	6976	4148	6661	0	3650
	Brahy.D03G0696900	95.111	1166	49	6	1002	2161	938	2101	0	1831
BdTR6g_Brahy.S04G0125300	Brahy.D03G0696900	93.572	949	32	14	3099	4018	3009	3957	0	1387
	Brahy.D03G0696900	92.651	762	38	8	62	819	1	748	0	1081
	Brahy.D03G0696900	93.096	449	25	4	2187	2635	2205	2647	0	652
	Brahy.D03G0696900	97.742	310	7	0	2718	3027	2646	2955	2.08E-149	534
	Brahy.D03G0696900	96.014	276	10	1	6971	7245	6974	7249	2.78E-123	448
	Brahy.D03G0696900	95.07	142	6	1	3875	4015	3966	4107	1.84E-55	222
BdTR6g_Brahy.S04G0135100	Brahy.S04G0135100	99.239	4599	35	0	1	4599	1	4599	0	8344

	Brahy.D03G0685500	93.486	1397	70	4	3161	4540	3783	5175	0	2056
	Brahy.D03G0685500	90.802	511	22	5	5	500	1	501	0	660
	Brahy.D03G0685500	91.688	397	24	3	1953	2340	1908	2304	5.75E-152	542
	Brahy.D03G0685500	94.752	343	18	0	2325	2667	2352	2694	9.63E-150	534
	Brahy.D03G0685500	89.053	338	15	9	1243	1562	556	889	3.66E-109	399
	Brahy.D03G0685500	91.968	249	13	5	2755	2996	2739	2987	6.26E-92	342
	Brahy.D03G0685500	87.442	215	12	6	1580	1792	1718	1919	3.93E-59	233
	Brahy.S04G0149600	99.845	4530	7	0	1	4530	1	4530	0	8327
BdTR6g_Brahy.S04G0149600	Brahy.D03G0670100	92.41	1805	78	31	2749	4527	2486	4257	0	2519
	Brahy.D03G0670100	88.872	1294	64	33	5	1267	1	1245	0	1519
	Brahy.D03G0670100	90.659	546	39	4	2143	2679	1946	2488	0	715
	Brahy.S04G0161500	99.858	2815	4	0	1	2815	1	2815	0	5177
BdTR6g_Brahy.S04G0161500	Brahy.D03G0657500	89.16	2251	126	48	664	2815	678	2909	0	2697
	Brahy.D03G0657500	92.565	538	20	11	41	573	1	523	0	754
	Brahy.S04G0228000	99.773	6605	15	0	1	6605	1	6605	0	12116
BdTR6g_Brahy.S04G0228000	Brahy.S04G0228000	82.524	103	14	4	1729	1829	1826	1726	4.66E-15	87.9
	Brahy.D03G0157200	93.748	2575	112	19	1824	4358	1760	4325	0	3818
	Brahy.D03G0157200	89.752	1493	82	24	277	1730	302	1762	0	1845
	Brahy.D03G0157200	93.475	1180	53	7	5401	6575	5226	6386	0	1731
	Brahy.D03G0157200	95.568	925	31	6	4413	5335	4321	5237	0	1472
	Brahy.D03G0157200	81.169	154	4	8	100	249	114	246	5.99E-19	100
	Brahy.S04G0305800	99.865	9631	13	0	1	9631	1	9631	0	17719
BdTR6g_Brahy.S04G0305800	Brahy.D03G0071600	94.616	1746	79	9	1404	3138	1456	3197	0	2689
	Brahy.D03G0071600	92.068	1538	80	19	3728	5250	3847	5357	0	2126
	Brahy.D03G0071600	92.867	1402	70	18	6284	7675	5354	6735	0	2008
	Brahy.D03G0071600	89.529	1423	90	22	1	1404	38	1420	0	1748
	Brahy.D03G0071600	91.086	617	39	8	8851	9457	7868	8478	0	821
	Brahy.D03G0071600	90.224	624	32	8	7827	8449	6955	7550	0	787
	Brahy.D03G0071600	97.087	412	8	3	3155	3566	3183	3590	0	691
	Brahy.D03G0071600	91.626	203	12	4	8455	8656	7670	7868	1.35E-71	276

	Brahy.D03G0071600	93.789	161	9	1	7669	7829	6759	6918	4.94E-61	241	
	Brahy.S04G0318200	99.032	17039	165	0	1	17039	1	17039	0	30572	
	Brahy.S04G0318200	100	28	0	0	11683	11710	11316	11289	4.40E-04	52.8	
	Brahy.S04G0318200	100	28	0	0	11289	11316	11710	11683	4.40E-04	52.8	
BdTR6g_Brahy.S04G0318200	Brahy.D03G0057700	92.008	3003	125	46	6452	9391	6239	9189	0	4109	
	Brahy.D03G0057700	94.889	2622	106	12	13258	15856	12592	15208	0	4074	
	Brahy.D03G0057700	92.766	2433	138	17	24	2423	170	2597	0	3483	
	Brahy.D03G0057700	92.686	1709	78	16	4194	5880	3912	5595	0	2420	
	Brahy.D03G0057700	94.901	1216	53	8	11749	12962	11287	12495	0	1893	
	Brahy.D03G0057700	95.494	1043	30	9	16010	17039	15461	16499	0	1650	
	Brahy.D03G0057700	95.41	1024	40	3	9389	10407	9313	10334	0	1624	
	Brahy.D03G0057700	94.932	592	26	2	5876	6464	5624	6214	0	924	
	Brahy.D03G0057700	91.159	690	32	15	3495	4157	3104	3791	0	909	
	Brahy.D03G0057700	92.887	478	29	3	10817	11290	10747	11223	0	689	
	Brahy.D03G0057700	86.468	436	29	8	3022	3430	2670	3102	3.71E-124	451	
	Brahy.D03G0057700	92.118	203	3	1	10422	10624	10490	10679	8.62E-71	274	
	Brahy.D03G0057700	93.396	106	7	0	12991	13096	12490	12595	9.06E-36	158	
	Brahy.D03G0057700	91.228	57	5	0	10670	10726	10690	10746	7.26E-12	78.7	
	Brahy.D03G0057700	100	34	0	0	11728	11761	11333	11366	2.03E-07	63.9	
		Brahy.S04G0330200	97.122	7437	214	0	1	7437	1	7437	0	12550
	BdTR6g_Brahy.S04G0330200	Brahy.D03G0044200	88.392	2369	192	39	436	2745	1257	3601	0	2776
Brahy.D03G0044200		92.507	1428	67	16	4822	6231	5817	7222	0	2008	
Brahy.D03G0044200		86.74	1184	82	37	2762	3906	3684	4831	0	1247	
Brahy.D03G0044200		89.368	950	45	18	3898	4823	4862	5779	0	1144	
Brahy.D03G0044200		87.678	982	71	17	6228	7180	7275	8235	0	1098	
Brahy.D03G0044200		85.294	374	28	14	3	353	718	1087	2.80E-97	361	
Brahy.D03G0044200		92.562	121	4	4	7243	7358	8234	8354	1.82E-39	169	
	Brahy.S04G0356700	99.835	1815	3	0	1	1815	1	1815	0	3336	
BdTR6g_Brahy.S04G0356700	Brahy.D03G0013900	88.895	1819	114	44	32	1812	88	1856	0	2159	
BdTR6g_Brahy.S05G0025700	Brahy.S05G0025700	100	2657	0	0	1	2657	1	2657	0	4907	

	Brahy.D04G0356700	84.639	1660	146	50	461	2090	536	2116	0	1552
	Brahy.D04G0356700	88.991	436	26	9	2237	2657	2152	2580	1.55E-145	520
	Brahy.D04G0356700	91.146	384	24	6	1	376	46	427	2.60E-143	512
BdTR6g_Brahy.S05G0037400	Brahy.S05G0037400	100	10576	0	0	1	10576	1	10576	0	19531
	Brahy.D04G0339400	94.697	5223	192	23	5344	10511	5279	10471	0	8032
	Brahy.D04G0339400	96.442	3429	113	4	1868	5295	1857	5277	0	5648
	Brahy.D04G0339400	84.538	1895	176	54	1	1865	5	1812	0	1768
BdTR6g_Brahy.S05G0044300	Brahy.S05G0044300	98.901	3641	40	0	1	3641	1	3641	0	6503
	Brahy.D04G0331300	89.145	1824	145	35	1841	3640	1618	3412	0	2222
	Brahy.D04G0331300	92.016	1027	67	9	603	1623	446	1463	0	1428
	Brahy.D04G0331300	89.631	434	24	13	3	422	1	427	2.74E-149	532
BdTR6g_Brahy.S05G0119900	Brahy.S05G0119900	99.853	5429	8	0	1	5429	1	5429	0	9985
	Brahy.D04G0415900	89.23	3194	212	63	634	3789	508	3607	0	3875
	Brahy.D04G0415900	92.166	1353	90	9	3959	5303	3696	5040	0	1897
	Brahy.D04G0415900	89.588	413	32	7	118	519	99	511	1.48E-143	514
	Brahy.D04G0415900	94.737	57	3	0	3786	3842	3642	3698	1.06E-15	89.8
BdTR6g_Brahy.S05G0140400	Brahy.S05G0140400	99.766	4271	10	0	1	4271	1	4271	0	7832
	Brahy.D04G0439500	87.889	1222	84	23	8	1170	5	1221	0	1378
	Brahy.D04G0439500	95.059	850	36	4	2273	3120	1964	2809	0	1332
	Brahy.D04G0439500	91.489	893	34	17	3230	4083	2803	3692	0	1190
	Brahy.D04G0439500	86.116	605	59	13	1166	1750	1252	1851	3.99E-178	628
	Brahy.D04G0439500	88.496	113	11	2	2100	2210	1848	1960	1.06E-29	135
BdTR6g_Brahy.S05G0162800	Brahy.S05G0162800	99.702	5703	17	0	1	5703	1	5703	0	10449
	Brahy.S05G0162800	91.525	118	6	3	4716	4829	1318	1435	8.41E-37	159
	Brahy.S05G0162800	91.525	118	6	3	1318	1435	4716	4829	8.41E-37	159
	Brahy.D04G0464300	94.521	1953	74	15	2561	4493	2405	4344	0	2983
	Brahy.D04G0464300	89.488	723	20	13	620	1310	530	1228	0	863
	Brahy.D04G0464300	90.924	606	35	8	1878	2466	1807	2409	0	797
	Brahy.D04G0464300	93.396	530	14	10	6	514	1	530	0	765
	Brahy.D04G0464300	93.86	456	23	5	4827	5281	4528	4979	0	682

	Brahy.D04G0464300	89.683	378	26	6	1525	1890	1356	1732	3.42E-130	470
	Brahy.D04G0464300	94.565	184	10	0	4534	4717	4346	4529	1.33E-74	285
	Brahy.S05G0235300	99.589	5591	23	0	1	5591	1	5591	0	10214
	Brahy.S05G0235300	97.024	168	5	0	4125	4292	3917	4084	4.69E-74	283
	Brahy.S05G0235300	97.024	168	5	0	3917	4084	4125	4292	4.69E-74	283
BdTR6g_Brahy.S05G0235300	Brahy.D04G0549700	92.423	2600	126	21	1748	4292	1737	4320	0	3655
	Brahy.D04G0549700	89.826	1091	78	15	4285	5351	4374	5455	0	1369
	Brahy.D04G0549700	86.489	1051	62	26	712	1743	673	1662	0	1081
	Brahy.D04G0549700	90.332	693	50	12	20	697	1	691	0	893
	Brahy.D04G0549700	93.81	210	10	1	3917	4126	4153	4359	5.98E-83	313
	Brahy.D04G0549700	95.833	168	7	0	4125	4292	3945	4112	1.01E-70	272
	Brahy.S05G0245200	99.841	5039	8	0	1	5039	1	5039	0	9263
	Brahy.D04G0559100	92.848	3761	155	48	1	3685	46	3768	0	5352
	Brahy.D04G0559100	96.684	1357	39	4	3684	5039	3882	5233	0	2252
	Brahy.S05G0250000	99.673	4582	15	0	1	4582	1	4582	0	8379
BdTR6g_Brahy.S05G0250000	Brahy.D04G0563900	94.393	1712	65	17	1060	2742	1192	2901	0	2601
	Brahy.D04G0563900	91.817	1723	107	17	2744	4451	3942	5645	0	2370
	Brahy.D04G0563900	88.71	682	29	20	1	653	84	746	0	789
	Brahy.D04G0563900	93.605	344	19	1	704	1047	795	1135	1.62E-142	510
	Brahy.S05G0255400	99.461	9830	53	0	1	9830	1	9830	0	17872
	Brahy.S05G0255400	91.102	236	19	2	1227	1461	1458	1224	2.26E-84	318
BdTR6g_Brahy.S05G0255400	Brahy.D04G0569300	89.795	3910	269	54	6003	9830	5072	8933	0	4891
	Brahy.D04G0569300	89.532	1987	152	31	1731	3671	1465	3441	0	2466
	Brahy.D04G0569300	91.714	1231	71	14	25	1228	2	1228	0	1679
	Brahy.D04G0569300	91.186	953	73	9	4672	5623	3768	4710	0	1284
	Brahy.D04G0569300	93.498	323	15	2	5684	6001	4713	5034	1.27E-131	475
	Brahy.D04G0569300	92.276	246	18	1	1457	1702	1224	1468	2.89E-93	348
	Brahy.D04G0569300	84.153	183	27	2	4171	4351	3439	3621	1.44E-41	176
	Brahy.D04G0569300	87.037	108	8	4	4487	4592	3664	3767	8.86E-24	117
	BdTR6g_Brahy.S05G0285900	Brahy.S05G0285900	99.45	7814	43	0	1	7814	1	7814	0

	Brahy.D01G0264000	88.431	994	74	16	7496	8468	6911	7884	0	1160
	Brahy.D01G0264000	91.333	150	5	6	7135	7281	6184	6328	3.14E-48	198
	Brahy.D01G0264000	91.892	111	7	1	7025	7135	6045	6153	6.90E-35	154
	Brahy.S06G0049500	99.442	5376	30	0	1	5376	1	5376	0	9762
BdTR6g_Brahy.S06G0049500	Brahy.D01G0269700	92.891	1913	90	30	1	1883	6	1902	0	2737
	Brahy.D01G0269700	86.913	1918	153	54	1892	3737	1848	3739	0	2061
	Brahy.D01G0269700	89.64	695	50	10	4616	5294	4055	4743	0	865
	Brahy.D01G0269700	84.225	355	41	8	4238	4591	3724	4064	1.59E-88	331
	Brahy.S06G0068800	99.341	4402	29	0	1	4402	1	4402	0	7995
BdTR6g_Brahy.S06G0068800	Brahy.D01G0292200	92.09	1732	99	23	2002	3709	1989	3706	0	2431
	Brahy.D01G0292200	84.341	2018	151	65	20	1951	47	1985	0	1823
	Brahy.D01G0292200	94.943	435	21	1	3726	4160	3690	4123	0	680
	Brahy.D01G0292200	94.774	287	14	1	4116	4402	4124	4409	4.44E-123	446
	Brahy.S06G0077500	99.882	8457	10	0	1	8457	1	8457	0	15581
BdTR6g_Brahy.S06G0077500	Brahy.D01G0301000	86.905	1619	110	33	1588	3141	1629	3210	0	1736
	Brahy.D01G0301000	90.517	1276	75	23	4104	5351	4017	5274	0	1644
	Brahy.D01G0301000	87.894	1363	104	36	15	1334	1	1345	0	1548
	Brahy.D01G0301000	89.168	877	51	29	7587	8457	7533	8371	0	1053
	Brahy.D01G0301000	93.31	583	30	4	3379	3960	3196	3770	0	852
	Brahy.D01G0301000	88.816	456	21	9	5671	6122	5473	5902	6.38E-149	532
	Brahy.D01G0301000	90.808	359	25	7	6142	6498	6062	6414	3.92E-131	473
	Brahy.D01G0301000	84.375	480	35	10	7151	7598	7033	7504	1.85E-119	435
	Brahy.D01G0301000	92.481	266	17	3	6573	6837	6417	6680	3.17E-102	377
	Brahy.D01G0301000	87.857	280	18	7	6835	7104	6762	7035	2.52E-83	315
	Brahy.D01G0301000	93.75	128	7	1	1411	1537	1343	1470	4.43E-46	191
	Brahy.D01G0301000	88.435	147	8	2	5393	5538	5266	5404	2.07E-39	169
	Brahy.S06G0136700	98.804	8777	105	0	4189	12965	4189	12965	0	15780
BdTR6g_Brahy.S06G0136700	Brahy.S06G0136700	99.928	4147	3	0	1	4147	1	4147	0	7642
	Brahy.D01G0360100	91.715	1714	95	22	8050	9738	7444	9135	0	2335
	Brahy.D01G0360100	88.904	1469	121	19	1636	3088	1077	2519	0	1772

	Brahy.D01G0360100	91.955	895	42	7	12048	12929	9742	10619	0	1227
	Brahy.D01G0360100	89.289	999	56	23	6802	7760	6458	7445	0	1205
	Brahy.D01G0360100	88.175	685	43	20	1	675	16	672	0	782
	Brahy.D01G0360100	91.667	564	36	9	3550	4108	3160	3717	0	771
	Brahy.D01G0360100	83.423	742	72	22	6058	6763	5740	6466	0	641
	Brahy.D01G0360100	87.368	475	47	10	3087	3550	2563	3035	9.80E-149	532
	Brahy.D01G0360100	89.895	287	21	2	5631	5917	5462	5740	1.36E-97	363
	Brahy.D01G0360100	79.145	585	67	28	11305	11863	9135	9690	8.19E-95	353
	Brahy.D01G0360100	82.41	415	24	16	682	1075	651	1037	1.07E-83	316
	Brahy.D01G0360100	84.328	134	17	4	4616	4747	4346	4477	5.40E-27	128
	Brahy.S06G0160600	99.788	6598	14	0	1	6598	1	6598	0	12107
	Brahy.S06G0160600	97.059	34	1	0	5926	5959	5862	5895	3.65E-06	58.4
	Brahy.S06G0160600	97.059	34	1	0	5862	5895	5926	5959	3.65E-06	58.4
BdTR6g_Brahy.S06G0160600	Brahy.D01G0714500	85.957	2820	257	71	1744	4495	1863	4611	0	2885
	Brahy.D01G0714500	83.634	831	77	35	5039	5837	5274	6077	0	726
	Brahy.D01G0714500	84.556	518	58	13	712	1214	817	1327	2.35E-137	494
	Brahy.D01G0714500	85.684	475	54	10	1275	1743	1312	1778	1.09E-135	488
	Brahy.D01G0714500	79.704	473	50	19	6086	6515	6245	6714	5.50E-79	300
	Brahy.D01G0714500	84.536	97	15	0	4539	4635	5137	5233	7.74E-18	97.1
	Brahy.S06G0160900	99.863	9455	13	0	1	9455	1	9455	0	17391
	Brahy.S06G0160900	100	55	0	0	315	369	263	317	2.39E-19	102
	Brahy.S06G0160900	100	55	0	0	263	317	315	369	2.39E-19	102
BdTR6g_Brahy.S06G0160900	Brahy.D01G0714800	93.558	3151	129	29	5951	9067	7242	10352	0	4626
	Brahy.D01G0714800	93.677	1961	77	15	1544	3489	1634	3562	0	2891
	Brahy.D01G0714800	92.152	790	43	11	4022	4797	3888	4672	0	1098
	Brahy.D01G0714800	88.859	754	58	15	716	1448	844	1592	0	904
	Brahy.D01G0714800	93.478	552	34	2	5403	5953	4854	5404	0	819
	Brahy.D01G0714800	84.52	323	19	10	315	632	177	473	4.74E-76	291
	Brahy.D01G0714800	87.747	253	19	4	9082	9328	10339	10585	2.21E-74	285
	Brahy.D01G0714800	92.81	153	11	0	3723	3875	3563	3715	1.76E-55	222
	Brahy.D01G0714800	84	250	18	3	67	315	1	229	6.31E-55	220

	Brahy.D01G0714800	90.141	142	9	4	5121	5262	4697	4833	1.07E-42	180
	Brahy.D01G0714800	88.889	117	11	2	9267	9382	10561	10676	1.41E-31	143
	Brahy.S06G0216900	99.629	7006	26	0	1	7006	1	7006	0	12820
BdTR6g_Brahy.S06G0216900	Brahy.D01G0756100	93.989	3560	151	33	3465	7006	3623	7137	0	5330
	Brahy.D01G0756100	92.485	652	39	8	1738	2384	2483	3129	0	924
	Brahy.D01G0756100	96.721	61	2	0	1681	1741	2379	2439	1.77E-19	102
	Brahy.S06G0218200	99.486	9528	49	0	1	9528	1	9528	0	17324
	Brahy.S06G0218200	81.739	230	28	13	7350	7572	7572	7350	1.08E-42	180
BdTR6g_Brahy.S06G0218200	Brahy.D01G0758700	90.242	1117	77	16	1116	2221	648	1743	0	1430
	Brahy.D01G0758700	92.151	981	44	15	4890	5867	6572	7522	0	1354
	Brahy.D01G0758700	91.037	781	47	13	2909	3682	3809	4573	0	1033
	Brahy.D01G0758700	91.384	766	36	11	6423	7178	8066	8811	0	1022
	Brahy.D01G0758700	93.813	598	31	3	8701	9294	12391	12986	0	894
	Brahy.D01G0758700	90.4	625	39	8	2218	2835	1866	2476	0	802
	Brahy.D01G0758700	95.392	434	17	3	5865	6297	7635	8066	0	688
	Brahy.D01G0758700	88.533	593	29	18	8116	8706	11729	12284	0	682
	Brahy.D01G0758700	86.972	568	24	16	3844	4372	4899	5455	3.25E-167	593
	Brahy.D01G0758700	88.438	320	31	4	4578	4895	6087	6402	2.76E-103	381
	Brahy.D01G0758700	88.785	321	19	5	4275	4582	5455	5771	3.57E-102	377
	Brahy.D01G0758700	89.011	273	23	2	3686	3958	4625	4890	2.82E-88	331
	Brahy.D01G0758700	88.048	251	16	7	446	695	410	647	2.22E-74	285
	Brahy.D01G0758700	94.203	138	7	1	6296	6433	1739	1875	1.38E-51	209
	Brahy.D01G0758700	92.361	144	9	1	7209	7350	10464	10607	6.41E-50	204
	Brahy.D01G0758700	85.93	199	13	5	7571	7764	10604	10792	2.98E-48	198
	Brahy.D01G0758700	93.814	97	6	0	7780	7876	10773	10869	1.10E-32	147
Brahy.D01G0758700	83.2	125	9	2	9296	9408	13065	13189	6.69E-20	104	
Brahy.D01G0758700	96.97	33	0	1	7189	7221	8809	8840	6.83E-05	54.7	
	Brahy.S06G0247400	99.9	14935	15	0	1	14935	1	14935	0	27497
BdTR6g_Brahy.S06G0247400	Brahy.D01G0796400	88.096	2957	235	67	11979	14887	11636	14523	0	3402
	Brahy.D01G0796400	89.534	1653	105	25	262	1902	240	1836	0	2032

	Brahy.D01G0796400	85.43	1963	194	39	3116	5020	3017	4945	0	1956
	Brahy.D01G0796400	88.636	1364	114	29	7456	8787	7139	8493	0	1622
	Brahy.D01G0796400	88.051	1339	102	24	9685	10977	9449	10775	0	1533
	Brahy.D01G0796400	87.611	1348	101	29	5136	6427	4961	6298	0	1504
	Brahy.D01G0796400	93.403	955	51	5	2114	3066	2069	3013	0	1404
	Brahy.D01G0796400	90.299	835	62	11	11158	11991	10781	11597	0	1075
	Brahy.D01G0796400	89.664	387	38	2	9244	9629	9046	9431	1.92E-136	492
	Brahy.D01G0796400	86.441	413	44	5	8828	9228	8579	8991	1.96E-121	442
	Brahy.D01G0796400	84.665	463	36	15	6461	6908	6298	6740	1.52E-117	429
	Brahy.D01G0796400	90.217	184	14	2	1934	2117	1839	2018	9.91E-60	237
	Brahy.S06G0268900	99.478	4984	26	0	1	4984	1	4984	0	9060
BdTR6g_Brahy.S06G0268900	Brahy.D01G0820400	92.515	2565	144	25	2412	4942	2581	5131	0	3629
	Brahy.D01G0820400	83.434	2149	187	72	1	2042	2	2088	0	1840
	Brahy.D01G0820400	85.789	380	34	6	2049	2414	2125	2498	1.11E-104	385
	Brahy.S07G0012100	99.881	4188	5	0	1	4188	1	4188	0	7707
BdTR6g_Brahy.S07G0012100	Brahy.D01G0692200	91.732	1270	71	16	1691	2956	2680	3919	0	1733
	Brahy.D01G0692200	85.104	1101	82	32	23	1052	28	1117	0	1050
	Brahy.D01G0692200	89.02	765	61	16	2995	3749	3915	4666	0	926
	Brahy.D01G0692200	89.819	442	28	2	3747	4187	4749	5174	8.70E-155	551
	Brahy.D01G0692200	90.774	336	30	1	1131	1465	1120	1455	1.17E-123	448
	Brahy.D01G0692200	88.511	235	24	2	1459	1690	2411	2645	1.26E-73	281
	Brahy.S07G0040500	99.914	4634	4	0	1	4634	1	4634	0	8536
BdTR6g_Brahy.S07G0040500	Brahy.S07G0040500	100	30	0	0	2821	2850	2718	2747	9.21E-06	56.5
	Brahy.S07G0040500	100	30	0	0	2718	2747	2821	2850	9.21E-06	56.5
	Brahy.D01G0657800	93.258	2655	133	22	1974	4597	1798	4437	0	3869
	Brahy.D01G0657800	88.621	1204	80	27	51	1230	28	1198	0	1411
	Brahy.D01G0657800	94.737	380	18	2	1273	1650	1179	1558	2.04E-166	590
	Brahy.D01G0657800	92.891	211	15	0	1650	1860	1589	1799	2.30E-81	307
	Brahy.D01G0657800	100	30	0	0	2718	2747	2638	2667	9.21E-06	56.5
BdTR6g_Brahy.S07G0080900	Brahy.S07G0080900	99.722	2873	8	0	1	2873	1	2873	0	5262

	Brahy.D01G0607200	89.979	958	57	24	798	1736	807	1744	0	1201
	Brahy.D01G0607200	92.897	718	30	13	3	709	48	755	0	1024
	Brahy.D01G0607200	92.671	614	44	1	2242	2855	3261	3873	0	883
	Brahy.D01G0607200	95.849	265	10	1	1974	2238	2193	2456	1.05E-117	427
	Brahy.D01G0607200	92.381	210	16	0	1735	1944	1986	2195	2.38E-79	300
	Brahy.S07G0095500	97.322	4631	124	0	1	4631	1	4631	0	7904
BdTR6g_Brahy.S07G0095500	Brahy.S07G0095500	100	65	0	0	2042	2106	2105	2169	3.22E-25	121
	Brahy.S07G0095500	96.923	65	2	0	2105	2169	2042	2106	6.96E-22	110
	Brahy.D01G0590100	86.627	1503	151	24	2127	3603	1535	3013	0	1616
	Brahy.D01G0590100	89.222	1336	83	32	476	1765	1	1321	0	1615
	Brahy.D01G0590100	85.556	360	36	12	4147	4499	3497	3847	4.84E-98	363
	Brahy.S07G0113300	99.805	3081	6	0	1	3081	1	3081	0	5659
BdTR6g_Brahy.S07G0113300	Brahy.S07G0113300	86.316	95	13	0	1634	1728	1725	1631	2.15E-20	104
	Brahy.D01G0570000	93.777	1607	66	12	30	1626	38	1620	0	2385
	Brahy.D01G0570000	96.89	1254	34	3	1833	3081	1809	3062	0	2095
	Brahy.D01G0570000	97.03	101	2	1	1727	1827	1625	1724	7.52E-40	169
	Brahy.S07G0191900	99.847	3923	6	0	1	3923	1	3923	0	7212
BdTR6g_Brahy.S07G0191900	Brahy.D01G0482000	94.65	1888	81	15	2015	3894	12673	10798	0	2909
	Brahy.D01G0482000	89.526	401	30	6	1436	1832	13451	13059	1.08E-138	497
	Brahy.S07G0237600	99.831	4154	7	0	1	4154	1	4154	0	7633
BdTR6g_Brahy.S07G0237600	Brahy.D01G0427600	96.438	1095	33	3	3022	4110	2696	3790	0	1801
	Brahy.D01G0427600	91.871	1144	61	9	1458	2591	1503	2624	0	1568
	Brahy.D01G0427600	86.667	1485	102	47	2	1454	1	1421	0	1557
	Brahy.S07G0265000	99.941	3387	2	0	1	3387	1	3387	0	6244
BdTR6g_Brahy.S07G0265000	Brahy.D01G0391400	89.6	3404	194	82	39	3385	1	3301	0	4178
	Brahy.S08G0013700	99.774	7982	18	0	1	7982	1	7982	0	14641
BdTR6g_Brahy.S08G0013700	Brahy.D02G0215000	95.798	2380	70	14	2545	4899	2452	4826	0	3814
	Brahy.D02G0215000	93.392	2497	108	13	13	2497	1	2452	0	3644
	Brahy.D02G0215000	94.595	999	36	5	5260	6247	6139	7130	0	1530
	Brahy.D02G0215000	87.674	1079	66	34	6402	7443	7300	8348	0	1194

	Brahy.D02G0215000	89.319	543	24	10	7444	7975	8407	8926	0	651
	Brahy.D02G0215000	91.053	380	9	9	4896	5252	5689	6066	3.68E-136	490
BdTR6g_Brahy.S08G0020400	Brahy.S08G0020400	99.969	3239	1	0	1	3239	1	3239	0	5976
	Brahy.D02G0223300	89.717	1906	139	31	1022	2894	1122	3003	0	2381
	Brahy.D02G0223300	90.23	174	13	4	431	603	431	601	1.66E-56	224
	Brahy.D02G0223300	89.13	138	8	3	122	258	201	332	1.02E-38	165
BdTR6g_Brahy.S08G0021000	Brahy.S08G0021000	99.538	14704	68	0	1	14704	1	14704	0	26799
	Brahy.S08G0021000	89.796	98	8	2	12202	12298	12298	12202	7.93E-26	124
	Brahy.D02G0223900	92.865	2649	126	26	4708	7325	5123	7739	0	3786
	Brahy.D02G0223900	95.088	2260	96	7	556	2814	512	2757	0	3544
	Brahy.D02G0223900	95.521	1429	52	7	2820	4244	2882	4302	0	2274
	Brahy.D02G0223900	89.33	1059	91	10	8194	9242	7851	8897	0	1310
	Brahy.D02G0223900	87.129	1111	101	18	10501	11575	10340	11444	0	1221
	Brahy.D02G0223900	83.617	1056	148	19	9456	10500	9136	10177	0	968
	Brahy.D02G0223900	93.567	513	17	7	23	520	1	512	0	750
	Brahy.D02G0223900	87.5	632	45	9	12297	12909	12056	12672	0	699
	Brahy.D02G0223900	94.678	451	19	4	4243	4689	4607	5056	0	695
	Brahy.D02G0223900	90.754	411	31	5	14226	14633	14052	14458	1.43E-152	545
	Brahy.D02G0223900	89.831	354	22	5	13061	13409	12909	13253	4.14E-123	448
	Brahy.D02G0223900	81.124	498	38	25	13715	14183	13582	14052	3.34E-94	351
	Brahy.D02G0223900	93.103	232	14	2	11951	12181	11797	12027	2.60E-90	339
	Brahy.D02G0223900	88.298	282	19	3	11682	11952	11491	11769	2.03E-86	326
	Brahy.D02G0223900	88.372	129	11	4	9271	9396	8998	9125	3.64E-34	152
Brahy.D02G0223900	97.297	37	1	0	7500	7536	7819	7855	1.75E-07	63.9	
BdTR6g_Brahy.S08G0140800	Brahy.S08G0140800	99.849	7305	11	0	1	7305	1	7305	0	13431
	Brahy.S08G0140800	82	100	12	6	3243	3339	3339	3243	8.63E-13	80.5
	Brahy.D02G0372600	97.686	2334	53	1	4904	7237	4665	6997	0	4012
	Brahy.D02G0372600	94.568	2301	107	7	1	2283	175	2475	0	3541
	Brahy.D02G0372600	91.835	1139	47	17	3338	4472	3496	4592	0	1546
	Brahy.D02G0372600	91.739	460	26	6	2795	3243	3041	3499	6.84E-178	628

	Brahy.D02G0372600	94.198	293	16	1	2282	2573	2589	2881	7.39E-123	446
	Brahy.D02G0372600	92.105	76	4	2	4888	4962	4592	4666	1.42E-20	106
	Brahy.D02G0372600	88.462	78	1	1	7236	7305	7037	7114	5.16E-15	87.9
	Brahy.S08G0142800	99.808	8345	16	0	1	8345	1	8345	0	15322
BdTR6g_Brahy.S08G0142800	Brahy.D02G0375100	85.989	3376	289	96	3338	6581	3566	6889	0	3445
	Brahy.D02G0375100	93.223	1697	97	13	35	1717	1	1693	0	2481
	Brahy.D02G0375100	91.131	902	66	5	7455	8345	7105	8003	0	1210
	Brahy.D02G0375100	85.453	928	89	24	2153	3064	2143	3040	0	924
	Brahy.D02G0375100	90.541	222	12	6	3100	3314	3039	3258	1.95E-74	285
		Brahy.S08G0145700	99.796	3921	8	0	1	3921	1	3921	0
BdTR6g_Brahy.S08G0145700	Brahy.D03G0465700	94.55	1743	67	10	1202	2935	930	2653	0	2667
	Brahy.D03G0465700	92.077	732	30	10	3171	3875	2806	3536	0	1005
	Brahy.D03G0465700	93.382	136	4	3	788	921	345	477	4.40E-48	196
	Brahy.D03G0465700	93.814	97	3	1	995	1088	832	928	5.81E-32	143
	Brahy.D03G0465700	82.778	180	10	5	2975	3150	2654	2816	2.09E-31	141
		Brahy.S08G0179800	99.919	6157	5	0	1	6157	1	6157	0
BdTR6g_Brahy.S08G0179800	Brahy.D02G0415600	92.899	3056	159	29	2057	5081	1978	5006	0	4388
	Brahy.D02G0415600	90.417	887	56	17	1	872	17	889	0	1140
	Brahy.D02G0415600	90.943	795	42	7	5376	6142	5553	6345	0	1042
	Brahy.D02G0415600	85.855	608	35	19	1475	2060	1319	1897	4.51E-169	599
	Brahy.D02G0415600	91.277	321	25	3	1157	1475	885	1204	1.35E-119	435
	Brahy.D02G0415600	95.536	112	5	0	5248	5359	5146	5257	6.97E-43	180
	Brahy.D02G0415600	96.226	53	1	1	5113	5164	5095	5147	1.56E-14	86.1
	Brahy.S08G0187200	99.454	6225	34	0	1	6225	1	6225	0	11358
BdTR6g_Brahy.S08G0187200	Brahy.S08G0187200	94.382	89	3	2	4567	4654	4654	4567	1.55E-29	135
	Brahy.D02G0425500	87.965	2634	242	42	588	3204	551	3126	0	3070
	Brahy.D02G0425500	88.88	1241	98	22	3309	4544	3331	4536	0	1491
	Brahy.D02G0425500	82.64	841	83	28	5236	6017	5018	5854	0	686
	Brahy.D02G0425500	86.709	316	38	4	5907	6219	5855	6169	1.83E-93	348
	Brahy.D02G0425500	89.057	265	19	5	230	484	88	352	3.98E-85	320

	Brahy.D02G0425500	91.429	70	2	2	115	184	9	74	9.44E-17	93.5
	Brahy.S08G0262200	99.096	7631	69	0	1	7631	1	7631	0	13815
	Brahy.D02G0522100	89.701	1874	119	36	680	2529	600	2423	0	2324
	Brahy.D02G0522100	94.154	1454	64	18	6098	7544	5587	7026	0	2194
	Brahy.D02G0522100	93.575	1074	44	11	4602	5654	4230	5299	0	1578
	Brahy.D02G0522100	90.213	940	45	21	3689	4606	3286	4200	0	1182
BdTR6g_Brahy.S08G0262200	Brahy.D02G0522100	92.072	391	25	3	3246	3634	2888	3274	5.68E-159	566
	Brahy.D02G0522100	91.798	317	24	2	2532	2846	2519	2835	1.66E-124	451
	Brahy.D02G0522100	91.603	131	6	3	5701	5826	5295	5425	1.12E-41	176
	Brahy.D02G0522100	91.743	109	5	2	578	686	447	551	2.44E-33	148
	Brahy.D02G0522100	76.761	284	35	23	61	320	1	277	8.83E-28	130
	Brahy.D02G0522100	100	30	0	0	6247	6276	5621	5650	1.52E-05	56.5
	Brahy.S08G0271400	99.896	9655	10	0	1	9655	1	9655	0	17775
	Brahy.D02G0532900	94.211	7013	253	53	1498	8481	1529	8417	0	10560
BdTR6g_Brahy.S08G0271400	Brahy.D02G0532900	83.253	1451	122	55	20	1392	14	1421	0	1221
	Brahy.D02G0532900	92.203	590	24	9	8558	9132	8412	8994	0	815
	Brahy.D02G0532900	93.176	425	19	3	9135	9557	9055	9471	7.04E-174	616
	Brahy.S09G0041100	98.946	5504	58	0	1	5504	1	5504	0	9843
	Brahy.D05G0061600	90.365	2491	137	43	3085	5503	3344	5803	0	3175
BdTR6g_Brahy.S09G0041100	Brahy.D05G0061600	95.558	1103	40	8	1995	3094	2177	3273	0	1757
	Brahy.D05G0061600	82.222	1440	102	70	81	1433	1	1373	0	1099
	Brahy.D05G0061600	90.625	64	5	1	1300	1362	1188	1251	5.02E-14	84.2
	Brahy.S09G0067200	99.743	7791	20	0	1	7791	1	7791	0	14277
	Brahy.D05G0110200	93.365	1266	57	12	4817	6075	6569	7814	0	1847
	Brahy.D05G0110200	92.881	1222	55	15	6413	7622	8165	9366	0	1746
	Brahy.D05G0110200	90.746	1113	62	18	3227	4328	4351	5433	0	1447
BdTR6g_Brahy.S09G0067200	Brahy.D05G0110200	84.179	1163	55	57	1690	2749	1658	2794	0	1009
	Brahy.D05G0110200	85.587	1013	57	48	49	1023	33	994	0	979
	Brahy.D05G0110200	89.816	599	20	8	1099	1685	1018	1587	0	730
	Brahy.D05G0110200	90.909	242	21	1	6176	6416	7811	8052	3.85E-86	324

	Brahy.D05G0110200	86.935	199	9	7	3025	3207	4166	4363	4.05E-51	207
	Brahy.D05G0110200	97.059	68	2	0	2768	2835	2876	2943	2.52E-23	115
BdTR6g_Brahy.S09G0076800	Brahy.S09G0076800	100	5298	0	0	1	5298	1	5298	0	9784
	Brahy.D05G0122600	90.345	5355	290	110	1	5253	22	5251	0	6815
	Brahy.S09G0124700	99.898	4890	5	0	1	4890	1	4890	0	9005
	Brahy.S09G0124700	81.011	653	100	16	944	1584	838	1478	1.34E-138	497
	Brahy.S09G0124700	81.011	653	100	15	838	1478	944	1584	1.34E-138	497
	Brahy.S09G0124700	84.134	479	62	10	838	1308	1156	1628	1.06E-124	451
	Brahy.S09G0124700	83.925	479	63	10	1156	1628	838	1308	4.94E-123	446
	Brahy.S09G0124700	83.028	436	60	8	838	1264	1048	1478	3.93E-104	383
	Brahy.S09G0124700	85.252	278	29	7	1310	1584	890	1158	6.85E-72	276
BdTR6g_Brahy.S09G0124700	Brahy.S09G0124700	84.892	278	30	7	890	1158	1310	1584	3.19E-70	270
	Brahy.D05G0178500	93.256	3944	206	34	944	4865	867	4772	0	5755
	Brahy.D05G0178500	86.456	1521	124	48	9	1478	1	1490	0	1592
	Brahy.D05G0178500	87.131	474	41	10	838	1308	1078	1534	2.87E-145	520
	Brahy.D05G0178500	88.759	427	32	9	838	1264	973	1383	6.21E-142	508
	Brahy.D05G0178500	82.963	540	66	14	1048	1584	867	1383	1.36E-128	464
	Brahy.D05G0178500	81.841	402	44	18	1156	1547	867	1249	1.88E-82	311
	Brahy.D05G0178500	89.401	217	20	2	1368	1584	867	1080	3.19E-70	270
	Brahy.D05G0178500	89.908	109	11	0	1476	1584	867	975	2.61E-31	141
	Brahy.S09G0136600	99.88	4158	5	0	1	4158	1	4158	0	7651
	Brahy.D05G0193900	92.656	1280	71	9	1252	2524	1199	2462	0	1821
BdTR6g_Brahy.S09G0136600	Brahy.D05G0193900	91.953	1193	56	17	1	1157	1	1189	0	1635
	Brahy.D05G0193900	93.478	598	15	11	3544	4129	3241	3826	0	867
	Brahy.D05G0193900	87.965	565	46	14	2931	3490	2677	3224	0	647
	Brahy.D05G0193900	88.073	218	18	3	2610	2821	2464	2679	9.81E-65	252
BdTR6g_Brahy.S09G0150900	Brahy.S09G0150900	100	1482	0	0	1	1482	1	1482	0	2737
	Brahy.D05G0214300	94.97	1491	63	6	1	1482	1	1488	0	2327
BdTR6g_Brahy.S09G0219200	Brahy.S09G0219200	100	3204	0	0	1	3204	1	3204	0	5917
	Brahy.D05G0293600	92.677	3127	125	61	135	3204	1	3080	0	4410

BdTR6g_Brahy.S09G0219300	Brahy.S09G0219300	100	2971	0	0	1	2971	1	2971	0	5487
	Brahy.D05G0293700	91.975	2380	142	26	610	2965	652	3006	0	3291
	Brahy.D05G0293700	84.146	246	19	15	13	247	6	242	1.97E-55	220
BdTR6g_Brahy.S09G0249300	Brahy.S09G0249300	99.934	3047	2	0	1	3047	1	3047	0	5616
	Brahy.D05G0325200	92.208	1540	83	18	1309	2825	1180	2705	0	2145
	Brahy.D05G0325200	89.27	932	61	8	1	897	19	946	0	1131
	Brahy.D05G0325200	90.865	208	14	3	2802	3009	2744	2946	1.53E-71	274
BdTR6g_Brahy.S09G0271600	Brahy.S09G0271600	99.878	4921	6	0	1	4921	1	4921	0	9055
	Brahy.D05G0351400	92.411	3874	179	42	32	3849	39	3853	0	5419
	Brahy.D05G0351400	91.751	994	50	21	3943	4921	3852	4828	0	1352
BdTR6g_Brahy.S10G0006200	Brahy.S10G0006200	99.914	5835	5	0	1	5835	1	5835	0	10748
	Brahy.D04G0007000	93.197	2837	124	21	2760	5548	2879	5694	0	4106
	Brahy.D04G0007000	91.407	1897	119	16	631	2496	631	2514	0	2560
	Brahy.D04G0007000	87.253	455	28	15	68	518	52	480	7.47E-137	492
	Brahy.D04G0007000	85.957	235	14	11	2496	2712	2551	2784	5.00E-59	233
BdTR6g_Brahy.S10G0016800	Brahy.S10G0016800	99.606	6602	26	0	1	6602	1	6602	0	12048
	Brahy.S10G0016800	96.875	32	0	1	5469	5500	5407	5377	1.70E-04	52.8
	Brahy.D04G0020500	94.62	5446	192	49	1	5383	23	5430	0	8340
	Brahy.D04G0020500	93.699	1111	60	7	5495	6602	5427	6530	0	1655
BdTR6g_Brahy.S10G0020700	Brahy.S10G0020700	99.119	7034	62	0	1	7034	1	7034	0	12646
	Brahy.D04G0024900	95.546	1796	71	5	5244	7034	4997	6788	0	2865
	Brahy.D04G0024900	92.704	1302	66	9	3962	5239	3599	4895	0	1851
	Brahy.D04G0024900	87.638	1537	119	29	7	1512	39	1535	0	1720
	Brahy.D04G0024900	91.134	1049	53	21	2327	3365	2432	3450	0	1386
BdTR6g_Brahy.S10G0074500	Brahy.S10G0074500	99.883	2557	3	0	1	2557	1	2557	0	4706
	Brahy.D04G0086700	95.942	2464	92	6	93	2553	13	2471	0	3989
BdTR6g_Brahy.S10G0090600	Brahy.S10G0090600	98.215	4763	85	0	1	4763	1	4763	0	8325

	Brahy.D04G0101500	92.283	1257	76	13	55	1298	13	1261	0	1764
	Brahy.D04G0101500	82.659	1459	160	38	3136	4541	2799	4217	0	1206
	Brahy.D04G0101500	85.836	353	33	10	1908	2251	1549	1893	6.44E-97	359
	Brahy.D04G0101500	87.681	138	10	4	1605	1737	1418	1553	3.26E-35	154
	Brahy.S10G0183100	99.441	4118	23	0	1	4118	1	4118	0	7478
BdTR6g_Brahy.S10G0183100	Brahy.D04G0184800	93.34	3048	126	22	19	3046	1	2991	0	4433
	Brahy.D04G0184800	96.519	747	23	3	3373	4118	3492	4236	0	1232
	Brahy.D01G0027400	99.536	5385	25	0	1	5385	1	5385	0	9817
	Brahy.S02G0402600	94.926	1971	89	10	451	2417	663	2626	0	3086
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0027400	Brahy.S02G0402600	93.41	1654	80	17	3727	5358	4573	6219	0	2423
	Brahy.S02G0402600	90.957	1327	65	21	2428	3731	2893	4187	0	1735
	Brahy.S02G0402600	84.876	443	23	12	18	452	1	407	2.57E-111	407
	Brahy.D01G0058900	99.652	4311	15	0	1	4311	1	4311	0	7880
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0058900	Brahy.S02G0371600	92.798	2888	129	28	1	2817	60	2939	0	4109
	Brahy.S02G0371600	93.891	1244	50	14	3080	4311	3237	4466	0	1853
	Brahy.S02G0371600	85.95	121	6	8	2809	2925	3075	3188	1.08E-24	119
	Brahy.D01G0093600	99.925	4008	3	0	1	4008	1	4008	0	7387
	Brahy.S02G0343400	91.352	1006	50	12	2799	3781	3196	4187	0	1341
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0093600	Brahy.S02G0343400	86.635	838	77	17	1	811	338	1167	0	894
	Brahy.S02G0343400	81.652	1150	120	36	1673	2777	1991	3094	0	870
	Brahy.S02G0343400	84.005	769	83	29	835	1577	1257	2011	0	702
	Brahy.D01G0118500	99.804	19915	39	0	1	19915	1	19915	0	36623
	Brahy.S02G0321500	96.651	5852	184	5	1	5846	27	5872	0	9710
	Brahy.S02G0321500	93.661	5411	230	31	8640	14019	7955	13283	0	7987
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0118500	Brahy.S02G0321500	94.632	1751	65	10	14097	15840	13282	15010	0	2686
	Brahy.S02G0321500	94.82	1699	70	6	6830	8526	6233	7915	0	2634
	Brahy.S02G0321500	88.186	2167	129	50	16681	18757	15869	17998	0	2466
	Brahy.S02G0321500	88.372	817	49	15	15844	16643	15081	15868	0	941
	Brahy.S02G0321500	90.226	266	23	3	5853	6116	5951	6215	7.57E-92	344
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0119000	Brahy.D01G0119000	99.7	9004	27	0	1	9004	1	9004	0	16526

	Brahy.D01G0119100	100	3683	0	0	4723	8405	3683	1	0	6802
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0178700	Brahy.D01G0178700	99.498	1593	8	0	1	1593	1	1593	0	2913
	Brahy.S02G0261500	96.245	1305	46	1	51	1355	1	1302	0	2137
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0185600	Brahy.D01G0185600	99.921	1272	1	0	1	1272	1	1272	0	2344
	Brahy.S02G0254000	94.858	1264	62	1	1	1264	1	1261	0	1971
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0206900	Brahy.D01G0206900	99.776	4009	9	0	1	4009	1	4009	0	7354
	Brahy.S02G0233200	94.578	1457	68	8	1601	3051	2158	3609	0	2242
	Brahy.S02G0233200	88.646	687	32	22	3332	4009	4168	4817	0	795
	Brahy.S02G0233200	87.057	734	37	24	1	686	43	766	0	776
	Brahy.S02G0233200	83.507	673	53	29	727	1366	769	1416	4.94E-162	575
	Brahy.S02G0233200	85.833	360	22	15	2997	3328	3617	3975	7.01E-96	355
	Brahy.S02G0233200	92.308	117	2	2	1287	1402	1693	1803	5.90E-37	159
	Brahy.S02G0233200	80.667	150	13	7	1503	1639	1554	1700	1.01E-19	102
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0255800	Brahy.D01G0255800	100	2981	0	0	1	2981	1	2981	0	5505
	Brahy.S06G0036300	96.292	2454	80	3	383	2833	363	2808	0	4017
	Brahy.S06G0036300	85	360	15	6	3	323	1	360	3.15E-88	329
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0313300	Brahy.D01G0313300	99.765	18762	44	0	1	18762	1	18762	0	34454
	Brahy.D01G0313300	89.429	350	19	10	10956	11296	11296	10956	2.48E-116	425
	Brahy.D01G0313300	98.347	121	0	2	11093	11212	11212	11093	7.55E-52	211
	Brahy.D01G0313300	98.361	61	0	1	11093	11153	11040	11099	3.66E-20	106
	Brahy.D01G0313300	98.305	59	0	1	11040	11097	11093	11151	4.74E-19	102
	Brahy.S06G0089300	93.276	1874	75	17	900	2758	1844	3681	0	2715
	Brahy.S06G0089300	94.987	1596	60	11	11215	12796	10499	12088	0	2486
	Brahy.S06G0089300	91.407	1699	72	22	15236	16887	14181	15852	0	2261
	Brahy.S06G0089300	96.201	1211	41	5	4413	5621	5178	6385	0	1977
	Brahy.S06G0089300	95.059	1093	36	5	17686	18762	16228	17318	0	1703
	Brahy.S06G0089300	92.667	1200	53	10	12787	13982	12110	13278	0	1696
	Brahy.S06G0089300	92.919	1045	47	8	5844	6886	6383	7402	0	1495
	Brahy.S06G0089300	94.764	764	22	8	3477	4231	4315	5069	0	1173
	Brahy.S06G0089300	89.832	895	38	10	2	844	4	897	0	1099

	Brahy.S06G0089300	91.266	790	35	5	7766	8554	7751	8507	0	1046
	Brahy.S06G0089300	88.53	898	52	14	14344	15238	13275	14124	0	1040
	Brahy.S06G0089300	94.7	566	17	6	8557	9121	8797	9350	0	867
	Brahy.S06G0089300	94.954	436	22	0	3006	3441	3692	4127	0	684
	Brahy.S06G0089300	92.605	311	20	3	10789	11099	10079	10386	6.84E-122	444
	Brahy.S06G0089300	95.556	270	6	2	9985	10248	9624	9893	6.89E-117	427
	Brahy.S06G0089300	94.65	243	10	3	6880	7120	7510	7751	9.10E-101	374
	Brahy.S06G0089300	88.77	187	13	4	10484	10665	9898	10081	3.49E-55	222
	Brahy.S06G0089300	92.254	142	10	1	11155	11296	10384	10244	1.63E-48	200
	Brahy.S06G0089300	92.126	127	9	1	10302	10427	7520	7394	7.66E-42	178
	Brahy.S06G0089300	95.327	107	4	1	16885	16991	15900	16005	4.61E-39	169
	Brahy.S06G0089300	89.831	118	12	0	10306	10423	10504	10387	4.64E-34	152
	Brahy.S06G0089300	96	75	2	1	4341	4414	5064	5138	1.31E-24	121
	Brahy.S06G0089300	83.761	117	19	0	4228	4344	1729	1845	7.88E-22	111
	Brahy.S06G0089300	89.412	85	5	3	10956	11037	10582	10499	1.32E-19	104
	Brahy.S06G0089300	81.667	120	18	4	4227	4344	7398	7515	2.21E-17	97.1
	Brahy.S06G0089300	92.188	64	3	2	11093	11156	10328	10389	3.69E-15	89.8
	Brahy.S06G0089300	80	120	20	4	4227	4344	10387	10504	4.77E-14	86.1
	Brahy.D01G0315700	99.809	5244	10	0	1	5244	1	5244	0	9629
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0315700	Brahy.S06G0091800	91.934	4699	258	46	5	4647	11	4644	0	6466
	Brahy.S06G0091800	94.652	617	30	2	4627	5243	4696	5309	0	953
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0342600	Brahy.D01G0342600	95.19	2890	139	0	1	2890	1	2890	0	4817
	Brahy.D01G0369200	99.84	5612	9	0	1	5612	1	5612	0	10314
	Brahy.S06G0145000	91.336	3024	168	38	11	2982	2	2983	0	4047
	Brahy.S06G0145000	95.288	1146	43	7	3260	4397	3841	4983	0	1807
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0369200	Brahy.S06G0145000	92.005	738	51	5	4731	5465	5424	6156	0	1029
	Brahy.S06G0145000	91.429	280	24	0	2982	3261	3516	3795	1.25E-104	385
	Brahy.S06G0145000	91.667	276	22	1	4434	4709	4987	5261	1.62E-103	381
	Brahy.S06G0145000	89.726	146	6	3	5462	5607	6188	6324	2.28E-42	178
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0454600	Brahy.D01G0454600	99.642	1958	7	0	1	1958	1	1958	0	3591

	Brahy.S07G0216000	95.913	1786	73	0	1	1786	234	2019	0	2894
	Brahy.D01G0508600	98.013	7903	157	0	1	7903	1	7903	0	13900
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0508600	Brahy.S07G0167800	93.814	1859	91	12	5998	7842	3410	5258	0	2774
	Brahy.S07G0167800	85.341	1187	124	23	3620	4766	1246	2422	0	1182
	Brahy.S07G0167800	83.354	799	69	21	4819	5586	2423	3188	0	680
	Brahy.S07G0167800	88.73	559	42	14	2206	2748	7	560	0	664
	Brahy.D01G0546700	99.707	13297	39	0	1	13297	1	13297	0	24339
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0546700	Brahy.S07G0131000	94.632	3819	147	23	39	3834	1	3784	0	5864
	Brahy.S07G0131000	89.833	1672	136	20	10191	11848	18421	20072	0	2115
	Brahy.S07G0131000	90.71	1324	94	19	11890	13197	20079	21389	0	1736
	Brahy.S07G0131000	91.179	1247	70	22	7854	9075	14272	15503	0	1657
	Brahy.S07G0131000	84.777	716	64	28	3848	4535	3880	4578	0	676
	Brahy.S07G0131000	87.013	539	48	8	6772	7288	13588	14126	2.11E-165	588
	Brahy.S07G0131000	95.608	296	11	2	9591	9884	16031	16326	6.18E-131	473
	Brahy.S07G0131000	85.246	366	29	9	6216	6565	12280	12636	8.40E-95	353
	Brahy.S07G0131000	84.644	267	25	9	4819	5074	4668	4929	3.15E-64	252
	Brahy.S07G0131000	94.737	152	7	1	9874	10024	16471	16622	3.17E-59	235
	Brahy.S07G0131000	88	175	18	1	5305	5479	10912	11083	8.95E-50	204
	Brahy.S07G0131000	92.063	63	5	0	10127	10189	16609	16671	2.61E-15	89.8
	BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0582800	Brahy.D01G0582800	99.797	4917	10	0	1	4917	1	4917	0
Brahy.S07G0101400		94.185	3130	123	25	169	3283	20	3105	0	4717
Brahy.S07G0101400		91.395	1534	74	21	3411	4907	3318	4830	0	2049
Brahy.S07G0101400		97.059	34	1	0	3349	3382	3283	3316	2.72E-06	58.4
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0595900	Brahy.D01G0595900	99.682	12583	40	0	1	12583	1	12583	0	23015
	Brahy.D01G0595900	85.517	145	17	4	7822	7964	7964	7822	4.02E-33	148
	Brahy.S07G0091300	91.359	3715	227	42	8912	12583	8737	12400	0	4996
	Brahy.S07G0091300	94.956	2617	88	13	1358	3958	1620	4208	0	4061
	Brahy.S07G0091300	91.307	1392	63	18	1	1360	161	1526	0	1847
	Brahy.S07G0091300	89.04	1396	120	23	4101	5477	4201	5582	0	1700
	Brahy.S07G0091300	87.941	1219	80	21	5482	6665	5628	6814	0	1375

	Brahy.S07G0091300	89.767	1075	75	12	6715	7766	6805	7867	0	1343
	Brahy.S07G0091300	89.218	371	21	8	8053	8414	8035	8395	1.27E-122	446
	Brahy.D01G0667700	98.167	4311	79	0	1	4311	1	4311	0	7668
	Brahy.D01G0667700	90.756	238	21	1	1653	1889	1980	2217	3.56E-84	316
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0667700	Brahy.D01G0667700	82.68	306	39	6	1980	2273	1653	1956	1.67E-77	294
	Brahy.S07G0032400	93.961	1689	96	4	90	1772	49	1737	0	2549
	Brahy.S07G0032400	100	51	0	0	4	54	1	51	1.81E-17	95.3
	Brahy.D01G0684700	99.724	1085	3	0	1	1085	1	1085	0	1988
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0684700	Brahy.S07G0018100	89.431	738	70	7	343	1076	361	1094	0	924
	Brahy.S07G0018100	88.384	198	12	5	69	256	126	322	4.24E-58	228
	Brahy.D01G0718400	99.64	3330	12	0	1	3330	1	3330	0	6083
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0718400	Brahy.S06G0164400	95.95	3333	114	8	1	3329	8	3323	0	5387
	Brahy.D01G0742300	99.015	6394	63	0	1	6394	1	6394	0	11561
	Brahy.D01G0742300	95.556	45	1	1	1667	1711	1606	1649	4.55E-10	71.3
	Brahy.D01G0742300	95.556	45	1	1	1606	1649	1667	1711	4.55E-10	71.3
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0742300	Brahy.S06G0203200	93.139	2507	110	24	2879	5356	4038	6511	0	3620
	Brahy.S06G0203200	88.526	1560	98	30	27	1526	1	1539	0	1814
	Brahy.S06G0203200	90.194	775	28	21	1667	2399	2400	3168	0	966
	Brahy.S06G0203200	90.872	493	18	6	2402	2890	3379	3848	3.57E-180	636
	Brahy.S06G0203200	87.234	94	12	0	1516	1609	1870	1963	3.46E-21	108
	Brahy.D01G0836000	99.398	2158	13	0	1	2158	1	2158	0	3914
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0836000	Brahy.S02G0211900	89.341	1107	65	27	742	1832	666	1735	0	1341
	Brahy.S02G0211900	91.449	421	9	5	234	633	202	616	1.24E-155	553
	Brahy.S02G0211900	86.17	188	6	8	48	234	1	169	5.21E-45	185
	Brahy.D01G0870400	99.721	3583	10	0	1	3583	1	3583	0	6562
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0870400	Brahy.S02G0178600	95.271	3595	121	22	1	3581	28	3587	0	5651
	Brahy.D01G0900600	98.639	5732	78	0	1	5732	1	5732	0	10211
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0900600	Brahy.S02G0149500	95.149	3195	125	10	2545	5732	722	3893	0	5014
	Brahy.S02G0149500	95.803	691	24	3	1697	2383	1	690	0	1110
	Brahy.S02G0149500	97.872	47	1	0	2402	2448	680	726	1.88E-13	82.4

BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0916900	Brahy.D01G0916900	99.968	3082	1	0	1	3082	1	3082	0	5686
	Brahy.D01G0916900	97.436	78	2	0	911	988	872	949	2.74E-29	134
	Brahy.D01G0916900	97.436	78	2	0	872	949	911	988	2.74E-29	134
	Brahy.S02G0136700	94.82	2143	81	13	955	3082	1189	3316	0	3315
	Brahy.S02G0136700	89.501	581	49	8	99	669	185	763	0	725
	Brahy.S02G0136700	81.538	195	20	8	725	917	1050	1230	3.52E-33	147
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0944600	Brahy.D01G0944600	99.951	6169	3	0	1	6169	1	6169	0	11376
	Brahy.S02G0114000	90.454	4494	225	91	15	4401	1	4397	0	5734
	Brahy.S02G0114000	92.797	833	37	13	5348	6169	5140	5960	0	1184
	Brahy.S02G0114000	91.105	697	51	5	4418	5107	4449	5141	0	933
	Brahy.S02G0114000	92.982	57	4	0	2889	2945	2931	2987	5.63E-14	84.2
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G0968100	Brahy.D01G0968100	95.658	11331	492	0	1	11331	1	11331	0	19091
	Brahy.S02G0094600	91.886	493	24	8	1	478	492	1	0	676
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G1003300	Brahy.D01G1003300	99.646	4522	16	0	1	4522	1	4522	0	8270
	Brahy.S02G0062700	94.682	3648	158	14	159	3781	191	3827	0	5637
	Brahy.S02G0062700	91.699	518	20	3	3778	4276	3908	4421	0	697
	Brahy.S02G0062700	93.701	127	6	2	47	171	1	127	8.49E-46	189
	Brahy.S02G0062700	89.928	139	2	5	4338	4475	4426	4553	1.11E-39	169
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G1024400	Brahy.D01G1024400	99.265	3812	28	0	1	3812	1	3812	0	6885
	Brahy.S02G0045100	92.285	3111	139	52	739	3769	774	3863	0	4322
	Brahy.S02G0045100	86.909	550	29	19	1	538	6	524	1.31E-162	577
BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G1037300	Brahy.D01G1037300	99.458	8295	45	0	1	8295	1	8295	0	15069
	Brahy.D01G1037300	87.387	111	12	2	5090	5199	5190	5081	1.24E-26	126
	Brahy.S02G0033300	89.519	2347	139	37	1210	3466	952	3281	0	2872
	Brahy.S02G0033300	88.254	945	69	20	7353	8284	6126	7041	0	1092
	Brahy.S02G0033300	86.34	959	60	36	74	991	26	954	0	979
	Brahy.S02G0033300	92.013	626	37	10	4473	5093	3287	3904	0	867
	Brahy.S02G0033300	91.852	270	18	4	5187	5454	3903	4170	4.02E-101	374
	Brahy.S02G0033300	81.548	336	50	7	5570	5899	5465	5136	7.01E-69	267
Brahy.S02G0033300	91.228	57	5	0	5454	5510	4190	4246	3.53E-12	78.7	

BdTR6g_Brahy.D01G1044900	Brahy.D01G1044900	99.416	4281	25	0	1	4281	1	4281	0	7768
	Brahy.S02G0025500	92.158	1951	90	23	2159	4057	2307	4246	0	2697
	Brahy.S02G0025500	92.033	1318	82	13	874	2173	980	2292	0	1831
	Brahy.S02G0025500	82.292	768	76	38	34	772	11	747	1.45E-172	610
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0046100	Brahy.D02G0046100	99.041	3545	34	0	1	3545	1	3545	0	6375
	Brahy.S01G0399900	90.864	3404	186	65	167	3531	285	3602	0	4462
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0054700	Brahy.D02G0054700	99.28	7227	52	0	1	7227	1	7227	0	13058
	Brahy.S01G0392000	91.543	2637	131	36	1973	4552	2060	4661	0	3550
	Brahy.S01G0392000	90.398	2083	122	37	7	2040	26	2079	0	2667
	Brahy.S01G0392000	91.594	1142	62	11	6058	7176	6137	7267	0	1546
	Brahy.S01G0392000	89.552	737	38	11	4969	5671	5007	5738	0	898
	Brahy.S01G0392000	92.857	350	24	1	5703	6052	5737	6085	3.31E-141	507
	Brahy.S01G0392000	93.215	339	12	4	4648	4985	4662	4990	1.20E-135	488
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0070200	Brahy.D02G0070200	99.244	5289	40	0	1	5289	1	5289	0	9546
	Brahy.S01G0377600	96.801	2157	69	0	3129	5285	3368	5524	0	3602
	Brahy.S01G0377600	93.546	1255	48	13	1893	3130	2093	3331	0	1838
	Brahy.S01G0377600	88.713	948	65	24	1	942	5	916	0	1120
	Brahy.S01G0377600	92.943	581	26	11	956	1527	966	1540	0	832
	Brahy.S01G0377600	92.09	354	21	3	1540	1891	1607	1955	6.77E-137	492
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0086500	Brahy.D02G0086500	99.637	5790	21	0	1	5790	1	5790	0	10576
	Brahy.S01G0362900	90.995	3176	192	35	2056	5171	2169	5310	0	4194
	Brahy.S01G0362900	85.789	1154	84	32	304	1407	455	1578	0	1149
	Brahy.S01G0362900	89.331	628	50	9	5176	5790	5431	6054	0	773
	Brahy.S01G0362900	89.535	602	42	11	1434	2020	1578	2173	0	743
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0143400	Brahy.D02G0143400	99.534	8149	38	0	1	8149	1	8149	0	14838
	Brahy.S01G0310200	91.12	4989	287	62	1816	6716	1775	6695	0	6615
	Brahy.S01G0310200	89.486	1322	87	30	6757	8055	6705	7997	0	1624
	Brahy.S01G0310200	84.935	1228	103	32	19	1226	144	1309	0	1168
	Brahy.S01G0310200	93.548	186	11	1	1222	1406	1390	1575	1.14E-71	276
	Brahy.S01G0310200	76.336	524	68	37	1220	1733	1827	2304	9.04E-58	230

	Brahy.S01G0310200	79.683	315	43	12	1733	2036	1265	1569	4.23E-51	207	
	Brahy.S01G0310200	84.615	130	12	7	1266	1393	1199	1322	1.58E-25	122	
	Brahy.S01G0310200	78.689	183	25	3	1027	1196	1775	1956	1.23E-21	110	
	Brahy.D02G0284700	99.736	11000	29	0	1	11000	1	11000	0	20153	
	Brahy.D02G0284700	100	28	0	0	5613	5640	5563	5590	2.84E-04	52.8	
	Brahy.D02G0284700	100	28	0	0	5563	5590	5613	5640	2.84E-04	52.8	
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0284700	Brahy.S08G0071600	91.587	5349	305	72	1	5322	38	5268	0	7251	
	Brahy.S08G0071600	93.566	2611	106	19	6603	9179	7578	10160	0	3834	
	Brahy.S08G0071600	92.057	1750	92	24	9293	10999	10334	12079	0	2418	
	Brahy.S08G0071600	92.29	428	22	5	5688	6114	6625	7042	2.91E-168	597	
	Brahy.S08G0071600	91.415	431	24	3	6111	6537	7154	7575	1.05E-162	579	
	Brahy.S08G0071600	93.038	158	6	2	5436	5593	5267	5419	1.58E-56	226	
	Brahy.S08G0071600	95.968	124	5	0	9164	9287	10172	10295	2.66E-49	202	
		Brahy.D02G0286800	99.586	7007	29	0	1	7007	1	7007	0	12785
		Brahy.S08G0074100	87.74	2814	180	83	181	2934	1	2709	0	3133
	Brahy.S08G0074100	93.646	1259	65	11	5021	6268	4717	5971	0	1868	
	Brahy.S08G0074100	91.029	680	36	12	6336	6999	6006	6676	0	894	
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0286800	Brahy.S08G0074100	93.603	594	25	7	3012	3601	2728	3312	0	874	
	Brahy.S08G0074100	91.171	589	32	10	3608	4187	3402	3979	0	782	
	Brahy.S08G0074100	94.177	395	15	5	4643	5033	4299	4689	6.65E-168	595	
	Brahy.S08G0074100	83.577	274	31	11	4112	4377	3932	4199	2.77E-62	244	
	Brahy.S08G0074100	92.727	110	8	0	4493	4602	4197	4306	1.03E-36	159	
		Brahy.D02G0366500	99.816	2169	4	0	1	2169	1	2169	0	3984
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0366500	Brahy.S08G0137700	93.411	2140	110	15	1	2117	5	2136	0	3142	
	Brahy.D02G0383700	99.711	9329	27	0	1	9329	1	9329	0	17078	
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0383700	Brahy.S08G0150400	93.97	3184	150	20	340	3491	208	3381	0	4778	
	Brahy.S08G0150400	95.748	2846	95	12	4650	7488	4811	7637	0	4562	
	Brahy.S08G0150400	94.49	1815	59	19	7529	9327	7641	9430	0	2760	
	Brahy.S08G0150400	95.256	801	27	8	3565	4364	3622	4412	0	1258	
	Brahy.S08G0150400	93.75	176	11	0	4362	4537	4637	4812	2.84E-68	265	

BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0521500	Brahy.D02G0521500	99.927	4130	3	0	1	4130	1	4130	0	7611
	Brahy.S08G0261500	92.076	2953	175	28	516	3460	234	3135	0	4102
	Brahy.S08G0261500	92.267	569	35	6	3460	4028	3199	3758	0	798
	Brahy.S08G0261500	90.045	221	13	3	254	468	8	225	1.61E-72	278
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0543900	Brahy.D02G0543900	99.763	6742	16	0	1	6742	1	6742	0	12381
	Brahy.S01G0435200	89.367	3066	192	52	1505	4488	1198	4211	0	3733
	Brahy.S01G0435200	90.341	1056	65	18	420	1464	90	1119	0	1351
	Brahy.S01G0435200	87.324	1136	92	24	4485	5573	5206	6336	0	1271
	Brahy.S01G0435200	91.087	819	48	5	5906	6722	6781	7576	0	1085
	Brahy.S01G0435200	88.824	340	25	7	5570	5904	6417	6748	1.16E-110	405
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0552200	Brahy.D02G0552200	99.883	5125	6	0	1	5125	1	5125	0	9431
	Brahy.S01G0443600	97.189	2917	71	8	2208	5122	1694	4601	0	4922
	Brahy.S01G0443600	94.536	1647	67	13	1	1632	62	1700	0	2521
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0573700	Brahy.D02G0573700	99.577	5435	23	0	1	5435	1	5435	0	9915
	Brahy.S01G0240300	90.637	3108	182	46	4	3027	1	3083	0	4026
	Brahy.S01G0240300	92.265	1073	42	27	3552	4588	3927	4994	0	1483
	Brahy.S01G0240300	87.416	890	39	25	4591	5428	5099	5967	0	955
	Brahy.S01G0240300	92.872	477	20	7	3086	3549	3078	3553	0	680
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0588300	Brahy.D02G0588300	99.94	3329	2	0	1	3329	1	3329	0	6137
	Brahy.D02G0588300	88.506	87	4	1	318	404	240	320	3.01E-19	100
	Brahy.D02G0588300	88.506	87	4	1	240	320	318	404	3.01E-19	100
	Brahy.D02G0588300	89.706	68	7	0	413	480	380	447	2.34E-15	87.9
	Brahy.S01G0226800	94.973	1830	69	13	1498	3315	1491	3309	0	2848
	Brahy.S01G0226800	88.061	1449	89	44	13	1431	5	1399	0	1640
	Brahy.S01G0226800	90.805	87	2	1	318	404	231	311	1.39E-22	111
	Brahy.S01G0226800	94.118	68	4	0	380	447	404	471	2.32E-20	104
	Brahy.S01G0226800	91.176	68	6	0	413	480	371	438	5.03E-17	93.5
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0613200	Brahy.D02G0613200	99.883	12835	15	0	1	12835	1	12835	0	23619
	Brahy.S01G0205100	90.494	3019	184	46	42	3017	1	2959	0	3890
	Brahy.S01G0205100	89.95	1791	116	30	8878	10625	5453	7222	0	2252

	Brahy.S01G0205100	91.475	1478	84	16	10747	12188	7207	8678	0	1993
	Brahy.S01G0205100	93.892	966	46	5	4320	5284	2945	3898	0	1445
	Brahy.S01G0205100	88.4	931	61	23	6846	7735	4318	5242	0	1077
	Brahy.S01G0205100	93.594	640	31	3	12187	12817	8749	9387	0	946
	Brahy.S01G0205100	92.641	231	11	5	8212	8439	5228	5455	4.91E-87	327
	Brahy.S01G0205100	88.43	242	25	3	5290	5528	3938	4179	2.32E-75	289
	Brahy.D02G0622400	99.904	4184	4	0	1	4184	1	4184	0	7705
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0622400	Brahy.S01G0197400	90.708	1765	94	31	1057	2807	1075	2783	0	2287
	Brahy.S01G0197400	93.367	1402	55	13	2796	4183	2956	4333	0	2039
	Brahy.S01G0197400	93.678	949	43	7	6	949	3	939	0	1404
	Brahy.S01G0197400	96	50	2	0	961	1010	1024	1073	1.37E-13	82.4
	Brahy.D02G0631400	99.592	2698	11	0	1	2698	1	2698	0	4922
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0631400	Brahy.S01G0188300	91.173	2481	155	26	11	2479	13	2441	0	3310
	Brahy.D02G0639700	99.509	6920	34	0	1	6920	1	6920	0	12608
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0639700	Brahy.S01G0180900	94.622	3682	160	13	3144	6807	2844	6505	0	5668
	Brahy.S01G0180900	90.249	1046	65	9	2107	3140	1728	2748	0	1332
	Brahy.S01G0180900	93.444	900	36	9	424	1314	52	937	0	1314
	Brahy.S01G0180900	93.159	687	32	6	1316	1990	1041	1724	0	994
	Brahy.D02G0655700	99.609	2814	11	0	1	2814	1	2814	0	5136
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0655700	Brahy.S01G0165500	93.05	1482	84	6	1333	2813	860	2323	0	2148
	Brahy.S01G0165500	87.817	829	78	9	872	1677	505	1333	0	950
	Brahy.S01G0165500	87.81	525	21	17	190	698	1	498	3.46E-162	575
	Brahy.S01G0165500	80.303	264	46	2	1276	1533	1070	1333	1.13E-47	195
	Brahy.S01G0165500	89.344	122	12	1	1274	1394	1212	1333	6.91E-35	152
	Brahy.D02G0710800	99.737	5704	15	0	1	5704	1	5704	0	10471
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0710800	Brahy.D02G0710800	91.667	60	4	1	2610	2669	2740	2798	1.87E-13	82.4
	Brahy.D02G0710800	83.871	93	6	2	2740	2831	2610	2694	6.73E-13	80.5
	Brahy.S01G0115100	95.366	1942	57	11	3400	5329	3145	5065	0	3057
	Brahy.S01G0115100	89.38	2307	165	32	996	3285	903	3146	0	2850
	Brahy.S01G0115100	89.087	898	59	20	11	883	18	901	0	1079

	Brahy.S01G0115100	94.613	297	12	3	5267	5563	5123	5415	2.66E-126	457
	Brahy.S01G0115100	96.825	63	2	0	5267	5329	5063	5125	1.11E-20	106
	Brahy.S01G0115100	82.927	123	11	3	2711	2831	2458	2572	1.44E-19	102
	Brahy.S01G0115100	81.301	123	10	3	2579	2693	2590	2707	4.02E-15	87.9
	Brahy.D02G0736600	99.504	5641	28	0	1	5641	1	5641	0	10262
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0736600	Brahy.S01G0092300	87.292	2770	203	64	38	2722	2269	4974	0	3027
	Brahy.S01G0092300	91.116	1756	127	15	3885	5630	5193	6929	0	2351
	Brahy.D02G0769400	99.697	2644	8	0	1	2644	1	2644	0	4839
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0769400	Brahy.S01G0063200	94.144	2647	139	7	1	2643	328	2962	0	4015
	Brahy.D02G0772900	99.742	6579	17	0	1	6579	1	6579	0	12056
	Brahy.S01G0059600	92.603	1825	94	24	2	1788	25	1846	0	2584
	Brahy.S01G0059600	92.581	1658	79	25	2796	4424	3137	4779	0	2340
	Brahy.S01G0059600	93.236	1375	63	13	5218	6579	5770	7127	0	1997
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0772900	Brahy.S01G0059600	95.196	895	40	3	1797	2688	1926	2820	0	1411
	Brahy.S01G0059600	93.488	430	26	2	4774	5203	5208	5635	1.02E-180	638
	Brahy.S01G0059600	91.9	321	18	2	4454	4766	4777	5097	8.61E-122	442
	Brahy.S01G0059600	93.617	94	6	0	2694	2787	2946	3039	3.52E-31	141
	Brahy.D02G0800900	99.319	8670	59	0	1	8670	1	8670	0	15684
	Brahy.S01G0034000	91.254	4528	305	46	4147	8652	4091	8549	0	6083
	Brahy.S01G0034000	90.776	1160	62	15	2698	3841	2825	3955	0	1507
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0800900	Brahy.S01G0034000	93.197	1029	59	4	1598	2625	1791	2809	0	1502
	Brahy.S01G0034000	89.585	1181	81	17	5	1156	7	1174	0	1461
	Brahy.S01G0034000	91.268	481	25	5	1162	1632	1316	1789	0	640
	Brahy.D02G0802300	99.861	1443	2	0	1	1443	1	1443	0	2654
BdTR6g_Brahy.D02G0802300	Brahy.S01G0032700	87.51	1249	107	33	13	1245	1	1216	0	1397
	Brahy.S01G0032700	78.977	176	21	9	1270	1439	1269	1434	2.77E-21	106
	Brahy.D03G0016400	99.571	3726	16	0	1	3726	1	3726	0	6798
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0016400	Brahy.S04G0354200	85.778	3340	292	100	378	3636	407	3644	0	3373
	Brahy.S04G0354200	85.564	381	28	19	6	377	1	363	1.80E-101	374
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0036300	Brahy.D03G0036300	99.642	3632	13	0	1	3632	1	3632	0	6636

	Brahy.S04G0336200	84.155	1603	152	46	745	2317	732	2262	0	1459
	Brahy.S04G0336200	92.273	660	37	8	67	719	1	653	0	924
	Brahy.S04G0336200	85.469	640	55	19	3006	3623	2931	3554	2.62E-179	632
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0085600	Brahy.D03G0085600	99.431	3868	22	0	1	3868	1	3868	0	7022
	Brahy.S04G0293400	91.868	910	47	17	2944	3841	3406	4300	0	1245
	Brahy.S04G0293400	84.825	1140	79	49	1640	2734	1892	2982	0	1061
	Brahy.S04G0293400	88.152	211	7	13	1	199	73	277	9.19E-60	235
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0279400	Brahy.D03G0279400	98.989	3165	32	0	1	3165	1	3165	0	5668
	Brahy.S03G0077300	87.174	1536	139	33	1445	2949	1288	2796	0	1692
	Brahy.S03G0077300	82.505	463	36	20	75	521	1	434	9.18E-99	364
	Brahy.S03G0077300	78.66	567	51	36	740	1248	570	1124	3.37E-83	313
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0378300	Brahy.D03G0378300	99.869	6850	9	0	1	6850	1	6850	0	12600
	Brahy.S03G0161800	92.3	1909	108	19	2217	4096	2124	4022	0	2675
	Brahy.S03G0161800	92.486	1770	67	32	4097	5814	4169	5924	0	2471
	Brahy.S03G0161800	92.422	1610	97	15	8	1601	1	1601	0	2274
	Brahy.S03G0161800	92.344	1045	55	11	5811	6834	7566	8606	0	1463
	Brahy.S03G0161800	84.035	451	41	21	1615	2062	1661	2083	1.18E-110	405
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0408900	Brahy.D03G0408900	99.839	1869	3	0	1	1869	1	1869	0	3435
	Brahy.S03G0185400	91.625	1003	67	6	655	1648	707	1701	0	1371
	Brahy.S03G0185400	94.175	618	21	7	1	603	16	633	0	928
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0423800	Brahy.D03G0423800	99.432	5102	29	0	1	5102	1	5102	0	9262
	Brahy.S03G0197200	91.367	2641	142	40	1	2575	45	2665	0	3535
	Brahy.S03G0197200	92.093	1075	65	9	2613	3678	2916	3979	0	1496
	Brahy.S03G0197200	88.411	535	31	8	4572	5102	5945	6452	3.71E-174	616
	Brahy.S03G0197200	91.566	249	15	4	3775	4023	4063	4305	9.00E-91	339
	Brahy.S03G0197200	100	37	0	0	2578	2614	2712	2748	1.30E-09	69.4
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0552100	Brahy.D03G0552100	99.945	1816	1	0	1	1816	1	1816	0	3349
	Brahy.S03G0304000	87.681	1591	109	45	37	1601	15	1544	0	1772
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0559500	Brahy.D03G0559500	99.221	2696	21	0	1	2696	1	2696	0	4865
	Brahy.S03G0310200	90.918	1057	45	21	1645	2696	1638	2648	0	1373

	Brahy.S03G0310200	88.336	763	60	17	2	751	11	757	0	889
	Brahy.D03G0590300	97.723	7817	178	0	1	7817	1	7817	0	13620
	Brahy.S04G0219600	92.614	1354	53	18	6504	7817	5515	6861	0	1903
	Brahy.S04G0219600	89.978	1377	74	18	2257	3600	10	1355	0	1720
	Brahy.S04G0219600	93.573	529	19	6	4400	4921	2035	2555	0	774
	Brahy.S04G0219600	88.983	590	38	10	5894	6471	4818	5392	0	704
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0590300	Brahy.S04G0219600	93.407	364	18	1	3945	4308	1679	2036	1.64E-149	534
	Brahy.S04G0219600	90.453	419	18	4	4918	5314	2578	2996	5.90E-149	532
	Brahy.S04G0219600	92.258	310	21	3	3638	3947	1343	1649	4.76E-120	436
	Brahy.S04G0219600	88.655	238	27	0	5618	5855	4580	4817	3.92E-76	291
	Brahy.S04G0219600	100	36	0	0	6470	6505	5425	5460	7.19E-09	67.6
	Brahy.S04G0219600	100	30	0	0	3610	3639	1424	1453	1.56E-05	56.5
	Brahy.D03G0616000	97.549	2448	60	0	1	2448	1	2448	0	4283
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0616000	Brahy.S04G0199400	96.94	1242	38	0	98	1339	1	1242	0	2084
	Brahy.D03G0675700	99.362	9089	58	0	1	9089	1	9089	0	16395
	Brahy.S04G0144200	94.061	2172	102	14	2369	4521	2477	4640	0	3271
	Brahy.S04G0144200	95.63	1556	53	9	7533	9084	8747	10291	0	2484
	Brahy.S04G0144200	91.762	1663	70	30	758	2369	656	2302	0	2250
	Brahy.S04G0144200	92.793	999	55	13	4608	5601	4767	5753	0	1430
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0675700	Brahy.S04G0144200	93.528	927	45	8	5967	6887	6419	7336	0	1365
	Brahy.S04G0144200	96.753	462	15	0	24	485	1	462	0	771
	Brahy.S04G0144200	87.734	587	39	20	6954	7530	7433	7996	0	654
	Brahy.S04G0144200	88.722	266	13	2	5739	5988	6147	6411	1.26E-81	309
	Brahy.S04G0144200	92.073	164	12	1	483	645	495	658	1.01E-57	230
	Brahy.D03G0678900	99.962	2650	1	0	1	2650	1	2650	0	4889
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0678900	Brahy.S07G0014900	91.704	1338	88	13	1335	2650	464	1800	0	1834
	Brahy.D03G0740300	99.948	3874	2	0	1	3874	1	3874	0	7143
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0740300	Brahy.D03G0740300	100	1046	0	0	3922	4967	3922	4967	0	1932
	Brahy.S04G0085200	96.473	1616	49	6	1924	3538	2313	3921	0	2662
	Brahy.S04G0085200	95.499	1444	54	8	490	1927	846	2284	0	2296

	Brahy.S04G0085200	93.391	1044	29	15	3922	4931	4432	5469	0	1509
	Brahy.S04G0085200	96.988	498	13	2	1	496	157	654	0	835
	Brahy.S04G0085200	97.688	173	4	0	3625	3797	4156	4328	1.49E-78	298
	Brahy.S04G0085200	90.816	98	1	3	3537	3626	3978	4075	2.67E-26	124
	Brahy.D03G0765500	99.599	4990	20	0	1	4990	1	4990	0	9105
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0765500	Brahy.S04G0061800	93.459	4097	150	52	110	4154	6	4036	0	5973
	Brahy.S04G0061800	92.192	730	30	10	4248	4977	4035	4737	0	1007
	Brahy.D03G0767300	99.875	2399	3	0	1	2399	1	2399	0	4414
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0767300	Brahy.S04G0060600	90.496	2178	126	37	137	2288	1751	3873	0	2800
	Brahy.S04G0060600	92.308	117	8	1	1	117	1589	1704	7.55E-39	165
	Brahy.D03G0771700	99.935	6107	4	0	1	6107	1	6107	0	11256
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0771700	Brahy.S04G0056300	92.629	2415	135	21	2893	5288	2839	5229	0	3434
	Brahy.S04G0056300	89.154	1678	130	27	1	1663	11	1651	0	2043
	Brahy.S04G0056300	92.871	1010	43	10	1789	2788	1665	2655	0	1439
	Brahy.S04G0056300	93.084	723	35	8	5397	6107	5242	5961	0	1044
	Brahy.S04G0056300	93.396	106	7	0	2786	2891	2691	2796	3.24E-36	158
	Brahy.D03G0787300	99.886	6127	7	0	1	6127	1	6127	0	11276
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0787300	Brahy.S04G0041700	89.874	1985	119	42	4169	6127	4261	6189	0	2477
	Brahy.S04G0041700	94.251	1461	57	10	2610	4051	2811	4263	0	2207
	Brahy.S04G0041700	91.083	1200	55	23	999	2190	1141	2296	0	1576
	Brahy.S04G0041700	85.652	683	47	23	1	668	133	779	0	671
	Brahy.S04G0041700	91.139	474	40	2	2149	2621	2291	2763	0	641
	Brahy.S04G0041700	89.394	66	5	2	837	901	1029	1093	2.01E-13	82.4
	Brahy.D03G0790200	99.442	5200	29	0	1	5200	1	5200	0	9474
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0790200	Brahy.S04G0039300	88.737	2264	175	40	481	2714	645	2858	0	2695
	Brahy.S04G0039300	93.077	650	29	2	4254	4900	4304	4940	0	942
	Brahy.S04G0039300	84.729	406	40	15	14	415	30	417	3.23E-105	387
	Brahy.D03G0793100	99.222	5398	42	0	1	5398	1	5398	0	9736
BdTR6g_Brahy.D03G0793100	Brahy.S04G0036700	91.371	4346	244	54	24	4293	47	4337	0	5827
	Brahy.S04G0036700	83.842	557	47	20	4849	5397	4561	5082	2.48E-136	490

	Brahy.S04G0036700	89.333	225	16	4	4383	4599	4342	4566	7.57E-72	276
BdTR6g_Brahy.D04G0003700	Brahy.D04G0003700	99.592	1714	7	0	1	1714	1	1714	0	3127
	Brahy.S10G0003900	94.029	1591	90	3	90	1679	1587	1	0	2407
	Brahy.D04G0029300	99.812	7990	15	0	1	7990	1	7990	0	14672
BdTR6g_Brahy.D04G0029300	Brahy.S10G0023800	96.009	5312	184	17	2471	7776	2730	8019	0	8610
	Brahy.S10G0023800	91.854	1424	73	17	1102	2484	1078	2499	0	1947
	Brahy.S10G0023800	87.417	1057	44	29	5	1028	10	1010	0	1133
	Brahy.D04G0080500	98.564	2646	38	0	1	2646	1	2646	0	4695
BdTR6g_Brahy.D04G0080500	Brahy.S10G0069600	96.441	2501	78	7	5	2495	1	2500	0	4128
	Brahy.D04G0098100	98.578	5203	74	0	1	5203	1	5203	0	9199
BdTR6g_Brahy.D04G0098100	Brahy.D04G0098100	77.895	380	72	9	2882	3255	3254	2881	7.45E-57	226
	Brahy.S10G0086400	94.678	2856	113	12	1	2850	1574	4396	0	4396
	Brahy.S10G0086400	94.872	1326	53	9	3887	5203	5676	6995	0	2058
	Brahy.S10G0086400	95.717	607	18	5	3286	3887	4399	5002	0	970
	Brahy.D04G0123200	99.855	3460	5	0	1	3460	1	3460	0	6362
BdTR6g_Brahy.D04G0123200	Brahy.D04G0123200	100	99	0	0	1519	1617	1414	1512	3.02E-44	183
	Brahy.D04G0123200	100	99	0	0	1414	1512	1519	1617	3.02E-44	183
	Brahy.S10G0110200	86.944	1080	80	17	1614	2633	1515	2593	0	1157
	Brahy.S10G0110200	93.122	567	29	2	2718	3282	2641	3199	0	822
	Brahy.S10G0110200	91.954	522	24	7	190	705	168	677	0	715
	Brahy.D04G0274300	99.561	12526	55	0	1	12526	1	12526	0	22842
BdTR6g_Brahy.D04G0274300	Brahy.D04G0274300	92.208	77	6	0	9696	9772	9591	9667	1.89E-21	110
	Brahy.S05G0075500	92.708	4251	233	37	808	5034	682	4879	0	6061
	Brahy.S05G0075500	90.957	752	43	7	10348	11080	4879	5624	0	989
	Brahy.S05G0075500	89.806	618	45	9	87	689	68	682	0	776
	Brahy.S05G0075500	87.187	679	43	20	11707	12368	5741	6392	0	732
	Brahy.D04G0425900	99.901	2020	2	0	1	2020	1	2020	0	3720
BdTR6g_Brahy.D04G0425900	Brahy.S05G0127900	92.574	2020	82	24	1	2011	8	1968	0	2837
	Brahy.D04G0428900	99.267	3547	26	0	1	3547	1	3547	0	6407
BdTR6g_Brahy.D04G0428900	Brahy.S05G0130500	94.684	2596	107	17	633	3220	838	3410	0	4000

	Brahy.S05G0130500	85.938	320	17	13	22	325	202	509	2.92E-84	316
	Brahy.S05G0130500	83.256	215	9	2	3284	3479	3412	3618	6.70E-41	172
	Brahy.D04G0445700	99.765	4689	11	0	1	4689	1	4689	0	8599
	Brahy.D04G0445700	100	32	0	0	1768	1799	2140	2109	7.20E-07	60.2
BdTR6g_Brahy.D04G0445700	Brahy.S05G0146300	93.926	1745	82	14	2406	4132	3033	4771	0	2614
	Brahy.S05G0146300	91.826	942	50	11	1	932	33	957	0	1288
	Brahy.S05G0146300	97.308	520	13	1	4167	4686	4887	5405	0	881
	Brahy.S05G0146300	90.937	651	50	6	1119	1766	2099	2743	0	867
	Brahy.S05G0146300	85.778	225	21	4	2141	2363	2743	2958	1.87E-57	228
	Brahy.D04G0448500	99.033	5171	50	0	1	5171	1	5171	0	9315
BdTR6g_Brahy.D04G0448500	Brahy.D04G0447600	96.597	5202	127	23	3	5171	33	5217	0	8623
	Brahy.D04G0567900	99.762	2939	7	0	1	2939	1	2939	0	5391
BdTR6g_Brahy.D04G0567900	Brahy.S05G0253900	90.535	2261	148	36	724	2938	834	3074	0	2931
	Brahy.S05G0253900	85.106	94	10	3	466	555	419	512	4.44E-17	93.5
	Brahy.D04G0607100	99.464	7092	38	0	1	7092	1	7092	0	12936
BdTR6g_Brahy.D04G0607100	Brahy.S05G0291000	97.354	2154	57	0	1078	3231	1324	3477	0	3663
	Brahy.S05G0291000	94.022	1656	65	8	3583	5221	4123	5761	0	2481
	Brahy.S05G0291000	90.536	560	32	4	530	1088	573	1112	0	721
	Brahy.S05G0291000	92.878	337	17	3	3257	3592	3560	3890	5.47E-134	483
	Brahy.D05G0131500	99.772	9227	21	0	1	9227	1	9227	0	16923
BdTR6g_Brahy.D05G0131500	Brahy.D05G0131500	88.112	143	16	1	5473	5615	5617	5758	2.26E-39	169
	Brahy.S09G0085500	90.917	3578	228	42	5703	9227	5117	8650	0	4717
	Brahy.S09G0085500	86.182	2381	208	75	3251	5558	2860	5192	0	2462
	Brahy.S09G0085500	90.047	1688	118	25	1575	3240	1228	2887	0	2141
	Brahy.S09G0085500	91.05	581	40	10	969	1541	649	1225	0	774
	Brahy.S09G0085500	83.146	356	24	25	1	354	328	649	1.29E-76	292
	Brahy.D05G0166000	99.752	9696	24	0	1	9696	1	9696	0	17791
BdTR6g_Brahy.D05G0166000	Brahy.S09G0113600	89.2	3000	235	41	917	3878	945	3893	0	3663
	Brahy.S09G0113600	89.958	2828	183	52	4743	7523	4661	7434	0	3555
	Brahy.S09G0113600	89.972	1755	144	21	7573	9308	7470	9211	0	2237

	Brahy.S09G0113600	92.899	859	37	9	33	874	84	935	0	1227	
	Brahy.S09G0113600	93.72	621	29	7	4130	4743	3929	4546	0	922	
	Brahy.S09G0113600	87.622	307	36	2	9341	9646	9207	9512	1.70E-95	355	
	Brahy.D05G0200800	99.971	7011	2	0	1	7011	1	7011	0	12936	
	Brahy.D05G0200800	85.787	197	18	4	5215	5404	4948	5141	6.10E-49	200	
	Brahy.D05G0200800	85.787	197	18	4	4948	5141	5215	5404	6.10E-49	200	
	Brahy.D05G0200800	100	30	0	0	3410	3439	3380	3409	1.40E-05	56.5	
	Brahy.D05G0200800	100	30	0	0	3380	3409	3410	3439	1.40E-05	56.5	
BdTR6g_Brahy.D05G0200800	Brahy.S09G0141800	87.161	2804	206	75	2116	4854	2268	4982	0	3042	
	Brahy.S09G0141800	85.417	1296	84	30	1	1251	45	1280	0	1249	
	Brahy.S09G0141800	83.65	685	72	12	1453	2116	1558	2223	8.55E-172	608	
	Brahy.S09G0141800	89.862	434	32	8	6388	6810	6130	6562	1.89E-153	547	
	Brahy.S09G0141800	84.828	435	41	13	5900	6319	5706	6130	2.00E-113	414	
	Brahy.S09G0141800	84	425	27	14	5456	5863	5240	5640	4.39E-100	370	
	Brahy.S09G0141800	91.324	219	19	0	5183	5401	4947	5165	5.84E-79	300	
	Brahy.S09G0141800	83.168	202	24	5	4948	5146	4979	5173	1.03E-41	176	
		Brahy.D05G0202000	100	8809	0	0	1	8809	1	8809	0	16268
	BdTR6g_Brahy.D05G0202000	Brahy.S09G0142600	94.291	2680	97	20	4045	6709	4434	7072	0	4050
Brahy.S09G0142600		91.703	2037	84	25	1492	3493	1280	3266	0	2747	
Brahy.S09G0142600		91.211	1536	87	25	6960	8482	8125	9625	0	2045	
Brahy.S09G0142600		91.224	980	63	15	72	1037	1	971	0	1312	
Brahy.S09G0142600		94.753	324	15	1	1057	1378	958	1281	5.21E-140	503	
Brahy.S09G0142600		94.198	293	13	2	3697	3989	3660	3948	3.21E-122	444	
Brahy.S09G0142600		97.814	183	4	0	6705	6887	7943	8125	7.29E-84	316	
Brahy.S09G0142600		96	175	4	3	3494	3666	3489	3662	2.66E-73	281	
Brahy.S09G0142600		93.939	132	6	1	8481	8612	9739	9868	2.76E-48	198	
Brahy.S09G0142600		94.355	124	6	1	1370	1493	3329	3451	1.66E-45	189	
Brahy.S09G0142600	90.476	63	5	1	3988	4050	4042	4103	2.90E-13	82.4		
BdTR6g_Brahy.D05G0219100	Brahy.D05G0219100	99.831	11267	19	0	1	11267	1	11267	0	20731	
	Brahy.S09G0155100	95.086	3683	156	12	1	3679	31	3692	0	5775	

	Brahy.S09G0155100	94.366	1491	59	10	7541	9023	8049	9522	0	2265
	Brahy.S09G0155100	93.691	1268	59	12	4334	5585	4748	6010	0	1879
	Brahy.S09G0155100	93.421	988	45	11	6576	7544	6961	7947	0	1447
	Brahy.S09G0155100	88.833	797	43	22	9301	10084	12123	12886	0	937
	Brahy.S09G0155100	96.591	264	9	0	10125	10388	12884	13147	1.91E-120	438
	Brahy.S09G0155100	90.578	329	27	4	6258	6583	6448	6775	8.88E-119	433
	Brahy.S09G0155100	94.074	270	13	1	5590	5856	6046	6315	5.38E-111	407
	Brahy.S09G0155100	94.323	229	6	5	3706	3932	3754	3977	4.28E-92	344
	Brahy.S09G0155100	86.711	301	20	8	9022	9302	9556	9856	9.33E-84	316
	Brahy.S09G0155100	95.238	105	5	0	4248	4352	3974	4078	9.95E-39	167
BdTR6g_Brahy.D05G0219600	Brahy.D05G0219600	100	2692	0	0	1	2692	1	2692	0	4972
	Brahy.S09G0156000	90.825	2692	171	29	1	2674	28	2661	0	3533
BdTR6g_Brahy.D05G0225700	Brahy.D05G0225700	99.956	4544	2	0	1	4544	1	4544	0	8381
	Brahy.D05G0225700	78.226	124	15	7	2783	2900	2900	2783	1.16E-09	69.4
	Brahy.S09G0160300	88.252	2894	156	69	18	2781	1	2840	0	3291
	Brahy.S09G0160300	88.072	1333	89	36	3277	4544	3281	4608	0	1517
BdTR6g_Brahy.D05G0280000	Brahy.D05G0280000	99.227	7500	58	0	1	7500	1	7500	0	13603
	Brahy.S09G0205800	91.169	3182	194	44	4348	7474	4011	7160	0	4239
	Brahy.S09G0205800	86.267	2068	171	58	1	1996	10	2036	0	2141
	Brahy.S09G0205800	93.083	824	51	6	3187	4006	2412	3233	0	1201
	Brahy.S09G0205800	85.09	389	37	9	2760	3148	2044	2411	2.81E-102	377
	Brahy.S09G0205800	87.013	231	15	6	4063	4292	3253	3469	8.26E-63	246
BdTR6g_Brahy.D05G0346000	Brahy.D05G0346000	99.628	2149	8	0	1	2149	1	2149	0	3925
	Brahy.S09G0266900	89.456	1802	155	20	158	1946	146	1925	0	2242
	Brahy.S09G0266900	95.652	46	2	0	71	116	81	126	1.17E-11	75